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GLOBAL SOLUTIONS**

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FORMS AND METHODS OF MANAGING COMMUNICATIONS IN A COMMERCIAL COMPANY IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract. *The article discloses the conceptual aspects of communication management, constituting the foundation for practical management of communication processes in a commercial company. Classification criteria of communication management forms and methods for managing them are identified. The interrelation of decisions on the selection of forms and methods of communication management in a company within the context of the digitalization of the economy is substantiated.*

Keywords: *communications, communication management, commercial company, classification, forms and methods of management, digital economy.*

The relevance of this study lies in the fact that despite a substantial body of work by both domestic and international scholars in the theory of communication management, the issue of selecting appropriate forms of communication management for a specific company remains controversial [1; 2; 3; 4; 5]. At present, specialists in the field of communications rarely address the issue of developing a comprehensive set of communication management forms; accordingly, it is appropriate to clarify this concept and propose a theoretically substantiated classification of forms and methods for managing communications within a company.

The forms of communication management should be understood as the practical expression of a company's communication activities in specific actions undertaken by a manager within the limits of their competence, which produce various consequences. The forms of communication management essentially reflect their content. They offer insight into how management is practically implemented and communication tasks are addressed. In fact, this concerns how the very process of the company's communication activity is conducted [6, p. 61].

The choice of forms of managing communications directly depends on the management methods employed by the company's leadership within the framework of its strategic and operational management. Academic literature presents interesting

findings from domestic and international research on methods of managing communications at the organizational level [7; 8].

The significance of information and communications continues to grow in the current stage. Scientific and technological developments, as well as changes in the political and economic environment, compel managers to adopt increasingly newer and more sophisticated methods in their work related to information and communications. An effective management system is one characterized by advanced communications, whereby managers grasp the core of the communication process, possess strong oral and written communication skills, and understand how the environment influences information exchange. Among the studies addressing issues of communication within organizations, it is essential to highlight the works of T. Yu. Anopchenko [9], E. B. Doronina [10], V. A. Konovalenko, M. Yu. Konovalenko, N. G. Shved [11], E. S. Yakhontova [12], and others.

From the standpoint of a company's management activities, information constitutes a set of data concerning the state of the managing and managed subsystems, as well as the surrounding environment. Information underpins the cyclically recurring management process, which involves obtaining and processing data about the state of the managed object and transmitting control commands to it [13].

In the management process, the primary function of information is to eliminate uncertainty. Information enables the organization of business processes and their alignment with the external environment and the internal needs of the company. By eliminating or reducing uncertainty, information determines the firm's strategy and the means of achieving the established objectives [14].

Information is inextricably linked to the company's communication processes, on which the effectiveness of operational decision-making depends. If information flows within the company and its connections with the external environment are disrupted, the very existence of the company is endangered. Information alone is insufficient. Only when it is properly transformed and processed, i.e., when communicative connections are established, is the existence and effective functioning of the company ensured [15].

The modern company management system consists of two subsystems: the managing subsystem (management subject) and the managed subsystem (management object), which are in constant interaction (Fig. 1) [16].

Communications between the managing and managed subsystems are carried out through direct and feedback channels. Managerial decisions, orders, directives, and instructions are transmitted to the managed subsystem through direct communication channels, where the necessary influence is exerted. Feedback channels transmit the response to the directives received, including information regarding inaccuracies, imperfections, and deviations. After which a new managerial decision is formed within the management system. Thus, the system operates within a closed management loop [17].

Fig. 1. Positioning of information and communications in the company management process

The primary objectives of organizational communications are to ensure effective information exchange between the objects and subjects of management, between the organization and its environment, to enhance interpersonal relationships in the process of information exchange, to establish information channels for exchanging data between individual employees and groups and to coordinate their tasks and actions, as well as to regulate and rationalize information flows.

To detail the communication management process, it is necessary to identify the most significant aspects of the object, which constitutes the foundation for constructing a conceptual model. For this purpose, the existing communication system must be examined. From a technical perspective, it can be represented as an information and communication system (landline telephone lines, mobile phones, the Internet), comprising hardware, software, communication channels, and networks. This element significantly influences the speed of information transmission within the system and directly affects its quality. It is one of the most dynamic communication subsystems, as information and communication technologies (ICT) undergo significant changes due to the development of technical and software components.

Within the communication process, information is the key element, as it passes through several stages of transformation: encoding and decoding, during which its

structure and meaning may change. Access to reliable, complete, and consistent information within the company and from the external environment substantiates the necessity of including the informational component in the company's communication system. This component is capable of providing the company with both internal and external information.

The social dimension of the communication system must also not be underestimated. This is due to the fact that automation and cybernetization of business processes in companies in Russia remain relatively low; consequently, labor resources play a key role in determining the effectiveness of communications within the company. Components of the social communication system include personnel qualifications, education level, professional development, and psychological factors.

Researchers highlight an additional component of the modern corporate communication system – the managerial component, which encompasses management functions and methods designed to systematize business processes and technological operations accompanying the company's activities. At the same time, the lack of order in the performed operations impedes the establishment of an effective automated communication system.

The components of the communication system outlined in the literature sufficiently reflect operational effectiveness; however, it is necessary to complement them with an organizational component as well [18]. The organizational structure of the company has a significant impact on the number of communication interactions between and within management levels. The quality of information changes depending on the number of management levels. Therefore, the optimal nature of the company's existing organizational system holds considerable importance.

Thus, the communication system is a set of interconnected elements (technical, informational, social, managerial, organizational) that ensure the processes of informational interaction both within the organization and with the external environment, aimed at achieving the company's objectives [19, p. 120]. The system between the recipient and sender of communications, comprising technical, informational, social, management, and organizational components, is presented as follows (Fig. 2). The flow of information between the internal and external environments of the company from different components of communication systems varies in intensity.

The informational component of the communication system receives information from the external environment regarding competitors, markets, products, services, and legislation; in response, it provides information about products, services, and advertising. In this component of the communication system, the intensity of received and transmitted information is essentially equal.

The managerial component obtains information from the external environment about existing and new management systems, while in turn providing information regarding the company's policy and strategy. The technical component of the

communication system transmits an information flow to the external environment several times greater than the flow entering the company's internal environment. This is due to the company's lack of interest in disclosing information about its existing software and hardware; consequently, feedback is provided exclusively to technical support services and developers of new information technologies.

- 1 – information about existing and new information and communication technologies, software;
- 2 – technical support for developers and providers of information and communication technologies;
- 3 – information about products and services, advertising;
- 4 – information about competitors, markets, products, services, legislation;
- 5 – information about existing and new management systems;
- 6 – information about the company's policy and strategy;
- 7 – information about personnel, labor legislation, and the state of the labor market in the country;
- 8 – information about working conditions.

Fig. 2. Company communication system (Author's design)

Similarly, information exchange occurs between the social component of the communication system and the company's external environment. The system receives information concerning personnel, labor legislation, and the overall condition of the labor market. Conversely, only information about working conditions is transmitted in the reverse direction for the purpose of attracting new employees. The

organizational component of the communication system does not interact with the external environment, while ensuring the interconnection among the social, informational, technical, and managerial components. Thus, the analysis of the existing communication system within the company enables the identification of inherent deficiencies in each component individually, as well as in the system overall.

Each component of the system can be evaluated according to the established criteria: technical component: 1) hardware; 2) software; 3) communication channels; social component: 1) staff qualification; 2) psychological characteristics; 3) social interactions; organizational component: 1) functionality; 2) the set of tasks assigned to employees of the departments; informational component: 1) external information support; 2) internal information support; managerial component: 1) management functions and methods.

The management of company communications must be systematic, ensuring the comprehensiveness and balance of the individual performance indicators of their activities. For this purpose, a dedicated mechanism for managing information and communications must be developed and implemented within the company's management system [20].

The elements of the mechanism for managing information and communications comprise the object of management, as well as the goals, functions, methods, and structures of the management subject. Since the mechanism for managing information and communications is formed based on a systemic approach, its object and subject must be clearly defined [21]. The object of management is the communication system, comprising social, managerial, informational, technical, and organizational components. The management entity comprises communication management leaders, each of whom exerts influence through the implementation of their respective functions. The management entity generates a controlling influence in the form of an order, command, or signal, which is transmitted to the object of management. According to the systems approach, the mechanism for managing information and communications may be generally represented as follows (Fig. 3):

The management mechanism is an open system, receiving resources as input and delivering unused and transformed resources to the external environment as output. The influence exerted on the control object, namely the communication system, is also part of the mechanism's output. The mechanism for managing information and communications is included within the company's internal environment. Accordingly, the specifics of its components can be determined in accordance with the characteristics of the particular company. The elements of the mechanism individually do not possess the properties that their aggregate exhibits; that is, there is an emergent property whereby the aggregate of certain elements exhibits a different set of properties that manifest only through their combination [22].

Fig. 3. General View of the Information and Communications Management Mechanism (Author’s Development)

The primary task of the mechanism is to establish the process of managing company communications. In accordance with the primary objective, the purpose of the mechanism for managing information and communications is as follows: the establishment of criteria for evaluating the communication system of companies and ensuring its adequacy in relation to the evolving external and internal conditions of activity; the adoption of operational managerial decisions; ensuring the effective circulation of information within the communication process; the implementation of incentives aimed at enhancing communication effectiveness; distribution of responsibilities among the subjects of communication management [14].

The graphical model of information and communication management within the company constitutes a combination of organizational and economic forms, structures, methods, and management tools that enable informed decision-making and the implementation of necessary interventions at all stages of communication management to ensure their effectiveness (Fig. 4).

The main stages of managing information and communications are (Fig. 4): study of information and communications, including the determination of needs for internal and external communications; diagnosis of the existing communication management system; formation of the management mechanism for the communication system; ensuring the operation of the communication management mechanism; development of indicators for evaluating the effectiveness of the communication system; evaluation of the effectiveness of the communication management mechanism.

Fig. 4. Graphical model of the formation of the mechanism for managing information and communications in companies (Author's development)

Thus, for companies operating in the digital economy, information becomes an integral component of managerial activities, as well as a production resource capable of enhancing the company's operational efficiency. The primary objective of the communication process is to ensure understanding and accurate perception of the transmitted information; to achieve this, it is necessary to eliminate noise arising during information exchange by improving feedback mechanisms, regulating information flows, filtering information, and optimizing the structure of the

communication process. Based on a systems approach and the principles of modeling complex economic systems, a management model for company information and communications was developed. This model encompasses the analysis of communication requirements, assessment of the existing communication system, forms and methods of communication management, as well as the evaluation of the effectiveness of information and communication management.

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**THE RETURN OF SCIENTIFIC SCHOOLS AND INSTITUTES
OF ANALYSIS AND EVALUATION AS THE BASIS FOR
A SUCCESSFUL IMPORT SUBSTITUTION POLICY:
IN ANTICIPATION OF THE IRANIAN STORM**

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Abstract. *The article examines theoretical approaches to import substitution policies both globally and in Russia, providing forecasts across various scenarios for high-tech sectors in anticipation of the looming global economic crisis triggered by developments in the Islamic Republic of Iran.*

Keywords: *import substitution, Russia, USA, China, EU, robot-humanoid order, sanctions, scientific schools, evaluation institutes.*

The task of developing approaches to the theoretical conceptualization of import substitution industrialization (ISI) policy in contemporary economic thought has undergone a qualitative transformation, evolving from classical protectionist measures to sophisticated strategies for securing technological sovereignty. In the widest sense, the essence of import substitution consists in implementing a set of government measures aimed at stimulating domestic production of goods and services to replace imported products in the domestic market¹.

The fundamental basis of this strategy is rooted in Friedrich List's concept of 'educational protectionism,' who argued that developing countries cannot compete with industrial leaders without temporary protection of their 'infant industries' through tariffs and subsidies. In the mid-20th century, this idea was further developed by the structuralist theory of Raúl Prebisch and Hans Singer, who justified the necessity of import substitution as the sole means to overcome the

¹ Import substitution definition [Electronic resource] // Fiveable: Educational portal.– 2024.– URL: <https://fiveable.me/key-terms/international-economics/import-substitution>

‘commodity trap’ caused by the long-term deterioration in the terms of trade for natural resource-exporting countries¹.

Between 2020 and 2025, the essence of import substitution is being reinterpreted within the context of global instability and the crisis of the classical division of labor model. Modern scholars emphasize that contemporary import substitution is not a pursuit of complete autarky but rather a mechanism to minimize risks amid the fragmentation of the global economy and the disruption of cross-border value chains. While the classical import substitution model of the 1950s through the 1980s focused primarily on consumer goods, the current phase is distinguished by a focus on ‘capital’ and ‘innovative’ import substitution. This signifies a transition to the production of high-tech equipment and software. Academic literature highlights that the success of contemporary import substitution industrialization directly hinges on the state’s capacity to integrate it with an export-oriented strategy, as exemplified by the experiences of China and India, where domestic market substitution served as a ‘springboard’ for the subsequent global expansion of national IT giants^{2,3}.

The goals of import substitution policy in the contemporary economy are inherently multi-level and interdisciplinary. At the macroeconomic level, the primary objective remains achieving balance of payments stability by reducing foreign currency expenditures on import procurement and stimulating domestic economic growth through the multiplier effect in industry. However, in recent years, strategic goals related to ensuring national security have taken precedence. Global challenges, including the pandemic and geopolitical tensions, have exposed the vulnerabilities of countries dependent on imports of critical technologies such as semiconductors, active pharmaceutical ingredients, and operating systems. In this context, the primary objective is to achieve technological autonomy, enabling the state to sustain stability in governance and essential services even amid external isolation. The social objectives of the policy encompass not only the creation of new employment opportunities but also a qualitative transformation of the labor market structure through fostering demand for

¹ Chervinski, YA. Import Substitution Policy: Concepts, Analytical Methods, and Key Areas for Improvement [Electronic resource] // *RRSociology: academic journal.* – 2012 (rev. 2022). – URL: <https://rrsociology.ru/en/journal/article/358/>

² Tyukavkin, N. M., Anisimova, V. Yu. Processes of Import Substitution in Russian Industry: Theoretical and Practical Aspects [Electronic resource] // *Scientific Journal «World of Science».* – 2023. – URL: <https://www.mir-nayka.com/jour/article/download/1412/978>

³ Successful Import Substitution Policies [Electronic Resource] // *FasterCapital: Analytical Portal.* – 2025. – URL: <https://fastercapital.com/topics/successful-import-substitution-policies.html>

highly skilled engineers and developers, thereby contributing to the preservation of human capital and the prevention of ‘brain drain.’¹²³

The instrumentarium for implementing import substitution policy in the period 2020–2025. Represents a complex synthesis of administrative, financial, and institutional mechanisms. Traditional tariff instruments encompass customs duties and quotas, which create an artificial price barrier against foreign goods, thereby rendering domestic counterparts more attractive to consumers. Nevertheless, in contemporary practice, non-tariff measures – such as technical regulations, certification systems, and sanitary standards – are deemed more effective, often functioning as covert instruments of market protection. Financial instruments play a particularly important role: preferential lending through specialized development institutions, direct government subsidies to cover R&D expenses, and tax policy measures (for example, reductions in profit tax and insurance contributions for the IT sector). These measures help reduce financial risks for companies developing the production of fundamentally new products for the national market^{4,5}

Institutional instruments have become the most dynamically evolving component of import substitution policy in the 2020s. One of the most critical mechanisms is government procurement, within the framework of which strict priorities are established for domestically produced goods. In addition, localization requirements for foreign investors are being actively enforced, compelling multinational corporations to relocate technological cycles domestically and transfer competencies to local specialists. In the most advanced frameworks (such as the ‘Self-Reliant India’ strategy or the Chinese ‘Made in China 2025’ plan), the state also assumes the role of coordinator in the development of innovation clusters

¹ Boyko I. V. The technological component of the import substitution policy in Russia // *Innovations*. 2016. No. 1 (207). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tehnologicheskaya-sostavlyayuschaya-politiki-importozamesheniya-v-rossii>

² India’s Industrial Policies: Rejecting the Old Status Quo [Electronic resource] // Council on Foreign Relations (CFR).– 2025.– URL: <https://www.cfr.org/article/indias-industrial-policies-rejecting-old-status-quo-and-creating-new>

³ Yakushev N. O., Ustinova K. A., Kochnev A. A. (2024). Import substitution as a factor in the development of domestic digital technologies // *Economic and Social Changes: Facts, Trends, Forecast*. Vol. 17, No. 3, pp. 82–101. DOI: 10.15838/esc.2024.3.93.5 – URL: <http://esc.vsc.ac.ru/article/29993/full>

⁴ Examples of successful import substitution strategies [Electronic resource] // *FasterCapital*.– 2024.– URL: <https://fastercapital.com/topics/examples-of-successful-import-substitution-strategies-in-developing-countries.html>

⁵ Abdikeev N. M. Import substitution in high-tech industries under external sanctions. *Management Sciences*. 2022;12(3):53–69. <https://doi.org/10.26794/2304-022X-2022-12-3-53-69>

and technoparks, where small technology companies gain access to infrastructure and guaranteed demand from large state-owned corporations. Thus, modern instruments of import substitution policy are aimed not so much at mechanically closing borders as at creating a competitive environment that encourages national businesses to achieve a technological breakthrough^{1,2}

The theoretical justification of the importance of technology for economic growth can be traced back to Robert Solow's neoclassical model, wherein technological progress serves as the 'residual' explaining that portion of economic growth which cannot be accounted for by simple increases in labor and capital inputs. Subsequently, endogenous growth theories (Paul Romer, Robert Lucas) advanced this thesis by postulating that investments in knowledge and human capital generate positive externalities and non-declining marginal productivity, thereby enabling sustained long-term economic growth. In 2024–2025, these theories received new empirical validation: according to data from the Nobel Committee in Economic Sciences, the key factor explaining the divergence in wealth levels between countries is the ability of national innovation systems to generate and implement technological breakthroughs. In this context, it becomes evident that investments in fixed capital lose their effectiveness without the development of a knowledge-based economy. This generates a 'rut effect': states that have not fostered an environment conducive to innovation today confront an almost insurmountable technological gap in the future³.

Simultaneously with changes in production functions, high technologies by 2025 will fundamentally transform the employment structure and the demands placed on human capital. According to the World Economic Forum (WEF) report 'Future of Jobs Report 2025,' there is a shift from the concept of 'labor substitution' to that of 'augmented intelligence.' In high-tech industries, the critical factor for growth is not merely the availability of qualified personnel but the speed with which staff can be retrained and adapted to work alongside AI agents. This generates a new form of 'digital inequality': countries investing in adaptive education

¹ Ustyuzhanina Elena Vladimirovna, Novikova Ekaterina Sergeevna. Problems of Import Substitution and Approaches to Their Resolution under Sanctions Pressure // KE. 2023, No. 5. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/problemy-importozamescheniya-i-puti-ih-resheniya-v-usloviyah-sanktsionnogo-davleniya>

² Belykh S. IMPORT SUBSTITUTION AS A STRATEGY OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT // Magyar Tudományos Journal. 2020. № 41–2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/import-substitution-as-a-strategy-of-economic-development>

³ Sustained economic growth through technological progress [Electronic resource] // Nobel Prize: Detailed information on the Prize in Economic Sciences 2025. – URL: <https://www.nobelprize.org/uploads/2025/10/advanced-economicsciencesprize2025.pdf>

systems secure an additional annual productivity gain of 1.5–2% of GDP compared to technological laggards. Thus, the contemporary technological race is primarily a race of educational models, where success is determined by an individual's capacity to effectively interact with machine intelligence¹.

One of the most significant features of high technologies in the 2020s has been their influence on global GDP. According to expert forecasts, the scale of the digital economy will reach approximately 24 trillion US dollars by the end of 2025, representing about 21% of the total global GDP. The key driver behind this trend is artificial intelligence. Analytical reports from the McKinsey Global Institute (MGI) for 2025 highlight that generative AI has emerged as a new productivity frontier, capable of contributing up to \$ 19.9 trillion in cumulative value to the global economy by 2030. Moreover, the principal influence of these technologies is realized through the automation of cognitive tasks and the optimization of value-creation chains, which enables leading companies (the so-called 'standout firms') to significantly outpace competitors in operational efficiency metrics. Such a significant impact is attributable to overcoming the 'productivity plateau' through automation of cognitive labor, which enables companies to advance towards hyper-personalization of services and a radical reduction in transaction costs^{2,3}.

A crucial financial mechanism for the advancement of high technologies has been the emergence of the DeepTech investment sector. By 2025, the structure of R&D financing shifted from purely government subsidies to complex public-private partnerships. Investments in 'deep penetration technologies' (quantum sensors, nuclear fusion, neurointerfaces) have come to be regarded as long-term assets with a high multiplier effect. According to data from Crunchbase and PitchBook for 2024–2025, the volume of global venture deals in the climate technology and biotech sectors has for the first time exceeded investments in traditional software (SaaS), reflecting a reallocation of capital toward solving fundamental physical and biological challenges. This shift confirms the readiness

¹ Future of Jobs Report 2025 [Electronic resource] // World Economic Forum.– 2025.– URL: <https://www.weforum.org/reports/future-of-jobs-report-2025>

² Digital Economy Trends 2025 [Electronic resource] // Digital Cooperation Organization (DCO).– 2024.– URL: <https://dco.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/Digital-Economy-Trends-2025.pdf>.

³ McKinsey Global Institute: 2025 in charts [Electronic resource] // McKinsey & Company.– 2025.– URL: <https://www.mckinsey.com/mgi/our-research/mckinsey-global-institute-2025-in-charts>

of the global market for extended payback cycles aimed at achieving significant technological breakthroughs¹.

Therefore, Russia's achievements in import substitution, as well as in the restoration of scientific schools and specialized evaluation institutes within each ministry and agency – destroyed during the turbulent 1990s – provide us with an opportunity to secure a respectable position in the emerging robot-humanoid paradigm and to return to a nationally oriented policy focused on endogenous capabilities.

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¹ The State of Deep Tech 2025 [Electronic resource] // BCG & Hello Tomorrow. – 2025. – URL: <https://www.bcg.com/publications/2025/state-of-deep-tech>

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DEVIATIONS AS A FACTOR OF ANOMIE IN THE SOCIAL ARCHITECTURE OF INNOVATION ACTIVITY

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Abstract. *This article elucidates the nature and specific features of deviant relations as a factor of anomie within the social architecture of innovation activity; it further details the content and specific manifestations of these deviant relations and proposes an integrated approach to developing mechanisms for their elimination.*

Keywords: *deviations, innovation, innovation process, innovation activity, social architecture, anomie, principles, management, elimination strategies*

The social architecture of innovation activity constitutes a complex system that ensures the necessary prerequisites, conditions, and factors for the effective development, piloting, implementation, and commercialization of innovations. It is a dynamically evolving system in which economic mechanisms are integrated with social factors. Its effectiveness depends on the coordinated interaction of all

component elements, institutional flexibility, and the consideration of the strategic social effects associated with the implementation of innovations.

One of the key social and economic problems in the innovative development of society is deviant behavior and anomie within the social architecture of innovation processes. Anomie in the social architecture of innovation processes fundamentally constitutes a systemic normative-institutional crisis in the functioning of a complex of social institutions, mechanisms, and other social factors that ensure the successful development, testing, and adoption of innovations, as well as enhancing the overall efficiency of the innovation activity system. [6]

Anomie typically emerges as a result of a systemic imbalance among goals, directions, and instruments, alongside the weakening and inefficiency of the activities of various institutions, which ultimately leads to the degradation and disorganization of innovation processes. This phenomenon is often underpinned by deviant relations that arise during the course of innovation activity. These deviant relations reflect the characteristics of interactions among participants in the innovation process and are marked by deviations from generally accepted norms and stereotypes, often conflicting with the individual interests of both innovation process participants and society as a whole. [1]

Deviant relations within innovation activities may manifest as:

- violation and disregard of various regulatory and legal acts;
- opportunism and manipulation;
- resistance to and sabotage of changes;
- aggressive competition for scarce resources;
- creative deviance;
- simulation of innovation activities;
- mimicry and retreatism;
- ritualism;
- illegal innovative solutions, among others [2].

As a result of the manifestations of deviant relations during the innovation process, control is typically lost, disorganization and conflicts occur, reputational risks arise, and efficiency declines, among other negative consequences [7].

Deviations frequently result from inequality and power struggles and arise in conditions of weakening and/or breakdown of social norms, as well as from conflicts between cultural objectives and the available means for their attainment. They typically manifest and intensify when society assigns corresponding labels to individuals as violators. Any occurrence of deviation represents a form of opposition by individuals or groups to established norms, values, traditions, social patterns, or the prevailing system as a whole.

The most common deviations in relationships within the sphere of innovation activity result from:

- the specific outcomes and features of certain innovations, as well as their perception by particular social groups, employees, and organizations;
- contradictions between proponents and opponents of innovations, along with employee passivity stemming from a lack of interest in innovations;
- resistance to innovations or their misunderstanding by employees or managers in situations related to the innovation process;
- various types of innovation conflicts, destructive and adaptive professional deformations, etc.

The formation and development of deviations in innovation activity are influenced by numerous external and internal factors.

External factors include:

- instability of legislation in the innovation and economic sectors. This instability affects investment conditions and profit utilization, etc.;
- unforeseen external economic factors (including inflation, taxation, and changes in the industry);
- increased competition intensity (leakage of confidential information, imperfections in marketing policy, etc.);
- external economic risks (possibility of imposing trade and supply restrictions, border closures), and the like.

Internal factors contributing to the emergence of deviant negative relations in innovation activity include:

- scientific and technical risks (negative outcomes of research and development (R&D), deviations in development parameters, mismatch between the technical level of production and the technical level of the innovation, delays in the implementation of design stages, etc.);
- legal support risks of the project (erroneous selection of patent protection, failure to obtain or delay in patent protection, etc.);
- commercial proposal risks (misalignment with market strategy, absence of necessary suppliers, etc.);
- organizational risks (lack of clear plans, insufficient justification of goals and objectives, absence of proper communications, etc.). [4]

At the same time, positive deviations simultaneously motivate and guide creative behavior, which facilitates the development of innovation processes, the overcoming of routine, the creation of new models, and other departures from accepted norms that often become the starting point for establishing new standards. [3]

Negative deviations are deviations that hinder the functioning of social institutions and can obstruct innovation activity.

Negative deviant relations and behaviors in innovation activities typically refer to stable behavioral patterns of groups or individuals – participants in the innovation process – that do not conform to officially established or de facto generally

accepted norms or expectations (legal, moral, cultural, and group). In this context, such norms refer to existing laws and regulations, widely recognized moral and ethical principles, and rules of ethics.

Negative patterns of deviant relationships and behavior are frequently regarded as destructive. It is widely accepted that deviant relationships within innovation activities may lead to distorted perceptions of reality and social norms, superficial judgments, an inability to establish long-term objectives, assess the consequences of one's actions, and account for social contexts.

The established norm of requiring non-standard methods for problem-solving to achieve technological breakthroughs, for example, in IT and other fields that demand creativity and readiness to experiment, can become a fine line between a creative approach and the violation of norms, crossing which appears easy and does not require profound reflection. Disregarding established practices in pursuit of a quick and ambiguous outcome may be perceived as an inherent part of the innovation process.

Developers of new technologies confronted with ethical risks often resolve these by violating ethical standards, such as data breaches or the misuse of technologies involving private user data without consent; disruption of workflows under stringent time constraints or intense competition, where companies disregard standard security procedures, quality control, and so forth.

Although this may expedite innovation development, such behavior frequently exceeds established norms; disregard of these norms can result in serious consequences – from legal risks to damage to the company's reputation.

In some IT companies, cultural characteristics emerge in the form of a corporate culture, more precisely a subculture, which encourages informality, toxic communication and behavior, and even bullying, thereby violating traditional ethics and being regarded as a form of deviation in conventional companies.

Cultural relativism is also frequently linked to behavioral deviation, whereby social norms are not viewed as absolute but are considered relative phenomena contingent upon specific culture, social group, historical period, or context. This implies that what is considered a deviation in one group or society may be perceived as a norm in another.

In conditions of intense competition for resources, recognition, or market share, some participants may resort to actions that violate moral or professional norms. These circumstances arise from the conditions under which developers of innovative projects are compelled to operate: work tension reaching a stressful state in the absence of regulations governing the work process, as well as systems of control and sanctions in rapidly evolving knowledge-intensive fields and a transforming, changing external environment, which fosters a sense of impunity.

Dynamic and legitimate competition rapidly evolves into a phase of deviant social relations that contravene the ethical standards of professional communities

and even legal regulations, manifested in intellectual property theft, industrial espionage, sabotage, fraud, disinformation, and so forth.

Deviant social relations frequently manifest in outcomes detrimental to innovation activities, such as violations of legal norms, which are often perceived as threats to social order.

Research into the problem and characteristics of deviant relations in innovation activity has made it possible to define a conceptual framework for the restoration of the lost social order and the reinstatement of appropriate, scientifically substantiated social norms and rules within the sphere of innovation activity. This framework should be reanomy, understood as the development of a model for the social architecture of innovation activity, encompassing a comprehensive set of measures aimed at restoring and enhancing adequate models of innovation processes.

Based on the axiom that it is practically impossible to completely eliminate deviant relations, it becomes clear that the implementation of strategies for managing deviant relations within innovation activity should and can be approached on the basis of principles aimed at their elimination. [5]

The elimination of deviant relations in the field of innovation activity should constitute a system that ensures a balance of interests, thereby creating favorable prerequisites, conditions, and factors for the effective development of innovation activity in accordance with, and without contradiction to, socially significant moral norms.

The management of processes aimed at eliminating deviant relations within the sphere of innovation activity should encompass two primary strategic directions:

- the first direction involves the maximal feasible neutralization and suspension of the development of a socially and criminally oriented deviant relations at all stages of innovation processes;
- an additional direction entails the establishment of effective regulatory mechanisms for continuous monitoring, ongoing identification, and implementation of criteria that balance the interests of society and all participants in innovation processes in accordance with universally recognized moral and ethical values.

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NEW APPROACHES TO ORGANIZING STRESS TESTING AT INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. *This article proposes the establishment of a dedicated structural unit within industrial enterprises specifically for the stress testing of organizational functions and business processes. The proposed methodology for the real sector of the economy is based on stress-testing frameworks utilized in the financial sphere. However, unlike the banking sector – where the primary objects of stress tests are financial assets – the objects of stress testing at industrial enterprises are defined as key success factors (KSFs). This distinction constitutes the scientific novelty of this research. To implement these processes, an eight-step algorithm for conducting stress tests at enterprises is presented.*

Keywords: *stress testing, industrial enterprises, risk management, key success factors, autogenous crisis, organizational structure.*

Introduction

In the contemporary market economy, characterized by high volatility and permanent crises, industrial enterprises face numerous uncertainties that threaten their financial stability. Consequently, the task of early identification of critical vulnerabilities within an enterprise as a system has become increasingly urgent. Stress testing, as a method of applying extreme loads to an object, serves as a solution to this challenge.

The methodology for stress testing economic systems originated in the banking sector under the Basel II and Basel III standards, proving its efficacy as a preventive risk management tool in the financial sector. However, the direct extrapolation of “financial” approaches to the real sector is impossible due to the differences in testing objects and the specific nature of production processes.

The objective of this work is to develop methodological recommendations for creating a stress-testing system at industrial enterprises. The relevance of this study is driven by the lack of unified models for assessing the resilience of non-financial

organizations to extreme but plausible events. Implementing the proposed mechanism will allow management to not only diagnose latent contradictions in business processes but also to plan development strategies reasonably under conditions of uncertainty.

Methods and Materials

The methodological framework of this research consists of a synthesis of statistical analysis, correlation and regression modeling, and scenario analysis. The regulatory and methodological basis includes Basel II and Basel III standards [8], as well as recommendations from the Bank for International Settlements [9], the International Monetary Fund [10], the Central Bank of Russia [3, 4, 5, 6], and Russian Government decrees [7]. General scientific methods of analysis and synthesis, alongside scenario analysis, were also employed.

Results

The research resulted in the development of core approaches for forming a stress-testing methodology for the real sector, including a conceptual-categorical apparatus, identification of subjects and objects, a process algorithm, resource requirements, and a fundamental organizational structure.

1. Conceptual Framework and Subject of Stress Testing

The concept of stress testing in the financial sector is widely known. The Bank of Russia defines stress testing as “an assessment of the potential impact on the financial condition of a credit institution of a number of specified changes in risk factors that correspond to exceptional but probable events” [5].

While stress testing is well-defined in the financial sector as an assessment of potential impacts from exceptional but plausible risk factors, Devyatkin (2023) defines it for the real sector as:

“Stress testing of the real sector of the economy is a methodology for assessing the response and stability of a system under conditions of potential negative impact of given extreme scenarios in the form of changes in key success factors that correspond to exceptional but probable events and are aimed at identifying a critical level of resilience in order to develop a preventive crisis and risk management program.” [2].

Thus, unlike the financial sector of the economy, where stress tests focus on financial resources and related areas, in the real sector, stress testing is understood as a methodology for assessing a system’s response to negative impacts through changes in key success factors (KSFs). At an industrial enterprise, stress tests focus on functions and business processes such as administrative functions, procurement, logistics, production, marketing, sales, HR, and others. Each of these functions has its own KSFs, and by testing them under a given scenario, one can assess the overall stability of the enterprise as a whole system.

2. Organizational Structure and Leadership

Recognizing the increasing importance of risk assessment in an environment of increasing uncertainty, it is proposed to create a specialized functional unit for the effective implementation of the stress testing process.

The internal contexts for organizing this specialized unit include:

- **Management Subjects:** The CEO sets tolerance limits and risk appetite and decides on initiating tests and scenarios.

- **Hierarchical Accountability:** The unit reports directly to the CEO or the Vice President for Strategic Development.

- **Department Functions:** Coordination, methodology development, scenario analysis, econometric modeling, KSF monitoring, and reporting on probable crisis symptoms.

- **Delimitation of Powers:** The unit should be structurally separate from regular risk management and internal audit to avoid duplication.

3. Process Algorithm

The organization of testing involves eight sequential stages:

1. **Primary Data Collection:** Gathering sustainability data (GRI, ESG), financial statements, and official site data.

2. **Selection of Target Function and KSFs:** Visualizing processes and determining trends.

3. **Data Parameterization:** Creating statistical samples and removing outliers.

4. **Determination of Dependencies (Correlation):** Analyzing correlations and eliminating multicollinearity.

5. **Construction of Regression Models:** Testing equations for reliability and conducting variance analysis.

6. **Development of Scenario Conditions:** Selecting exceptional but plausible events based on historical trends.

7. **Determination of Extreme Indicators:** Conducting tests under set scenarios and determining “safety margins”.

8. **Summarizing Results:** Analyzing outcomes and issuing recommendations.

4. Interaction and Resources

The stress testing department is integrated into the company’s overall organizational structure, with defined vertical (between hierarchical levels) and horizontal interactions (with marketing, logistics, finance, legal, production, and other departments). Resource requirements include specialists in **Big Data**, programming, business analytics, and specialized software.

Discussion and Conclusion

The creation of a separate department will transform stress testing from a discrete, unsystematic, “mechanical exercise” for individual objects into a continuous strategic management tool. Establishing a permanent stress testing department

will help identify latent “bifurcation points” where standard risk management methods fail. The department’s primary success criterion is control over crisis situations at all stages of the organization’s lifecycle. The system’s effectiveness should be assessed annually through self-assessment and independent audit.

The ongoing integration of stress testing methods into internal and strategic planning, with subsequent stakeholder access to this information, will be a competitive advantage. Disclosing test results to external parties can significantly enhance the company’s investment appeal. Further research should focus on integrating artificial intelligence for real-time situation monitoring.

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THE SYSTEM OF PERSONNEL TRAINING FOR THE TOURISM SECTOR IN SWITZERLAND¹

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the system of personnel training for the tourism and hospitality industry in Switzerland. The role of the federal and cantonal levels of government in regulating the educational process is examined. Particular attention is paid to the practice-oriented approach to learning, including a high proportion of internships and the implementation of student business projects (using the example of the SBP program at EHL Hospitality Business School). The author investigates the mechanism of interaction between educational institutions, industry associations, and government structures such as the State Secretariat for Economic Affairs (SECO). Based on the analysis, key elements of the Swiss system that are of interest for adaptation in Russian practice are identified: dialogue platforms for coordinating stakeholders, the student business project program, and the decentralization of tourism education.*

Keywords: *Switzerland, personnel training, tourism, hospitality industry, practice-oriented learning, student business projects, decentralization of education, interaction with industry.*

Introduction. The modern tourism and hospitality industry places high demands on the quality of specialist training. Graduates must not only possess theoretical knowledge but also have practical skills for working in real business conditions. In this context, the experience of Switzerland is of particular interest, as its education system in the tourism sector is recognized as one of the best in the world due to the close integration of academic learning with the needs of the labor market. The

¹ The article was prepared within the framework of the state assignment of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Bashkortostan.

purpose of this article is to analyze the organizational structure and key operational mechanisms of the Swiss system for training tourism personnel. The work examines the role of federal and cantonal authorities in regulating the sector, explores the forms of interaction between universities and the business community using the example of student business projects, and identifies promising practices that could be adapted in the Russian education system to enhance its flexibility and relevance.

In the Swiss education system, the cantons play a key role in organizing and implementing education at all levels, except when it comes to university education. The Swiss education system has a decentralized structure and was formed according to the principle of federalism [1]. Cantons are responsible for the education system as long as the Federal Constitution does not grant legislative power to the cantons and the Confederation. Cantons, in turn, can cooperate to jointly solve tasks and for further coordination. This applies particularly to the areas of compulsory and higher education. Switzerland has 26 cantons, one of which is the Federal Switzerland [2]. The Swiss system of higher tourism education is centered around the practical experience of students. All training programs and courses in tourism and hospitality include a relatively high (up to 60%) component of student practice in the industry, providing opportunities for internships directly within the industry. As a rule, such internships are part of bachelor's and master's programs. This opportunity also exists in doctoral programs but is less common [3, 4].

The Swiss education system encourages and stimulates interaction with the industry. For instance, since 2000, EHL Hospitality Business School has run the SBP program (Student Business Project). This program aims to provide consultancy to businesses in the hospitality and service sectors. Its distinctive feature is that the consultants are students enrolled in hospitality and tourism programs. Since its launch, SBP has completed over 1,100 projects for 650 companies and currently handles between 80 and 100 projects per year [2]. The need to involve students in the project stems from the fact that students can offer innovative ideas and thus facilitate the transfer of knowledge from the academic environment directly to the industry. Also, while working on an SBP project, students gain a realistic picture of the business situation in the industry, familiarizing themselves with current problems and tasks they may encounter in the work environment [1]. The SBP project involves coordination between three parties: the client, a team of six final-year students, and two faculty members [5]. The client places an order for a project with the student group through the university. The students act as consultants in their areas of professional interest. Faculty members with expertise in the project's topic are appointed to supervise the students. They also monitor the quality of project execution.

During the business project, students propose ideas and innovative solutions, constantly communicating with clients who have approached them with an urgent problem. Interestingly, clients prefer that solutions come from students rather than

industry consultants. Teachers, although acting as supervisors and mentors for the students, do not participate directly in the project and have no contact with clients. Thus, SBP consulting services emphasize the key role of students as the primary participants in the business plans [5].

Programs like SBP are widespread in leading Swiss universities, representing one of the market mechanisms for training personnel for the tourism and hospitality industry. Government bodies regulating the country's policy in the tourism sector play a crucial role in the development of vocational education in Switzerland. Swiss tourism policy is developed and implemented by the State Secretariat for Economic Affairs (SECO). SECO interacts with political bodies at the national and regional levels, ensuring compliance with the Federal Act on the Promotion of Innovation, Cooperation, and Knowledge Building in Tourism. This organization also monitors two associations: Switzerland Tourism and the Swiss Society for Hotel Credit. The former is responsible for the marketing activities of Swiss tourism, while the latter supports investments in the hotel business [1]. Since tourism makes an important contribution to the economy of many cantons, each has a tourism office, with promotion carried out at the cantonal level. Switzerland also hosts an annual tourism forum, which fosters close interaction between the central government, cantons, and stakeholders in the tourism sector. Cantons and tourism associations play a key role in strengthening the labor market in tourism. For example, in 2017, the industry association *Hotelleriesuisse* launched a qualification campaign in the hotel business [5]. In this context, close cooperation between employers, industry associations, and responsible cantonal agencies is also important to simplify access to the labor market for local workers, including legally recognized refugees and immigrants with temporary residence permits in Switzerland. Collaboration among all players is crucial, so SECO assumes a stronger coordinating function. The main goal here is also to strengthen cooperation with the State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI), the Confederation's competence center for national and international issues of education, research, and innovation policy [2]. A platform for dialogue and coordination is an ideal tool for collaboration. The Switzerland Tourism Forum (TFS) is a national platform for interaction and dialogue among tourism business professionals. The forum provides an opportunity to form and coordinate working groups comprising representatives from various government levels, local cantonal administrations, invited industry experts, and academics.

Analysis of the personnel training system for tourism in Switzerland allows us to conclude that the following are of greatest interest for the Russian education system:

- **Dialogue Platform for coordinating stakeholder actions.**

Developing such a platform to address pressing issues in tourism and education would entail active interaction between government structures, representatives of the education system, and the tourism industry. This would help ensure the necessary

collaboration between representatives from different fields to identify current problems and work out solutions. This approach would lead to flexibility and timely responses to ongoing changes in education and tourism and would help ensure the relevance of the educational system concerning labor market needs, regarding the number of jobs and the training of necessary specialists in the tourism industry.

– **Student Business Project Program.**

Establishing such a program or its analogs would facilitate interaction between the education system and the tourism industry. Students could gain necessary experience and understanding of the industry before graduating, while business partners, in turn, could receive necessary consultations regarding theoretical and practical aspects of business operations. This approach could provide the education system with up-to-date information on the state of the tourism industry, while businesses could obtain current academic data from university representatives.

– **Decentralization of Tourism Education.**

Creating a decentralized (regional) system would provide additional flexibility and relevance in education and, consequently, in the tourism industry as a whole. This approach would help reduce the time needed to process information and develop necessary solutions, as regional authorities, dealing with their region's issues, have access to current information and can implement necessary changes locally in the shortest possible time. Thus, having analyzed the Swiss system of tourism education and identified mechanisms for interacting with the labor market and training relevant personnel for the tourism industry, it should be concluded that this system has a positive effect in the country and has proven itself internationally. The ideas of decentralization, development of business projects involving students and university scholars in the process of developing and making decisions in the industry could be implemented at the national and regional levels in Russia [6]. For more effective interaction between the tourism industry, government bodies, and the education system, it is relevant to hold an annual tourism forum as a dialogue platform within a practice-oriented approach to training tourism personnel.

Conclusion. The conducted analysis of the personnel training system for the tourism sector in Switzerland allows us to conclude that its decentralized model, based on the principles of federalism and close interaction among all stakeholders, is highly effective. Key success factors include: active state participation (through SECO and SERI) in coordinating educational and tourism policy; a high degree of practical orientation in training (up to 60% practice); the introduction of innovative working forms, such as the student business project program (SBP), which allows students to act as consultants for real businesses; and the existence of permanent dialogue platforms (e.g., the Switzerland Tourism Forum) ensuring communication between government, business, and academia.

The mechanisms identified during the research — decentralization of education management, creation of business projects involving students and scholars, and organization of annual forums for professional dialogue — represent valuable experience for improving the Russian system of tourism education. Implementing similar approaches in Russia at the national and regional levels will enhance the flexibility of the educational system, its ability to respond promptly to labor market changes, and, consequently, improve the quality of training for specialists capable of effectively addressing the current challenges of the tourism industry.

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**THE SYSTEM OF SPECIALIST TRAINING IN
THE FIELD OF HOTEL AND TOURISM BUSINESS
IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS OF FRANCE¹**

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***Abstract.** The article is devoted to the analysis of the system of professional training for the hotel and tourism industry that has developed in France. The article examines the structural features of higher education in France, where the prestigious Grandes Écoles, as well as public universities, occupy a key place. The work presents the characteristics of leading educational institutions providing training in the hospitality sector, including the University of Bordeaux, the international culinary school Le Cordon Bleu, the Vatel business school, and La Rochelle Business School. Special attention is paid to unique educational methods based on the inseparable connection of theoretical training with mandatory and intensive practice, internships in operating hotels and restaurants, as well as the interaction of educational institutions with leading players in the global market. The author highlights current trends and distinctive features of the French model of training managers for the hospitality industry, which make it one of the most sought-after and effective in the world.*

***Keywords:** personnel training system, France, hospitality industry, hotel business, tourism business, higher education, Grandes Écoles, professional training, internship, tourism management, practice-oriented training.*

Introduction. The modern tourism and hospitality industry places high demands on the level of professional training of personnel, which actualizes the need to study the most successful global educational models. France, being one of the leaders

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in the global tourism market and a recognized center of gastronomy and high-end service, possesses a unique and effective system for training specialists in this field. The French education system, combining centuries-old traditions with innovative approaches, is characterized by the presence of both public universities and elite *Grandes Écoles*, access to which is competitive. Diplomas from the latter are highly valued both within the country and abroad, facilitated by close partnerships between educational institutions and such global business giants as ACCOR, L'Oréal, and others. The aim of this article is to analyze the structure, methods, and key features of the French system of training personnel for the hotel and tourism industry using the example of the country's leading specialized educational institutions.

Currently, France is among the 20 most effective countries in terms of its economy due to the excellent outcomes of its professional higher education. Presently, France has 60 public and over 100 private universities. Access to prestigious schools, which include schools of hotel and tourism business, is through national competitions, for which candidates prepare through two years of intensive work in preparatory schools. Furthermore, tuition at *Grandes Écoles* is fee-based for both French citizens and international students. Ten of the country's *Grandes Écoles* that train specialists for the hospitality industry are among the most sought-after and prestigious. Diplomas from these institutions are valued much higher in France than those of university graduates. It is well known that France is one of the world's centers of gastronomy, renowned for high-end service in the hotel and tourism industry. Consequently, the country is one of the most popular destinations for students — future specialists in hospitality — not only for domestic students but also for applicants from around the world. The French education system is highly developed, modern, and, crucially, in demand. Not insignificant is the fact that France is one of the most economically developed countries in the world; business giants such as L'Oréal, Groupe Danone, Air France, BNP Paribas, ACCOR, Renault, Peugeot, Dassault, Bouygues-Construction, Total, Orange, France Telecom, EADS, Hennessy, Louis Vuitton, Dior, and Sanofi-Aventis originated here. Many of them are long-standing and reliable partners of French hospitality schools, offering students the chance to undergo internships or work placements, gaining invaluable knowledge and experience in France and many countries around the world [1, 2]. Among the public and private universities and schools, there are leaders in the field of training specialists for hospitality enterprises. One of the leading universities and the third most renowned, included in international rankings like Times Higher Education and the Shanghai Ranking, is the University of Bordeaux, founded in 1441 by Pope Eugene IV. The university has undergone numerous reorganizations: it was closed in 1793 and only resumed its existence in 1896. After the famous student unrest in France in 1968, by decree of the French Minister of Education Edgar Faure, the university was restructured, resulting in three autonomous universities:

Bordeaux I, Bordeaux II, and Bordeaux III. Having undergone many transformations, the institution was finalized in 2007, comprising four universities and three technical schools. Thus, the University of Bordeaux III includes three faculties, three institutes, and one doctoral school, “Montaigne and Humanities,” named in 1990 after the French writer and philosopher Michel de Montaigne. The Faculty of Territorial and Communication Sciences houses the “Planning, Tourism, and Urbanism” department, offering two bachelor’s programs in International Hotel Management and Tourism. The structure for training specialists in hotel and tourism management includes three years of study. The first year includes a six-month academic semester comprising a basic management course, including introductions to marketing fundamentals, human resources, management, professional culture, two weeks of professional practice in a school, restaurant, culinary, and banquet productions, as well as a four-month internship in France. The second year follows a similar schedule of theoretical study and practice, during which students encounter practical management situations by organizing work with first-year students and learning from the experience of third-year students, and also complete an internship at one of the 31 international VATEL schools, followed by a one-year internship abroad. The third year includes alternating academic study and professional practice, involving exposure to entrepreneurial skills, including an internship as an assistant manager at one of the hotels and restaurants of the VATEL company, which has partnered with prestigious hotels and restaurants (Grand Hotel Bordeaux & Spa, Mercure Hotel Cite Mondiale, Hotel Le Boutique & Wine Bar, Hotel & Spa Grand Barrail Saint-Emilion, L’O De L’HA), where students undergo internships, gaining experience and becoming highly qualified specialists. Upon completion of the three-year program, graduates are awarded a Bachelor’s degree in International Hotel Management, receiving the French state-recognized Certified Level II degree. Subsequently, successful graduates have the opportunity to continue their education in full-time, evening, correspondence, or online master’s programs. The awarding of a Master of Business Administration (MBA) degree in Hospitality and Tourism provides a significant advantage in securing leadership positions in international hotel and tourism businesses. The largest international school for training personnel in culinary arts and the hospitality industry is Le Cordon Bleu (founded in 1895, 20,000 students), encompassing 50 schools in 23 countries across 5 continents. The Le Cordon Bleu campus is located on the banks of the River Seine. The school’s origin is linked to the Order of the Holy Spirit, established in France in 1578. Knights of this order were required to wear the Cross of the Holy Spirit on a blue ribbon (cordon bleu). One version suggests these aristocrats were famous for their extravagant and luxurious banquets, which also came to be called cordons bleus. Although the lavish dinners ceased during the French Revolution, the term cordon bleu remained a synonym for excellent cuisine. According to another version, the

blue ribbon was synonymous with the highest quality in general, and in culinary arts specifically. Le Cordon Bleu offers students programs in culinary arts, pastry, baking, winemaking, and restaurant management. The training consists almost entirely of practical sessions: students are constantly in kitchens, demonstration halls, and sometimes on farms or at markets, learning to select the best ingredients for future masterpieces. The teaching staff includes world-renowned chefs, leading managers of major restaurants and hotels, Michelin-starred chefs, and famous culinary historians and critics. After studying at Le Cordon Bleu, a student can obtain the following levels of professional education: diploma and advanced diploma, certificate (for cooks and pastry chefs across 3 levels: from beginner to advanced), and sommelier diploma. The best students undertake internships in one of the Michelin-starred restaurants. Various seminars and advanced training courses, as well as thematic short-term programs useful for specialists at any level, are also regularly conducted. Throughout its 120-year history, Le Cordon Bleu culinary school has graduated tens of thousands of restaurateurs, pastry chefs, chefs, and wine specialists working in the finest French and international establishments. Among the school's famous graduates are chefs of Michelin-starred restaurants and acclaimed professionals such as Julia Child, Nancy Silverton, Nathalie Dupree, Bruce and Eric Bromberg, James Peterson, and others. Paris — the world capital of gastronomy, renowned for high-end service in the hotel and tourism industry. Students at Le Cordon Bleu Paris immerse themselves in the atmosphere of their future profession, gaining invaluable experience from professional chefs, establishment managers, and being in proximity to luxury restaurants and hotels. Le Cordon Bleu passes on culinary traditions to future generations while considering current trends, innovations, and new technologies, adapting curricula to the needs of the modern restaurant business.

Leaders in training specialists for the hotel and tourism sector include Vatel Business School of Hotel Tourism Management France (founded in 1950, 7,000 students) — one of the most famous and prestigious institutes for hotel and tourism business. The institute has 35 branches worldwide, but the French divisions are considered flagship institutions and serve as models for all other structural units. The university's two large French campuses are located in the cities of Nîmes and Bordeaux. Vatel Nîmes, which educates about 900 students from 45 countries, operates on a territory spanning over 14,000 square meters: a functioning four-star hotel, academic buildings and lecture halls, computer labs, and a comfortable residence for 400 people. Students have access to the spa and other common areas for relaxation and leisure. The second campus, Vatel Bordeaux, created in 1994 and educating about 600 students, is located in Bordeaux — a major cultural, financial, business, and university center in France. This city was named the “Ideal City” by the CSA Poll in 2015. The Vatel Bordeaux educational complex covers about 10 hectares in the historic Chartrons district:

at students' disposal are a functioning four-star hotel serving as a training base, the themed restaurant Les Tables Vatel (Global Tastes and Wines), and a spa center with a lounge bar. Students can study in French in Lyon and Paris, and in English in Bordeaux and Nîmes. Studying at the Institute guarantees a practical orientation of classes, a close connection between acquired knowledge and the realities of modern hotel business and management. The mandatory internships organized for students at each stage of study are also very beneficial. The annual work placement provides an opportunity to hone knowledge and skills, test them in practice in the best restaurants and hotels worldwide, build a professional reputation, and establish useful connections and contacts for future employment. Moreover, the practical training and internships organized in the second semester are paid, which helps reduce tuition costs. In 2016, in Paris, Vatel Business School of Hotel Tourism Management was named the best hotel school in the world by the XVII annual Worldwide Hospitality Awards ceremony. Today, Vatel Business School is a member of numerous prestigious international hospitality organizations: AMFORHT (World Association for Training Specialists in Tourism and Hospitality); EURHODIP (European Hotel Diploma Association); C.H.R.I.E. (Council on Hotel, Restaurant, and Institutional Education); F.Q.F. (France, Quality, Education); A.D.I.R.H. (International Association of Hotel and Restaurant School Graduates); EURHOFA (European Association of Hotel School Directors); I.H.R.A. (International Hotel and Restaurant Association). The private business school La Rochelle Business School (founded in 1988, 230 students + 400 international students) — located on the Atlantic coast, in the tourist-friendly green town of La Rochelle, 480 kilometers from Paris, trains highly qualified specialists in business, management, economics, and finance and is ranked among the best business schools in the world by the Financial Times. The school is an independent, non-profit research-type institution, accredited by the national Ministry of Education, and is part of a single educational complex together with La Rochelle University Institute of Technology and the School of Engineering (EIGSI). Today, the business school has campuses in New York, Helsinki, and Beijing. La Rochelle students can continue their studies at any of the business school's campuses. La Rochelle Business School combines excellent developed infrastructure, the quality and balance of academic programs, and the professionalism of experienced educators. Current specializations at the School of Business and Tourism include International Business; Tourism, Hotel, and Event Management; Sports Management; and Luxury Management. The prestigious business school offers students the opportunity to obtain Bachelor's, Master's, and MBA degrees, take Business Foundation courses or French language courses, and specialized business courses designed for professionals and top managers. Double degree programs allow students to study in both English and French.

Academic programs in business, hotel, tourism, and entertainment management are in the Top 10 of the national rankings. La Rochelle Business School holds the top position in the ranking of international business programs and is ranked among the top 100 best business schools in the world by the Financial Times. The quality of specialist training at La Rochelle is characterized by its high level, the balance of curricula, and the professionalism of experienced teachers. Classes are taught by practitioner-lecturers: about half of all teaching staff at La Rochelle run their own businesses. Students develop a fundamental understanding of the deep foundations of modern business processes and technologies, learning to develop and apply them. Each training program is constantly refined according to current business requirements, making education more valuable and practice-oriented. The main goal of education is to cultivate valuable personnel for the European labor market and to develop the international practice of student exchange. The innovative approach to learning aims to train modern, ambitious managers. La Rochelle students undergo annual internships in their specialty at any of the 173 partner universities in 48 countries worldwide. All training is focused on success and the application of innovative approaches, which guarantees subsequent successful employment and an excellent career in an international environment. 96% of La Rochelle graduates are employed by world-renowned companies such as Nestlé, Disneyland Resort Paris, Microsoft, and L'Oréal within 4 months of graduation. Thus, in the French higher education system in recent years, there has been a trend towards the development and implementation of a system of standards for training hospitality industry specialists, and criteria for the professionalism of hotel and tourism business managers at various stages of their development. A peculiarity of the French personnel training system lies in the fact that the need for parallel education is most clearly felt when training managers for hotel and tourism enterprises and organizations, implying the unity of managerial skills with in-depth knowledge in a specific field of activity. Tourism and hotel companies have recently begun to favor university graduates over specialists trained in prestigious French *Grandes Écoles*.

Conclusion. The conducted analysis allows us to conclude that the system of training specialists for the hotel and tourism business in France represents an established, effective, and dynamically developing mechanism. Its foundation is composed of prestigious *Grandes Écoles* and universities offering programs aimed at training highly qualified managers. A key feature of the French model is the harmonious combination of a fundamental academic base with a pronounced practical orientation of training. Mandatory and paid internships in the best hotels and restaurants worldwide, the involvement of active professionals and chefs in teaching, and the strategic partnership of educational institutions with industry leaders allow students not only to acquire relevant competencies but

also to build a successful career already during their studies. Schools such as Le Cordon Bleu, Vatel, and La Rochelle Business School have become recognized global brands in the field of education, confirming the high status of the French hospitality school. A current trend is the integration of managerial skills with in-depth knowledge in related fields, which contributes to the training of specialists capable of working effectively in the conditions of global competition and meeting the challenges of the modern economy [3]. France's experience in this area is of undoubted interest for improving national education systems in the field of tourism and hospitality.

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FROM “C5” TO “C6”: THE PROCESS AND DRIVERS OF THE EXPANSION OF REGIONAL MECHANISMS IN CENTRAL ASIA

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Abstract: *On November 16, 2025, at the seventh Consultative Meeting of the Heads of States of Central Asia, Azerbaijan officially became a full-fledged member of the “Consultative Meeting of the Heads of States of Central Asia”, expanding the Central Asian regional mechanism from the “Five-State Consultation (C5)” to the “Six-State Collaboration (C6)”. This marks another expansion of regional mechanisms in Central Asia, following the “C5+1” foreign ministerial dialogue mechanism. Employing research methods such as regionalism theory, this paper analyzes the motivations and characteristics of the expansion of Central Asian regional mechanisms on multiple levels, based on an overview of the development process and current status of these mechanisms from “C5” to “C5+1” to “C6”. The research indicates that the expansion of Central Asian regional mechanisms stems not only from external pressures of great power rivalry but, more fundamentally, from the practical needs of Central Asian countries to enhance their autonomous voice and address developmental challenges. This process reflects the expansion of outward linkages, the strengthening of strategic autonomy, and the enhancement of international participation.*

Keywords: *Central Asia; Mechanism Expansion; C5+1 Mechanism; C6 Mechanism*

According to a report by Kazinform, on November 16, 2025, Azerbaijan becomes full-fledged member of Consultative Meeting of Heads of Central Asian States, expanding the Central Asian regional mechanism from the “Five-State Consultation (C5)” to “Six-State Collaboration (C6)” [Arailym Temirgaliyeva, 2025]. This represents another expansion of Central Asian regional mechanisms, following the “C5+1” foreign ministerial dialogue mechanism. Mechanism expansion introduces new members and rules, which will profoundly impact the dynamics and pathways of cooperation between Central Asian countries and external states.

1. The Process of Expanding Central Asian Regional Mechanisms

1.1 Internal Five-State Consultation Mechanism — “C5”

The “C5” consultation mechanism among the five Central Asian states is a regional cooperation platform initiated and led independently by these countries, aimed at strengthening coordination and cooperation among them. Its member states include Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Uzbekistan. This represents the highest-level consultation mechanism within Central Asia today.

Previous “C5” Consultative Meetings

Meeting	Time	Location	Host Country	Main Topics
1st C5 Meeting	March 2018	Nur-Sultan (now Astana)	Kazakhstan	Connectivity, water resource management, energy cooperation, regional security
2nd C5 Meeting	November 2019	Tashkent	Uzbekistan	Multi-level mechanism development, logistics and energy corridor construction, cooperation in social welfare sectors
3rd C5 Meeting	August 2021	Awaza	Turkmenistan	Pandemic cooperation, regional supply chain stability, digital connectivity, water resource coordination
4th C5 Meeting	July 2022	Cholpon-Ata	Kyrgyzstan	Regional security, the situation in Afghanistan, economic and trade cooperation, infrastructure cooperation
5th C5 Meeting	September 2023	Dushanbe	Tajikistan	Regional security cooperation, economic integration, transport connectivity
6th C5 Meeting	August 2024	Astana	Kazakhstan	Strengthening scientific and educational cooperation, jointly addressing regional security challenges
7th C5 Meeting	November 2025	Tashkent	Uzbekistan	Mechanism development, security cooperation, connectivity, economic and digital cooperation, water resource utilization, rare earth element development

Source: THE EXECUTIVE COMMITTEE OF THE COMMONWEALTH OF INDEPENDENT STATES

1.2 External Great Power Dialogue Mechanism — “C5+1”

Current domestic and international academic and media circles commonly use the term “C5+1 mechanism” to refer to the cooperative framework between external actors and the five Central Asian states. This framework involves the five Central Asian countries acting as one entity, engaging with a single external partner country or integration organization based on principles of voluntariness, equality, and pragmatic cooperation. It constitutes a multilateral high-level dialogue and cooperation framework, with the core being the “5 Central Asian states + 1 external partner” model of dialogue and consultation, rather than an alliance or military bloc [Li & Zeng, 2025, pp. 69–86].

The “C5+1” cooperation mechanism was established with the first “C5+1” Foreign Ministers’ Meeting held by U. S. Secretary of State John Kerry with the five Central Asian states in 2015. This meeting was subsequently elevated to a Heads of State Meeting mechanism. Subsequently, India, Russia, China, Germany, and other countries established similar mechanisms, successively holding “leaders’ summits”. According to incomplete statistics, as of July 2025, 12 countries and organizations have created “C5+1 mechanisms” in Central Asia.

2025 could be described as the “Summit Year” for the “C5+1 mechanism” [Su & Guo, 2025, pp. 50–75]. In April 2025, the EU held its inaugural summit with Central Asia, announcing the establishment of a strategic partnership; in December of the same year, Japan hosted the inaugural Japan-Central Asia Summit. Additionally, China, Russia, and the USA held their second leaders’ summits with Central Asia as scheduled. Looking ahead to 2026, the inaugural ROK-Central Asia Summit and the second India-Central Asia Summit are scheduled to be held.

1.3 New Member Expansion — “C6”

On November 16, 2025, at the “7th Consultative Meeting of the Heads of States of Central Asia” held in Tashkent, the Republic of Azerbaijan was officially admitted as a full member of this cooperation mechanism, and it was decided that the “8th Consultative Meeting of the Heads of States of Central Asia” would be held in the “Central Asia + Azerbaijan” format. This decision marks an upgrade and transformation of the Central Asian regional cooperation model towards the “Central Asia + Azerbaijan” model (the “C6” model). Its areas of cooperation have simultaneously expanded to include new directions such as Trans-Caspian logistics, trade with Europe, and energy corridor development.

It is noteworthy that the Central Asian regional cooperation mechanism possesses certain particularities. It is a consultative mechanism built upon historical and cultural ties, common security concerns, and economic complementarity. As the first country outside the traditional Central Asian region to join this mechanism, Azerbaijan’s accession is not merely a simple expansion, but a result based on multiple practical interest considerations and long-term regional interaction.

2. Drivers of the Expansion of Central Asian Regional Mechanisms

2.1 External Pressures

Responding to great power rivalry and pursuing multi-vector balanced diplomacy. Facing this objective reality of great power rivalry, Central Asian countries participate in various “C5+1” dialogue mechanisms to implement a “multi-vector balanced diplomacy”. By maintaining cooperation with all major powers simultaneously, Central Asian states can maneuver among them, securing greater political support, economic assistance, and technological cooperation, thereby maximizing the protection of their national interests. For instance, while maintaining traditionally friendly relations with Russia, Kazakhstan actively develops energy cooperation with China, becoming one of China’s crucial energy suppliers [Wang & Su, 2025]. Uzbekistan, through the “C5+1” mechanism, engages in consultations with the U.S. on regional security issues while also collaborating with the EU on democratic reforms and economic development.

Promoting logistics and economic corridor development. On September 11, 2025, the Polish government closed all its land border crossings with Belarus, leading to cargo accumulation and transport congestion at the Poland-Belarus border [Gu, 2025]. Consequently, Central Asian countries urgently needed to explore alternative routes. The Trans-Caspian International Transport Route, known as the “Middle Corridor”, became a critical alternative.

Azerbaijan, bordering the Caspian Sea to the east, the South Caucasus to the west, and Turkey to the south, is the only country on the western Caspian shore possessing capabilities for both large-scale port operations and railway connectivity, occupying approximately 20% of the Caspian Sea’s shoreline and waters. Cooperation with Azerbaijan can effectively address the core challenge facing landlocked Central Asian states: the “lack of access to seaports”. Furthermore, the Caspian region benefits from favorable climatic conditions; the Port of Baku remains ice-free year-round, serving as a natural harbor. This ensures the possibility of year-round, normalized navigation along this transport route, guaranteeing stability of transportation.

For example, goods departing from the Port of Aktau in Kazakhstan can traverse 508 kilometers across the Caspian Sea to reach the Port of Baku in Azerbaijan, completing the crucial transition from “Central Asian land transport” to “South Caucasus land transport”. This forms a complete transport corridor along the “Middle Corridor”, linking China, Kazakhstan, the Caspian Sea, Azerbaijan, and Europe [Yang, 2025]. The upgrade to the “C6 mechanism” institutionalizes this cooperation, stabilizing collaboration between Central Asia and Azerbaijan and ensuring the reliability of “the Middle Corridor” route.

2.2 Endogenous Drivers

Enhancing strategic autonomy and regional voice. The admission of Azerbaijan represents a significant step taken by Central Asian countries to bolster strategic

autonomy and regional voice. As a crucial state linking Central Asia with the South Caucasus region, Azerbaijan possesses not only a unique geostrategic location but also abundant energy resources. By incorporating Azerbaijan, the Central Asian regional mechanism can not only expand its cooperation domains and strengthen ties with the South Caucasus but also form a larger combined force, enabling it to secure a more favorable position in interactions with external powers. For instance, in the development of Trans-Caspian energy corridors and logistics routes, Azerbaijan's participation will facilitate the integration of resources from Central Asia and the South Caucasus, enhancing the region's bargaining power in international energy markets and global supply chains. This, in turn, helps reduce dependence on any single external power and achieves a more balanced foreign and economic policy. The formation of "C6" empowers Central Asia with stronger collective bargaining power in dialogues with other major players.

Meeting practical developmental needs. Central Asian countries are currently facing urgent imperatives for modernization, infrastructure upgrades, and green transitions, necessitating foreign investment, technology, and market access. Foreign capital, in particular, constitutes a significant proportion of developmental funding in Central Asia [Yu, Hou, & Ning, 2025, pp. 1–20, 137]. Therefore, attracting participation from multiple parties becomes a natural choice driven by developmental necessities.

From a technological perspective, Kazakhstan, for example, possesses abundant rare earth element (REE) reserves but lacks advanced REE separation and deep processing technologies. Consequently, most of its rare earth resources are still exported as primary products, yielding limited economic benefits. Through cooperation with countries like China and Russia via "C5+1" mechanisms, Kazakhstan can introduce REE processing technologies, gradually expand its industrial chain, increase the added value of its resources and products, and thereby boost fiscal revenues. Furthermore, Azerbaijan's membership brings new market opportunities for Central Asian countries in Trans-Caspian logistics and trade with Europe. By jointly developing the Trans-Caspian transport corridor, Central Asian states can more efficiently export their energy, minerals, and agricultural products to European markets, expanding export volumes and optimizing trade structures.

The evolution from "C5 Consultations" to "C5+1 Dialogues" and now to "C6 Collaboration" clearly delineates the geostrategic development path of Central Asia since its independence. This transformation is not merely a product of Central Asian states responding to great power rivalry and blocked transit routes; its fundamental impetus stems from the pursuit of strategic autonomy, international discursive power, and the pressing needs of domestic economic development against this international backdrop. Compared to "C5+1", the "C6 mechanism" represents not only a geographical expansion but also a tangible manifestation of Central Asian states' proactive pursuit of deeper outward cooperation.

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IS PALLIATIVE CARE AN ALTERNATIVE TO EUTHANASIA AND SUICIDE?

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Abstract: *The article examines the issues of palliative care as an alternative to the use of euthanasia and the suppression of suicidal actions on the part of terminally ill citizens.*

Keywords: *palliative care, euthanasia, suicide, hospice.*

Introduction

One of the humane manifestations of the right to death is palliative medical care, as well as the establishment of hospices for terminally ill patients in Russia. The specific nature of the right in this case is that there is no talk of accelerating or delaying death. This is likely to be a dignified death in the eyes of many terminally ill individuals. This is because most of the measures, such as psychological, social, and other support, are aimed not only at the dying person but also at their family and loved ones. The relevance lies in the possibilities of palliative medical care, which is likely to contribute to solving the most difficult problems related to the right to die. This includes reducing pain and providing assistance to patients, which, in fact, is an effective prevention of suicide when considering each individual case. Palliative medical care does not contain any form of as a social phenomenon of negative attitudes, in contrast to euthanasia, suicide, and abortion, which cause negative reactions. In this regard, it should be noted that research on the right to death does not pay enough attention to palliative care, which is a significant disadvantage.

However, medical corporations pay enough attention to palliative care. At the same time, lawyers dealing with human rights issues often undeservedly ignore this issue. The main aspect of palliative care is to alleviate the patient's suffering, which can lead to euthanasia and suicide.

Suicide is severely condemned by religious and social norms, and an attempt to commit this act leads, at best, to compulsory psychiatric care. Because the person himself, for psychological and other reasons, often cannot commit suicide (for example, in the case of an incurable disease). With euthanasia banned almost everywhere, palliative care is often the only way to end life with dignity.

Unfortunately, appeals to the problem of palliative care are relatively rare in the legal literature. Legal aspects are more often addressed in medical or foreign literature.

In this regard, it would be appropriate to mention the monographic study by N.V. Ekkert on the state and problems of the development of palliative care in Russia. This issue is mainly addressed by medical professionals. It is also important to consider the ethical aspects of this problem. Palliative care services are being developed and provided, as well as the training of specialists on this basis, various organizations, both public and private, are formed to address this issue.

If we look closely, we can find a connection between suicide and palliative care. Effective palliative care can be an effective preventive measure against suicide. One of the doctor's responsibilities towards a hopeless patient is to alleviate their suffering, which is precisely what palliative care provides.

However, V.O. Babenko emphasizes the inadmissibility of euthanasia both in law and within the framework of medical ethics. Palliative medical care (PMC) is considered by this author to be a "universal" means of ensuring a dignified death.

In 1990, the WHO proposed a definition of palliative care. In 2002, it was published in a new edition. The WHO's definition of palliative care is an attempt to describe a standard of care that ensures the best quality of life for both patients and their families. It emphasizes the need to consider physical, psychological, social, and spiritual aspects.

E.A. Otstavnova believes that proper care for seriously ill patients will reduce the relevance of discussions about euthanasia. The author's analysis of international acts led to the conclusion that, despite the costs, the rights of terminally ill people need to be protected as much as possible.

It is also mentioned that the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe recommends providing a wide range of services, including care, hospitalization, ambulance services, and more, when providing palliative care. The wishes of patients themselves should be taken into account.

According to many scientists, hospices are the epitome of humanity. It is also emphasized that hospices do not bring death closer or further away, but rather create the most comfortable conditions possible.

However, it should be noted that the development of hospices is hindered by a lack of funding. Private hospices are highly expensive. According to many authors, public funding may face a shortage of funds due to high expenses. Thus, I.V. Kopeikin points out that death is often undeservedly overlooked in legal studies, which necessitates a focus on various aspects of morality and religion. While this is a valid observation, it is worth noting that the lack of legal material in legal studies on death issues often leads to a reliance on sociological and religious works, as can be seen in the relevant literature. Therefore, it is crucial to develop the legal aspects of death issues.

Few scientists who have studied the effectiveness of palliative care have noted that its shortcomings include the imperfections of Russian legal acts regulating the activities of the institutions that provide it, the competence of specialists, etc. Since palliative care has been developing in Russia since the mid-1980s, the first category of people to receive it were cancer patients. However, the development of this type of assistance is proceeding at a slow pace. According to I.V. Ponkin and A.A. Ponkina, it is still too early to talk about creating a full-scale system for providing palliative care and training relevant specialists.

In the context of medical advancements, the ideas of eugenics are once again being discussed, often causing horror and outrage due to the high cost of treating and caring for seriously ill individuals.

In our country, hospices were opened on the basis of the Order of the Ministry of Health of the RSFSR “On the Organization of Nursing Homes, Hospices, and Nursing Departments of Multidisciplinary and Specialized Hospitals” dated 01.02.91 No. 19.

There are guidelines for the organization of palliative care (approved by the Deputy Minister of Health and Social Development on September 22, 2008, No. 7180-RH).

Since the adoption of the order, the development of hospices has been carried out in two directions. Due to the acute need of patients with malignant neoplasms for effective pain relief, some hospices, having obtained licenses for the use of narcotic drugs and having adopted the philosophy of the hospice movement, began to provide specialized medical treatment mainly for cancer patients. Thus, hospices of a new type were organized (based on the model of English hospices), examples of which are hospices in the cities of Moscow, St. Petersburg, Kemerovo, etc.

However, there is no scientific literature on the sufficiency of these standards for providing palliative care in hospital settings. Despite the fact that the regulatory documents have some shortcomings, the authors state that there is a regulatory framework necessary for the organization and development of the primary health care system in the Russian Federation, as well as for planning this type of care, doctors continue to face incurable patients. Often in this situation, the doctor is

forced to continue treatment due to unwillingness to take responsibility or talk about the incurable nature of the disease. At the same time, it would be more correct to introduce a clear criterion for recognizing a person as terminally ill and transferring him to palliative care.

It would be fair to focus on helping the families and relatives of terminally ill citizens, such as providing psychological, volunteer, and other assistance. However, there is no legal regulation in Russian legislation regarding the mechanism for interacting with them. In general, there is a very low level of awareness among citizens about their rights in the field of palliative care. There is no mass information from the government, and social advertising resources are not being used. Representatives of non-profit organizations are trying to improve the situation. Citizens are poorly informed about their rights, such as the use of painkillers. The problem lies in the fact that the current legislation considers it a violation to mention narcotic drugs and encourage their use for medical purposes.

“Acceptance” as the final stage of the dying person’s psychological development is the spiritual foundation that allows the patient to die peacefully and with dignity. This is why the “principle of openness to diagnosis” is one of the key principles in the hospice concept.

The main problems that prolong the stay of patients in nursing beds are:

- waiting lists for inpatient social protection facilities for the mentally ill;
- long waiting lists for documents for placement in nursing homes, due to insufficient interaction with agencies subordinate to the Ministry of Internal Affairs (identification, passport issuance), and medical and social examination institutions (establishment of disability).

The structure of palliative medical care (hereinafter referred to as PMC) in St. Petersburg has been established in accordance with the procedures for providing PMC to adults and children, approved by the orders of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation dated 14.04.2015 No. 187n and No. 193n.

Palliative care for cancer patients is provided in 8 medical organizations in St. Petersburg, which have 245 beds. The average duration of treatment on palliative cancer beds in 2017 was 17.8 days.

One of the most important results of the work carried out was the introduction of amendments to the Social Code of St. Petersburg (Law of St. Petersburg dated 07/03/2017 No. 491-71), providing for the provision of certain categories of citizens residing in St. Petersburg who are registered at dispensaries in medical organizations subordinate to the executive bodies from 01.01.2018 at the expense of the budget of St. Petersburg. state authorities of St. Petersburg suffering from serious illnesses requiring life-threatening mechanical ventilation at home (hereinafter referred to as ventilator), equipment and supplies for ventilation at home.

The main problems in the field of medical treatment:

- absence of the position of an anesthesiologist-resuscitator in the procedure for providing CPR to the adult population;
- the absence of a day hospital and a home hospital in the procedures for providing primary health care to the population;
- the absence of equipment and supplies for home ventilation in the Federal List of Rehabilitation Measures, rehabilitation equipment and services provided to a disabled person (hereinafter referred to as the Federal List).

According to V.O. Babenko, in order to improve the legal mechanism for providing palliative medical care, it is necessary to amend the legislation, primarily by expanding psychological and other (non-medical) assistance. It is also important to develop educational activities and transfer certain powers and resources to public organizations.

Palliative medical care is proposed to be understood as the right to a dignified death and an alternative to euthanasia, both active and passive. It is necessary to develop the psychological aspects of palliative care for both seriously ill patients and their family members. At the same time, the role of civil society institutions and their funding is insufficient, and there are also shortcomings in the legal and organizational system of providing palliative medical care in Russia.

Conclusion.

Today, there is an active discussion about death. At the same time, death is considered both as a legal fact-event and as a legal fact-action. Deliberate self-destruction is a very ambiguous action, on the one hand, infringing on the fundamental and inalienable right to life, protected by the state, and on the other hand, due to obvious reasons, such actions are not illegal for the person who performs them on himself.

There is a change in values and ethical guidelines, including the right to control one's own life. Many legal issues related to death continue to remain unresolved in Russian law. One of the reasons for this is the ambiguity of the approach in science and law to the right to dispose of one's own life. In foreign legislation, there is a significant variety of approaches that require theoretical and legal analysis. . The problem of death in the theory and history of state and law continues to be relevant.

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TRANSFORMATION OF RUSSIAN CIVIL SOCIETY IN THE CONTEXT OF THE SPECIAL MILITARY OPERATION

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Abstract. *The relevance of this study stems from the fact that as the Special Military Operation enters the phase of a full-scale armed conflict, an increasing number of social groups become involved in the process of direct or indirect support of the Russian military and irregular units. Large-scale military operations and unprecedented sanction pressure, combined with aggressive anti-Russian propaganda, have become a genuine test of the civic qualities both of each individual Russian, as well as of society as a whole. The current military-political situation inevitably affected the process of transformation of civil society institutions, which was triggered by the collapse of the Soviet system and has been ongoing to the present day. The fact that an important factor in overcoming the foreign policy and particularly military threat is society's capacity for consolidation and constructive interaction with the state determined the objective of the research addressed in this article. The authors identify the transition of the Special Military Operation to the phase of full-scale confrontation with the Atlantic coalition as the reason for public activity, which necessitated augmenting the state's military organizational structure through volunteer irregular formations.*

The authors also consider, that despite the contradictory nature of the ongoing changes, the predominant trend of civil-state dialogue in the contemporary Russian Federation is becoming the sphere of military-civil relations. Subjects, who have established themselves as a connecting link between the army and the people, are capable of remaining effective actors in societal processes in Russia of the 21st century in the foreseeable future.

Keywords: *social transformation, social institutions, civil society, institutional changes, institutional traps, consolidation, trust, state power, military-civil relations, volunteers, armed conflict, civil society, volunteering, Special Military Operation.*

Momentous political events, unfolding recently before our eyes, affect not only the immediate moods and opinions of individuals, but also impact the deeper layers of societal consciousness. The existing military-political situation inevitably affected the course of transformation of civil society institutions — the large-scale military operations and unprecedented sanction pressure, coupled with aggressive anti-Russian propaganda, constituted a genuine test of the civic virtues both of each individual Russian, and of society as a whole. Our society, not yet fully recovered from the consequences of the post-Soviet crisis, found itself confronted with a new existential challenge. The changed circumstances inevitably affected the state of the social system and the course of transformational changes, however, the direction of this influence still requires further study and evaluation. We are visibly changing as a nation now. Moreover, this involves not only a shift in superficial attitudes, but a transformation of the deep layers of mass consciousness, which is unfolding against the backdrop of significant changes in the political, cultural, economic, technological, communication, and other spheres of contemporary life. After February 2022. Our perceptions of ourselves, of our country, of the world, of Russia's mission in this world have fundamentally changed. If during the years of Perestroika and the early post-Soviet period we regarded our country as backward in comparison to the “civilized” countries of the West, then today, despite, and, perhaps, precisely because of sanctions in the economy, and the military actions waged against our country by Ukraine and NATO, the majority of Russian citizens are turning inward toward themselves, experiencing a sense of pride in their country and self-respect. Since the beginning of the Special Military Operation (SMO), this process has accelerated sharply. Today, a reassessment of values is occurring in Russian society, both in foreign and domestic policy spheres, and, to some extent, a devaluation of the Western values previously espoused by our so-called ‘European partners’ — now direct enemies — such as freedom, democracy, and liberalism. Many citizens have observed, that the values of freedom in world politics are being replaced by the values of dictatorship, the values of democracy — by the values of Nazism and fascism — in the West, as well as in the East. Surprisingly, our Russian economy has demonstrated resilience, the entire economic system, established in the XXI century, despite unprecedented sanction pressure, has withstood a significant external shock, preserving numerous opportunities and considerable development potential. The conception of justice regarding the Special Military Operation has transformed Russian society, our entire way of life has changed over these four years. And, the most important aspect — civil society during the time of trials has

demonstrated maturity, obvious not so much and not only in the capitals and major cities, close to power and the so-called centers of decision-making, but above all in the regions, in the very fabric of popular life. Despite natural dissent, thousands of conspicuous departures, opposition, and even more so, the presence within the information space of the most overt enemies, we once again felt ourselves as a united people, consolidated in the face of danger. This feeling proved to be remarkably stable. The current consolidation of Russian society, which, undoubtedly, came as a very unpleasant surprise to our opponents, happened not through force, nor by orders from some-appointed organizers above, but almost spontaneously, born from a genuine popular feeling. It is obvious that these shifts affect different social groups in various ways, but today it is clear that we all already live in a completely different political reality, which influences the political behavior and consciousness of people at present and will continue to influence it in the future. Since the beginning of the Special Military Operation, all public opinion research conducted by both governmental and independent organizations demonstrates a high level of support expressed by Russian citizens regarding the decisions of the president and government adopted with the aim of denazification and demilitarization of Ukraine.¹

The results of the study demonstrated that in the process of transforming civil society institutions, several positive trends have clearly emerged, related to the increase in open interpersonal trust, the readiness for dialogue with state authorities, and societal consolidation. The level of citizens' agreement with the decision to commence the Special Military Operation in the first days of the operation stood at 65%, and according to the VCIOM survey dated 24.02.2024, t.e. Two years later, the figure reached 68%, while the necessity for each person to make a contribution feasible to the successful completion of the Special Military Operation was also expressed by 72% of Russians. A high level of trust in the president and the army

¹ Fedorov V. On Russians' attitude toward the Special Military Operation, the effect of consolidation around the flag // VCIOM. 18.05.2022. URL: <https://wciom.ru/sobytie/valerii-fedorov-v-intervju-rtvi-rasskazal-ob-otnoshenii-rossijan-k-svoehffekte-obedinenijavokrug-flaga> (accessed: 27.08.2024); Sociologists have created profiles of supporters and opponents of the Special Military Operation // RBC. 18.05.2022. URL: <https://www.rbc.ru/politics/18/05/2022/62825a8f9a794718a6e8560f> (accessed: 27.08.2024); Experts discussed the transformation of the hero's image in the consciousness of the nation's citizens//Lenta.ru. 21.07.2022. URL: <https://lenta.ru/news/2022/07/21/geroi/> (accessed: 27.08.2024); All-Russian survey of patriotic social groups regarding attitudes toward the Special Military Operation//Kharkov.ru. 19.09.2022. URL: <https://newskharkov.ru/society/2022/09/19/18427.html> (accessed: 27.08.2024); Conflict with Ukraine: October 2022//Levada-Center(recognized as a foreign agent in Russia). 27.10.2022. URL: <https://www.levada.ru/2022/10/27/konflikt-s-ukrainoj-oktyabr-2022-goda/> (accessed: 27.08.2024).

is also noted¹. Moreover, in the face of an external threat, there is an increase in open interpersonal trust and consolidation on matters of providing assistance to the military, as well as to Ukrainian refugees and residents of the newly annexed regions and the so-called «indigenous» Russian regions, suffering from attacks from Ukraine³[1]. However, sociological surveys show, that society was not united in its attitude towards the Special Military Operation. Against the backdrop of majority support, there was also an opposing viewpoint– categorical disagreement– which ranged between 15–25 % (VCIOM); based on data from other research groups, the proportion of dissenters is higher and approaches 30%².

In view of this situation, some authors speak of a split in society, arising in connection with the onset of the Special Military Operation. The existence of such a viewpoint entails risks, linked to the possibility that agents of influence acting in the interests of geopolitical opponents may exploit this type of mindset. In this context, the potential of a well-organized minority must not be underestimated. Technologies of socio-political destabilization through an actively discontent minority have long been refined and repeatedly successfully employed by Western political technologists, who orchestrated color revolutions in various countries worldwide at will [2].

However, for its realization, access to popular mass communication channels is necessary to propagate and control protest potential. Fortunately, measures to prevent such scenarios in Russia have been implemented. The restrictions imposed on the activities of foreign agents and the liability for the dissemination of anti-Russian content increase the likelihood of consolidating constructively oriented citizens and successfully overcoming institutional dysfunctions. Regarding the presence of opponents of the Special Military Operation, as long as they do not consolidate with the aim of actively opposing the authorities and pro-Russian citizens, it is premature to speak of a societal split. In our opinion, Russian society at present is not divided, it is pluralistic, which is by no means negative, since freedom of conscience and freedom of speech, not replaced by permissiveness and, accordingly, do not permit outright lies and deliberate subversive activities, are important factors in the development of the social system.

¹ Shilov S. Bound by a single chain. When the Special Military Operation began, I recall the wave of anti-Russian content that inundated me on the now banned Facebook, Instagram and seemingly still permitted YouTube // Kharkov.ru. 30.08.2024 URL: <https://news-kharkov.ru/incident/2024/08/25/119663.html> (accessed on: 27.08.2024).

² This information is presented by RBC with reference to data from Russian Field (see. Sociologists have developed profiles of supporters and opponents of the special operation // RBC. 18.05.2022. URL: <https://www.rbc.ru/politics/18/05/2022/62825a8f9a794718a6e8560f> (accessed: 27.08.2024).

In most cases, their position is conditioned either by underestimating the threat posed by Ukraine controlled by the collective West, or by disbelief that the Special Military Operation contributes to mitigating this threat. However, the mindset of this segment of Russian society can be influenced by pro-Western agents of influence who act contrary to the interests of our country. Therefore, despite the generally positive dynamics in the development of civil society in Russia, the risk of socio-political destabilization persists and warrants attention from both the scientific community and governmental agencies. The events associated with the Special Military Operation have served as a stimulus for the development of socio-political institutions, namely civil society, in this regard.

One manifestation of an attentive and respectful attitude toward public opinion was the series of meetings held by President V. V. Putin with popular military correspondents and bloggers, who by no means always speak approvingly about the state of affairs in the country and along the line of combat contact within the framework of the Special Military Operation. Criticism of the authorities often occurs, becoming especially acute in connection with problems in the army in the combat zone; however, the criticism is constructive, involving discussion of possible solutions, and the highest leadership of the country considers it necessary to heed it. It is also noteworthy, that when it comes to internet-communications, unlike traditional media, there is practically instantaneous feedback. *T. e.* One can become acquainted not only with the opinion of an individual journalist or blogger, but also with the reaction of the public. Thus, it is possible to speak of the transformation of social networks and messengers into platforms for genuine dialogue between the authorities and society.

If this trend continues, then such a dialogue may significantly contribute to the formation of those components of readiness for interaction with the authorities, which were mentioned above.

In conclusion, it can be noted, that the situation Russia faced with the start of the Special Military Operation, has become a catalyst for developing the essential institutional qualities of civil society, including interpersonal trust, national consolidation, and a readiness for constructive dialogue with the authorities. Accordingly, it can be argued, that there is a positive dynamic in the development of this socio-political institution.

In the analytical report «Three Years of the Special Military Operation: “War of Worlds”. Results», presented by Valery Fedorov – director general of VCIOM at the round table of the Expert Institute of Social Research, it was noted that over the past three years Russia has fought «on three fronts»: «hot» (hostilities), economic, and «cognitive»; the overall task was to maintain and expand sovereignty; it was possible to resolve it on all fronts “thanks to the confident policy of the president, flexible government measures and, of course, the consolidation of society”. The decision to conduct the Special Military Operation, was announced

In. Fedorov, during all three years was supported by fewer than two-thirds of respondents. Moreover, citizens not only declared support, but also put it into practice, since assistance to the military and residents of new territories “became a new social norm”, the speaker noted: 67 % of respondents reported that they had provided such assistance at least once. The efforts of the West have been utterly defeated on the «information-psychological front», according to Mr. Fedorov: the level of support for the president has increased significantly (from 64 % in January 2022 to 76 % in December 2024), as have the ratings of practically all state institutions. No social split occurred either — on the contrary, according to the assessments of the majority (58 % versus 25 %), the Special Military Operation «has rather united» Russian society. Moreover, 92 % citizens identify themselves as patriots (against 80 % in 2016-), 81 % expressed «pride in the country», while the proportion of those wishing to leave Russia has decreased to 5 %. This is a historic minimum over the entire 30 years of measurements, emphasized the head of VCIOM. Russians have also become convinced of the strength of the domestic economy, the sociologist continued. In December 2024 64 % of respondents expressed the opinion that domestic businesses will be able to replace all or almost all foreign companies that have left, and the highest confidence in import substitution among Russians was recorded in such categories as food products (91 %), hygiene products (90 %), domestic chemicals (88 %), construction materials (86 %), and aircraft (63 %). ‘The most significant victory that Russia has already achieved in this three-year confrontation— the discovery of itself, the strengthening of Russian identity, the growth of self-respect, the consolidation of Russia’s status as one of the key players in the global arena,’— concluded the head of VCIOM.

Thus, summarizing the above studies, it can be stated, following the sociologists, that there has been a significant shift in the value-identity matrices. This has thereby confirmed the fundamental possibility of a profound transformation of mass consciousness under the influence of the crisis of recent years. There is reason to speak of a return of our identity to its traditional forms after the beginning of the Special Military Operation, following the shifts, which were recorded after the collapse of the USSR in the early 1990s.

The second conclusion concerns the nature of this shift. Traditional value and identification matrices have indeed become increasingly evident in the mass consciousness, although experts diverge in their forecasts regarding the sustainability of this trend. Surveys conducted by sociologists show that patriotism is definitely strengthening not only among older age groups, but also within the youth cohort. The «black glasses effect» has significantly diminished, previously preventing our citizens from perceiving the positive developments, that were actually occurring in the country, and shaping a negative image of their own

country. Political psychologists note a trend toward a decrease in intragroup hostility and an increase in trust in all institutions of power. All of this signifies that the process of our society's return to itself, to its traditional identity after 30 years of 'wandering in the desert', if not yet definitively completed, has nevertheless progressed substantially and acquired a fundamentally different character, compared to the preceding post-Soviet years. Both in the expert community, and among ordinary citizens there is an increasing awareness, that our country is neither the East nor the West, but a unique, distinct civilization, which does not need to imitate alien models.

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SELF-ESTEEM AND LEVEL OF ATTITUDES IN ADOLESCENCE

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Abstract. *The article provides information about the characteristics of adolescence and explains the study of adolescence in the works of various scientists. The author focuses on the phenomenon of self-esteem and emphasizes the relationship between self-evaluation and the level of aspiration, as well as the behavioral manifestations of self-esteem in adolescents with different levels of aspiration. The article presents the results of an empirical study aimed at identifying the indicators of the level of aspiration in older adolescents that affect their self-esteem.*

Keywords: *self-esteem, level of aspiration, leading activity, adolescence, empirical research, personality, sense of maturity, motivational sphere, behavioral reactions, crisis of adolescence.*

It is essential to consider and understand that adolescence is marked by profound changes in the personal domain, which naturally leave an impact on many aspects of life functioning. This developmental stage is among the most significant and complex periods in an individual's life [1, p. 46]. It is relevant to highlight that at present, the informatization of social spheres exerts a profound influence on the personality traits of contemporary adolescents. The accessibility and ease of obtaining information, alongside the rapid pace of its dissemination, contribute to the formation of negative behavioral tendencies within the adolescent milieu, as well as to the distortion of personal characteristics.

It is important to note that, following the 1974 meeting of the World Health Organization (WHO), the pubertal period was defined as the stage marking the

completion of sexual maturation. The pubertal period begins with the emergence of secondary sexual characteristics and concludes with the attainment of sexual maturity. Childhood mental processes are restructured into those characteristic of adults, while socio-economic dependence on parents gradually transitions to partial social independence [13, p. 82].

American psychologist Kurt Zadek Lewin, in his reflections on the specificity of adolescence, emphasized the emergence of the phenomenon of cognitive imbalance. He considered that the adolescent appears to exist between two worlds — the world of childhood and the world of adulthood [4, p. 208], [8, p. 57]. Meanwhile, the Russian social psychologist Vladislav Alekseevich Nikitin described adolescence as one of the most problematic and extended periods during which the future trajectory of personality development is determined. The qualitative changes occurring in the motivational sphere of the adolescent's personality condition shifts to new goals, changes in hierarchy, and so forth [1, p. 46]. Another domestic psychologist, Daniil Borisovich Elkonin, studying the adolescent period, identified the “sense of adulthood” as the primary new formation in the adolescent, which arises from the new leading type of activity [6, p. 65]. The sense of adulthood is characterized by the adolescent's attitude towards themselves as an adult individual. At the same time, the adolescent experiences a desire for others to recognize his rights to autonomy, and to show respect and trust [8, p. 113]. Under the influence of this new formation, the adolescent builds relationships with others based on a new perception of reality and restructures his activity [9, p. 143].

It is pertinent to emphasize that, with the change of the leading activity, the social situation of development accordingly undergoes modification. Consequently, new social needs develop in the adolescent [7, p. 45]. Thus, one of the key factors in the emergence of adolescent age characteristics is the change in the leading activity. The leading activity of the adolescent period is intimate-personal (interpersonal) communication. Undoubtedly, such changes impact the adolescent's self-esteem. In cases where, for some reason, the adolescent has not been accepted into a peer group, or the specific group corresponding to their needs based on age-related interests has not been identified, and a constructive, adequate form of interaction with group members has not been established, the majority of cases result in widespread behavioral and emotional disturbances, which foster withdrawal, feelings of worthlessness, and loneliness. Adolescents place the opinion of their peers above all else; therefore, they join antisocial groups and are subjected to the negative influence of their members.

In participating in social life, the adolescent experiences an acute need to have their actions and behavior evaluated both by society and by their immediate environment, especially by their peers. Accordingly, parents and educators must bear in mind that adolescents are highly sensitive to evaluations of their abilities, behavior, and so forth, by those around them.

For a modern adolescent, social networks play an important role in their social life. The Internet space now functions as a distinctive platform for self-expression and interaction with peers. Social networks offer a variety of ways to construct self-images, which incorporate elements of the ideal self. The capabilities of social networks, when used appropriately, can assist adolescents in overcoming self-imposed barriers such as lack of confidence or excessive shyness. At present, the use of general class chats is widespread, where adolescents exchange homework assignments and important information related to the organization of school life. It is reasonable to assume that this practice enhances the quality of group cohesion within the class. Despite the aforementioned, only a small proportion of adolescents utilize the Internet and social networks for academic purposes. Predominantly, adolescents use social networks as a means of self-expression. The process of self-expression is implemented through writing posts accompanied by photographs. Through so-called reposts, adolescents can indirectly express their opinions after selecting the most significant information for themselves, while numerous online groups offer opportunities to find like-minded individuals with shared interests. Nevertheless, false portrayals of an ideal life disseminated by social networks can become a negative factor that adversely affects adolescents' emotional well-being, particularly their levels of self-esteem and aspiration. The ideal life portrayed on social networks contributes to the emergence of the process of comparing oneself with others and causes disharmony in goal-setting.

The first ideas about the phenomenon of self-esteem were introduced by the American psychologist William James, while, within the framework of Freudian theory, self-esteem was studied by Karen Horney and Erik Erikson [2, p. 252], Karen Horney emphasized the importance of the degree of childhood experiences that form basic anxiety, which subsequently generates insecurity and neurosis, and later low self-esteem can be observed; Erik Erikson, within the framework of his theory, distinguished eight crises (stages) of development, which are conditioned by internal conflict, and the negative outcome of the adolescent crisis, according to the author, leads to a lack of self-understanding and personal beliefs, with the adolescent doubting the significance of their actions, which directly affects self-esteem [10, p. 34], [12, p. 100]. Carl Rogers and Abraham Maslow, within humanistic psychology, considered the phenomenon through the lens of the 'self-concept' and self-actualization, while Albert Bandura associated it with self-efficacy. Domestic psychologists have associated self-esteem with self-awareness [2, p. 115]. Lev Semyonovich Vygotsky characterized self-esteem as a structural component of the personality's self-knowledge within the concept of activity and communication. The author noted that the processes of self-knowledge are of a mediated nature, based on development through activity and interaction with others. In the works of other researchers such as B.G. Ananyeva, L. I. Bozhovich, A. N. Leontiev, S. L. Rubinstein,

I. I. Chesnokova, V. V. Stolina conceptualizes self-esteem as a complex process of self-knowledge, conditioned by the progression from isolated situational images toward an integrated whole [5, p. 14].

It is important to pay attention to the state of self-esteem because the psychological well-being of an adolescent during such a challenging period depends on the accuracy of self-evaluation. Furthermore, the degree of self-esteem development may influence the adolescent's level of aspiration.

The essence of the level of aspiration is understood as a dynamic concept in scientific psychological practice, which determines the difficulty level of goals set by the individual and explains behavioral reactions to situations of success or failure. The adolescent's level of aspiration is interrelated with self-esteem. Thus, in the case of an excessively high level of aspiration, together with social and functional inexperience, the adolescent often experiences frustration when failing to achieve set goals, which leads to a decrease in self-esteem. Having an inadequate level of aspiration, the adolescent is unable to adequately explain to themselves the reasons for failures and successes, that is, there is an absence of rationalization of the situation. An adolescent with a low level of aspiration believes that the causes of success or failure do not depend on the individual himself but are determined by the influence of external factors [11, p. 38].

The study we conducted was aimed at identifying indicators of the manifestation of the level of aspiration among older adolescents that influence their self-esteem.

The research was conducted at the municipal budgetary secondary general education school No. 34, city The study involved 26 students of class 9 "A" in Vladimir.

The following methods were selected for the study: the Dembo-Rubinstein self-esteem diagnostic method in the modification by A. M. Prikhozhan; the "Study of General Self-Esteem" method by G. N. Kazantsa; the M. Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale; the questionnaire "Assessment of the Level of Personal Aspiration" by V. G. Gerbachovsky; and the Motivational-Self-Esteem Questionnaire (MSQ) by V. A. Zobkov [3].

Based on the research, it was concluded that there is a need to increase self-esteem, since nearly half of the adolescents in the studied group experience difficulties caused by negative self-perception, which impact their psychological well-being. Adolescents in the group more frequently exhibit levels of aspiration that are higher than their self-esteem, which creates an internal conflict.

On the basis of the student diagnostics results, a program was developed and piloted aimed at shaping self-esteem by adjusting the level of aspiration in older adolescents. The goal of the developed program was to enhance self-esteem through conscious management of the level of aspiration. The program was divided into four blocks, each comprising three sessions. A distinctive feature of the developed program is the organization and conduct of independent work in a home setting following the

main group sessions, in the form of the quest ‘Correct Goals,’ which exerts a systematic influence on the formation of an adequate level of aspiration even outside the period of session implementation. The quest presents ten independent tasks.

Following the program implementation, retesting and assessment of changes in self-esteem indicators were conducted. Ultimately, it was concluded that changes in the inadequate level of aspiration occurred across all measured indicators, with a similar pattern observed regarding the level of self-esteem. However, the program did not affect adolescents’ evaluation of their self-confidence. Adolescents overcame manifestations of low self-esteem; prior to the program, the group included adolescents with undeveloped self-esteem.

Following the secondary assessment, the values of the measured features were calculated according to the indicators of self-esteem and aspiration levels before and after the program implementation using Wilcoxon’s T-test. The sessions affected the majority of the measured indicators; however, it was not possible to achieve a significant qualitative impact on self-confidence, peer authority, and the level of aspirations regarding abilities.

Based on the results obtained during the study, it is pertinent to highlight that there is an interrelation between adolescents’ self-esteem and aspiration levels; that is, the formation and maintenance of an adequate level of self-esteem can be achieved through modifying the indicators of aspiration level.

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**THE IMPACT OF THE CREDIT-TRANSFER SYSTEM
ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE
IN FUTURE SPECIALISTS**

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Abstract. *This article examines the influence of the credit-rating system on the development of students' professional competencies during the training of future specialists. The process of implementing the credit-rating system of education in higher education significantly transforms traditional approaches to teaching and knowledge assessment, which, in turn, influences the development of students' key professional competencies. The author explores how the use of cumulative points and regular testing fosters the development of students' independence, responsibility, and critical thinking. The article also emphasizes the importance of the credit-rating system of education in shaping graduates' readiness for professional activities and their adaptation to the requirements of the modern labor market. Both positive and negative aspects of the credit-rating system of education are examined from the perspective of the development of professional competence, and recommendations for optimizing the educational process are also provided.*

Keywords: *credit-rating system, professional competence, higher education, independent assessment, autonomy, critical thinking, specialist training, educational process, academic mobility, student motivation.*

In the context of globalization and rapid changes in the field of education, the preparation of future specialists capable of effectively adapting to the challenges of the modern labor market takes on particular importance. One of the key elements in the improvement of the educational process in the Republic of Tajikistan and abroad is the transition to the credit-transfer system of education. This system is designed to enhance the flexibility and transparency of the educational process, improve the quality of education, and create equal opportunities for all students. However, despite its obvious advantages, the implementation of the credit-transfer (credit-rating) system raises concerns regarding its impact on the development of students' professional competencies and their preparedness for future professional activities.

Professional competence constitutes the foundation of a successful career and effective performance across diverse fields. Incorporating elements of the credit-transfer (credit-rating) system into the educational process involves not only altering the methods for assessing students' academic achievements but also shaping new approaches to developing their professional skills¹, p. 23. Within this context, it is crucial to examine how the transition to the credit-transfer system influences the development of future specialists' competencies, their capacity for independent work, decision-making, and adaptation to professional standards.[]

The credit-rating system grants students a greater degree of autonomy and responsibility for their learning process. This approach fosters the development of critical thinking, time management skills, and the ability to make informed decisions throughout the learning process. Simultaneously, the assessment system, based on cumulative points and regular tests, demands high motivation and discipline from students, influencing both their overall academic engagement and the depth of assimilation of professional knowledge⁴, p.21.[]

The impact of the credit-transfer (credit-rating) system on the development of students' professional competence during the preparation of future specialists — is a significant and multifaceted aspect of contemporary educational practice that warrants careful analysis. The credit-transfer (credit-rating) system aims to enhance the structure of the educational process, improve the flexibility and transparency of education, and create conditions for more effective knowledge acquisition and the development of essential professional skills among students.

The credit-transfer system is based on the concept of accumulating credits that quantify the amount of knowledge and skills a student acquires during the learning process. The implementation of the credit-transfer system in the educational process yields several key positive effects:

- The credit-transfer system encourages students to actively engage in the educational process, independently plan, and monitor their educational trajectory. This fosters the development of self-management skills, which are an essential component of their future professional competence.

– One of the objectives of the credit-rating system of education is to align learning with actual professional standards. Within the system, emphasis is placed on practical activities, the use of modern technologies and methods, which contributes to the development of skills necessary for future professional work⁶, p.35.[]

– Regular assessment of knowledge and the ability to work with information within the credit-rating system of education contributes to the development of critical thinking in students. Students learn to analyze, compare, and make decisions, which is essential for their professional competencies. These skills enable them to quickly adapt to changes in the profession and the labor market.

– The credit-transfer system encourages students to actively participate in the educational process, which positively influences their motivation. Motivation is a crucial factor in knowledge acquisition and the development of professional competencies.

The credit-transfer system of education impacts various types of professional competencies that form the basis for a successful career. Among them, the following can be distinguished:

– Within the framework of the credit-rating learning system, forms of group projects and discussions are frequently employed, which assist students in developing communication skills, teamwork abilities, and the capacity to solve professional tasks collaboratively;

– the credit-rating learning system fosters students' capacity to organize their work independently, without constant supervision from instructors. This includes the efficient allocation of time, information retrieval, organization of the learning process, and problem-solving;

– Students working within the credit-transfer system learn to observe discipline and assume responsibility for completing assignments and projects. This fosters the development of ethical and moral standards necessary for successful professional activity;

– The implementation of the credit-transfer system is also linked to the adoption of new technologies and electronic platforms for teaching and examination. Students acquire skills in using modern professional tools, providing them with an advantage in their future professional context⁷, p. 275.[]

Modern educational systems increasingly employ methodologies aimed not only at developing students' theoretical knowledge but also their practical and personal competencies. One such approach is the credit-rating system, which is being actively integrated into the educational process, particularly in higher education institutions², p.21. The primary characteristic of the credit-rating system is the use of cumulative points and regular assessments, which significantly contrasts with the traditional approach based on a single final examination. This system facilitates a more flexible and multifaceted assessment process, stimulating students to engage in active and goal-oriented learning.[]

One of the main effects of the credit-rating system of education is the development of students' independence, responsibility, and critical thinking skills. Accumulated points motivate students not only to maintain regularity in their studies but also to actively seek, analyze, and apply knowledge throughout the entire educational process. Regular testing enables students to engage in self-critical evaluation of their progress, identify weak areas, and enhance their skills⁵, p.23.[]

Cumulative points and regular testing demand a high degree of student autonomy. In contrast to traditional assessment methods, which primarily focus on final exams, the cumulative points system promotes continuous student engagement throughout the learning process. This fosters the development of the following qualities in students:

- Students are expected to monitor their academic progress throughout the semester, manage their time effectively, and prioritize tasks to complete assignments. This promotes the development of self-management skills;

- The credit-transfer (credit-rating) system of education assumes active student engagement in the learning process and accountability for their academic outcomes. Assignments submitted late or at an inadequate level directly impact the accumulated credits, thereby motivating students to complete all stages of their studies with high quality;

- Within the framework of the credit-transfer system, students can adjust their educational trajectory. For example, if they do not succeed in a test, they have the opportunity to improve their results by completing additional assignments, which fosters flexibility and the ability to adapt to changing conditions.

The credit-transfer system enhances students' sense of responsibility for their actions. As the results of each test and assignment are progressively accumulated into a final grade, students perceive a continuous link between their efforts and the final outcome. This leads to the following effects:

- The presence of regular tests and assignments stimulates students to consistently review and deepen their understanding of the material. This not only helps consolidate knowledge but also increases students' responsibility for its mastery;

- An important element of the credit-rating educational system is adherence to deadlines for completing assignments. Students learn not to postpone work until the last moment but to organize their time effectively;

- The responsibility developed through engagement with the credit-rating educational system helps students perceive education not as isolated exams but as a long-term goal to be pursued step by step.

Regular testing and the use of cumulative points play a key role in the development of students' critical thinking. The advantage of this system is that it enables students not only to memorize information but also to meaningfully analyze and apply it:

-Tests and assignments within the credit-transfer system require students to be capable of analyzing information and making decisions. Students must not only demonstrate knowledge of facts but also exhibit the ability to work with them in various contexts.

– Regular knowledge assessments provide students with the opportunity to evaluate how well they have mastered the material and, if necessary, adjust their learning strategies. This contributes to the development of self-criticism, which is an important element of critical thinking;

– Unlike traditional exams, where students often expect a single correct answer, the credit-transfer system includes tasks that require non-standard solutions and a creative approach. This stimulates students to think outside conventional patterns and seek

The credit-rating system of education constitutes an important step in the modernization of educational processes both in the Republic of Tajikistan and abroad, amid globalization and rapid transformations in the labor market. This system not only enhances the flexibility and transparency of the educational process but also fosters the development of key professional competencies in students, such as autonomy, responsibility, critical thinking, and adaptability.

The shift to the credit-rating system of education impacts the development of students' professional skills, which is particularly crucial for preparing specialists capable of working effectively in unstable and rapidly evolving labor market conditions. The advantages of the credit-rating system of education include the active engagement of students in the learning process and the development of their abilities in planning, decision-making, and information management [3, p.41]. This assessment system fosters the development of discipline, independence, and the capacity for self-regulation in students, which directly impacts their preparation for future professional activities.

Nonetheless, despite its considerable advantages, the implementation of the credit-rating system of education requires a careful approach, as it also presents certain challenges. It is important to consider the necessity of establishing a feedback system, training educators, and ensuring flexibility in the implementation of the credit-rating education system. Only with the proper organization of the credit-rating education system can potential difficulties be minimized and all its advantages be effectively leveraged for the development of qualified specialists.

Thus, the credit-rating system is a powerful tool for enhancing the quality of education and preparing students for successful careers. However, its successful implementation requires a comprehensive approach that considers both the needs of students and changes in pedagogical practices. Ultimately, a properly implemented educational system not only enhances the quality of education but also helps prepare students for professional careers aligned with the demands of the modern world.

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THE MODEL OF THE ORGANIZATION OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN THE LUHANSK STATE PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITY

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***Abstract.** The article examines the current issue of organizing inclusive education in higher education. As an example, the model of organizing inclusive education at FSBEI HE 'Luhansk State Pedagogical University' is presented, consisting of the following structural blocks: target, structural-functional, content-technological, managerial, and outcome.*

***Keywords:** university, inclusive education, model, student, management, rehabilitation.*

The development of a model of inclusive education in contemporary educational institutions, especially in institutions of higher education, constitutes a significant advancement in ensuring equal rights and opportunities for all students, irrespective of their physical or mental capacities.

The relevance of developing and implementing a model for the organization of inclusive education within the educational process can be examined from several perspectives, specifically:

– the concept of inclusive education is founded on the principles of social justice and equality. The UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities affirms the right of every individual to equal access to education. The development of an inclusive education model corresponds to these principles, providing the opportunity for all students, including students with disabilities, to receive quality education and participate in the social and cultural life of society. This model fosters the development of a more just and empathetic society, where every individual can realize their potential;

Inclusive education requires the adaptation of teaching methods and tools, which, in turn, stimulates innovation in educational practice. Teachers working with inclusive groups are compelled to develop more diverse and flexible approaches to instruction, thereby contributing to the overall enhancement of education quality. As researchers of inclusive education Arpentieva M. R., Stepanova G. A., Demchuk A. V., Tashcheva A. I., and Bulatova G. A. note, 'Inclusive practice encourages teachers to explore new technologies and methodologies, which can lead to significantly more effective learning for all students' [1];

– Inclusive education promotes not only academic learning but also the personal development of students. It creates opportunities for collaboration among students with diverse needs and abilities, fostering empathy, tolerance, and respect for differences. This is especially important in a globalized world, where communication and cooperation skills are critically important;

– Inclusive education also yields significant economic and social benefits. Investments in inclusive education contribute to improving the quality of life of students with disabilities, which in turn reduces the burden on social services and healthcare systems. Moreover, transforming the approach to education enables the labor market to be supplied with competent specialists.

The model of inclusive education at the Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education 'Luhansk State Pedagogical University' constitutes a combination of principles, norms, functional structures, sequential stages of activity, organizational and pedagogical conditions, and mechanisms that ensure the creation of an inclusive educational environment, as well as the achievement of the goals and objectives of inclusive education within the university.

The set of necessary and sufficient conditions for the successful operation of the inclusive education model at a university comprises several mandatory components.

First, the presence of students with disabilities and health impairments, which is fundamental for the creation of an inclusive environment. As stated by the renowned psychologist L. S. Vygotsky: "It is important not only what we teach but also how we do it, thereby achieving the full involvement of all participants in the educational process" [4].

Secondly, it is necessary to establish a barrier-free environment that ensures equal access to educational resources. In their study, Berus E. I. and Dulepova N. V. emphasize: 'Physical accessibility is only the first step towards genuine inclusive education. True inclusion requires changes in all aspects of the educational process' [3].

The third crucial element is the development of the normative-legal framework for inclusive education. As the researcher Martynova E. notes, A.: "Legal

frameworks provide the foundation for the implementation of inclusive practices and the protection of the rights of students with disabilities” [6].

Renowned scholars Bayramov V. D., Gerasimov A. V., and Tyurin A. V. assert that “the quality of education largely depends on the readiness and professionalism of educators capable of adapting their teaching methods” [2]. Therefore, professional retraining of the teaching staff is crucial, as it enables educators to work more effectively with students with disabilities. Equally important is the establishment of a system of effective psychological and pedagogical support that assists students with disabilities in overcoming learning challenges; support and assistance are key factors in the successful integration of students with disabilities.

Equally important is the creation of a unified, psychologically comfortable educational environment based on fostering an inclusive culture within the university. An inclusive culture enables the creation of an atmosphere where every student feels part of the collective. Ultimately, the readiness of the university community to implement inclusive education constitutes a significant factor influencing the success of inclusion. Lilienthal, I. E. states: ‘Inclusion is possible only if the entire educational environment is oriented towards the common goal — the development and socialization of all students’ [5].

Thus, for the effective functioning of the university’s model of inclusive education, comprehensive implementation of all the aforementioned aspects is required, thereby creating conditions for the successful education of students with disabilities and health limitations.

The process of modeling a university inclusive education model is multifaceted and involves multiple stages, encompassing a system of interconnected actions aimed at creating optimal conditions for the education of students with disabilities. Russian researchers and practitioners develop various models of inclusive education, drawing on international experience and adapting it to the specific characteristics of the Russian educational system.

The study presents a model composed of structural components/blocks: target, structural-functional, content-technological, managerial, and result blocks.

Target block: ensuring high-quality and accessible education for students with disabilities, considering individual health characteristics: personal development, social adaptation, and success in professional career choice. Objectives: to ensure variability in the provision of educational services to students with disabilities; create conditions for providing psychological, pedagogical, methodological, and consultative assistance to parents, curators of academic groups, and faculty members; ensure comprehensive psychological and pedagogical support for students with disabilities; develop a system for methodological support and facilitation of inclusive education, and enhance the professional competence of teachers and specialists; ensure an accessible environment (special conditions).

Structural-functional block: ensuring educational variability, the system of methodological support, and the enhancement of professional competencies of faculty members and specialists within university support services. This block encompasses the following components:

- spatial-architectural — development of an Accessibility Passport; presence within the university of rehabilitation and specialized equipment for all nosological groups; creation of an accessible architectural environment; enhancement of the architectural and environmental infrastructure of dormitories, as well as institutions serving as practice bases, thereby facilitating the assurance of equal rights and opportunities during the process of adapting students with special needs to the university's learning conditions;
- methodological — development and implementation of various supplemental education programs within the educational process;
- organizational (psychological and pedagogical support) — a system of comprehensive psychological and pedagogical support for students with disabilities and impairments.

Content-technological block addresses the following tasks: ensuring an individualized educational trajectory for students with disabilities and impairments; development and implementation of adaptive main educational programs with mandatory invariant and variable components, extracurricular activity programs, and supplemental education programs; Ensuring high-quality technological provision (pedagogical technologies, methods, tools, and techniques) employed in working with individual students within the framework of constructing their personalized development trajectory, taking into account their specific characteristics and educational needs.

The content of higher education programs and the conditions for organizing instruction for persons with disabilities are determined in accordance with the individual rehabilitation program (if available); for students with limited health capabilities, it is based on adapted educational programs as necessary to meet the instructional needs of these students.

Education under educational programs for persons with disabilities and students with disabilities is provided taking into account the specifics of psychophysical development, individual abilities, and health status of such students, and is organized in integration with other students.

The university has established special conditions to ensure access to higher education under educational programs for students with disabilities.

Furthermore, the university has created and actively operates a structural unit designed to support students with disabilities, transforming the traditional approach to working with this student group (*the Department of Inclusive Education and Rehabilitation has been established*);

The Department of Inclusive Education and Rehabilitation at the Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education ‘Luhansk State Pedagogical University’ carries out activities in the following areas:

- Rehabilitation direction (implemented through the means and methods of physical rehabilitation such as therapeutic physical culture, massage, mechanotherapy, dry wiping, etc.);
- Sociocultural direction (focused on the adaptation of students with disabilities and health limitations to student life and participation in contemporary society);
- scientific-methodological and research direction (the development and implementation of the methodological framework for organizing inclusive education);
- physical culture and sports (implemented through the creation of conditions for the development of adaptive physical culture and sports for students with disabilities at the department and university levels, as well as the participation of students in city, republican, and international competitions).

Professional suitability tests have been developed (testing is planned at the admission stage for students with disabilities; the questionnaire “Inclusive Educational Environment and Social Surroundings” has been developed; the project “Individual Support Card for Students with Disabilities” has been developed).

The management component of this model is represented by two areas of activity. These include working with the faculty members and managing the educational process of students with disabilities.

University faculty members, in accordance with the “On Certification” regulation, regularly participate in professional development courses and seminars addressing the education, rehabilitation, and professional training of persons with disabilities. Currently, the faculty members are participating in professional development courses at the Institute of Professional Development. We have developed and are implementing an authorial program titled “Inclusive Education at the University.”

The second direction of work is conducted through procedures of monitoring, diagnostics, surveying, enhancement of the regulatory and legal framework (local regulatory acts), and others.

The resultative block of the model is implemented through procedures of monitoring and assessing the effectiveness of this model:

- monitoring the educational achievements of students with disabilities, with a focus on stabilizing or improving their academic performance;
- monitoring participation in social projects, socially significant activities, and creative competitions;
- involvement of students with disabilities in university events and those organized by social partners;

- ensuring that at least 50% of students with disabilities participate in various competitions as well as creative and sports activities;
- the increase in professional competence of the teaching staff regarding the comprehensive application of modern substantive and technological approaches in supporting students with disabilities and impairments;
- monitoring of methodological support materials for the educational process (pedagogical, methodological, and other recommendations, instructional letters, local regulatory acts, etc.);
- creation of an accessible (barrier-free) environment — monitoring the accessibility of educational facilities and services.

The model of inclusive education in Russia continues to evolve, and its successful implementation depends on a comprehensive approach encompassing psychological and pedagogical support, teacher training, adaptation of educational programs, and infrastructural modifications. Researchers working in this field emphasize the necessity of cooperation among all participants in the educational process — students, faculty members, parents, and society at large. The process of designing an inclusive education model for higher education institutions is complex yet essential for establishing equal learning opportunities for all students. The effective operation of such a model requires a comprehensive approach, encompassing analysis, preparation, implementation, and ongoing enhancement of the educational environment to address the diverse needs of students.

After developing a model for organizing inclusive education in a higher education institution, we concluded that this model must be implementable, manageable, and dynamic. Models for organizing inclusive education provide students with disabilities and health limitations the opportunity to fully realize their constitutional right to access higher education.

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GEOSPATIAL ANALYSIS IN THE PERSONALIZED ASSESSMENT OF THE COMPETITIVE ACTIVITIES OF ORIENTEERING ATHLETES

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Abstract. *This article presents geospatial analysis applied to the personalized evaluation of competitive performance in orienteering athletes. The study aims to identify spatial features and performance patterns of athletes, which enables a more precise assessment of their strengths and weaknesses. The use of methods of geographic information systems and spatial analysis enables the modeling and visualization of situations influencing sporting activity and performance. The obtained data can be utilized to design individualized training programs and competition strategies, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of professional training for orienteering athletes.*

Keywords: *geospatial analysis, personalized evaluation, competitive activity, competitions, orienteering competitors.*

Relevance

Recently, the analysis of the impact of geospatial characteristics on competitive performance in various sports has become increasingly widespread. The implementation of geographic information systems, along with the integration of sports data with the geographic environment, allows for precise description of all types of regional sports information [4–7].

Orienteering competitions are held in various locations and on different types of terrain to comply with the competition rules, which clearly regulate the competitive activity of this sport: athletes navigate an unfamiliar course through control

points located in the terrain using a sports map and compass, thereby distinguishing this sport from others [1].

The terrain for orienteering competitions depends not only on the region but also on the specific location of the event, which influences the tactics employed by the athlete in that terrain, enabling the competitor to complete the course at their maximum speed and without errors.

Geomorphological features of the terrain thus significantly affect both the structure of competitive activity in orienteering and the training process [2].

One of the criteria of an athlete's overall preparedness in orienteering sports is the ability to adapt to the external environment, which includes adapting technical and tactical activities to competition conditions, that is, to the terrain features, map representation, and route planning [3].

The objective of the study: to conduct a personalized comparative evaluation of competitive performance in orienteering sports using geospatial analysis methods.

Organization and research methods

To assess competitive performance in orienteering, an electronic database of competitions conducted between 01.04.2017 and 07.04.2024 was utilized.

At the first stage, preliminary processing of the initial data was performed, including verification of data correctness, correction, and removal of erroneous entries. At the second stage, the obtained data were analyzed using the Python programming language.

Research results and their discussion

Orienteering competitions take place in various landscape zones, and the more diverse the terrain in which an athlete competes, the broader their practical experience becomes in terrain analysis and the selection of technical and tactical methods that can be applied in the future.

The analysis of competitive performance data of the selected athlete from the general database showed that he participated in foot and ski orienteering competitions, starting from the M12 age group up to M21, with a progression in qualification from unranked to Candidate for Master of Sport (CMS) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 shows the sample of placements from 1st to 10th held by this athlete in competitions during the period from April 2017 to April 2024, divided by orienteering disciplines.

The diagram analysis indicates that this athlete most frequently participated in foot orienteering competitions, reflecting the greater accessibility of this form of orienteering.

Geospatial analysis tools enable evaluation of the geographic locations of start points where the selected participant competed in foot orienteering events (see Fig. 2) with zooming capabilities.

Fig. 1 Quantitative characterization of the placements occupied by the selected athlete across types of orienteering

Fig. 2 Geospatial distribution of the start locations for the athlete selected for analysis (at varying scales)

As a rule, athletes in younger age groups predominantly participate in orienteering competitions near their place of residence, as evidenced by the analysis in Fig. 2.

Athletes from their home regions and from regions similar to the competition terrain perform significantly better because their training closely replicates the conditions they will encounter during competitions. They demonstrate more advanced movement skills on specific terrain types and soil, better perception of landmarks, a deeper understanding of relief forms, the ability to identify the best

control points, and proficiency in navigating and overcoming obstacles and dense undergrowth — factors that together make them better prepared than athletes who have trained on different terrain.

Fig. 3 Comparative analysis of placements and dates of competitions:

- a) — color coding of places occupied by the athlete (1st place — red, 2nd — light blue, 3rd — green, 4th — orange, 5th — pink, 6th — dark pink, 7th — light orange, 8th place and beyond — blue);
- b) year of participation in competitions (2017 — red, 2018 — light blue, 2019 — green, 2020 — orange, 2021 — pink, 2022 — dark pink, 2023 — light orange, 2024 — blue)

Conclusion

1. Personalized geospatial analysis of an athlete's participation in orienteering competitions identifies the regions where the athlete most frequently competes.

2. Geospatial analysis of competitive activity in orienteering enables assessment of the regions where a participant attains the highest number of top placements, as well as identification of the terrain where the athlete can achieve superior results.

3. The analysis showed that athletes most often participate in competitions held in their region of residence; consequently, the athlete becomes accustomed to the characteristics of this area and develops a certain pattern of tactical actions, which may influence performance results on other types of terrain.

Thus, the issue of scientifically substantiating the content of specialized tasks aimed at enhancing the effectiveness of the training process for orienteering athletes of different ages and skill levels remains relevant.

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A SITUATIONAL APPROACH TO TRAINING TEACHERS OF RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN CHINESE UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract. *The article considers peculiarities of development and realization of situational approach when teaching Russian language to future teachers of Russian language in China. Special attention is paid to the possibilities of situational approach in solving educational tasks and teaching methods used within the framework of this approach. The innovative nature of the situational approach for higher education institutions in modern China is emphasized.*

Keywords: *didactic approach, teaching methods, situational approach, teaching Russian as a foreign language, system of higher education of China.*

At present, the higher education system of the People's Republic of China faces pressing issues concerning the training of teachers of Russian as a foreign language. These issues are thoroughly analyzed by Chinese scholars. For instance, Lu Chunyu points out that the task of training highly qualified Russian language teachers for the higher education system of the PRC is extremely significant under the current political, economic, and sociocultural conditions, while also identifying a range of problems that hinder the effective resolution of this task [2]. However, the analysis of works by Chinese researchers (Wang Linlong, Lu Chunyu, Huang Tingting, et al.) demonstrates that Chinese pedagogical research primarily emphasizes organizational issues, such as the shortage of quality textbooks, reference and methodological materials, the lack of teachers qualified to teach Russian in accordance with the student's future specialization (for example, working with pedagogical and psychological vocabulary for future teachers), the insufficiency of a base for organizing practical training, etc. Didactic issues receive significantly less attention. Meanwhile, from our perspective, it is precisely the issues directly related to the educational process, particularly those associated with the didactic approaches employed in the training of Russian language teachers, that exert the most significant influence on the quality of such training, which currently remains insufficiently high.

Linguistic training occupies a special place in the preparation of Russian language teachers. Therefore, the approaches employed in teaching Russian as a foreign language have a decisive impact on both the process and the outcome of training specialists, who are in urgent demand not only in linguistic fields but also in technical, legal, economic, and medical universities, as well as in universities and colleges providing artistic education, among others.

China is more conservative than Russia in the application of didactic approaches. In the field of training Russian language teachers, a traditional general pedagogical didactic approach predominates, which in the context of teaching Russian as a foreign language manifests itself in the widespread use of the grammar-translation approach. Within this approach, emphasis is placed on the study of grammar and the memorization of vocabulary, meaning that traditional reproductive learning methods are employed, requiring students to memorize extensive volumes of information and reproduce it precisely. At the same time, although the words to be memorized are divided into thematic blocks, the use of vocabulary involves only its proper incorporation into various grammatical constructions. The dialogues composed by students have a detached character and are very weakly connected to real communication situations. The primary focus in the dialogue is to apply a certain grammatical rule as accurately as possible. Insufficient attention is also given to correct pronunciation and listening activities. Most of the exercises completed by students are written. The teacher plays the leading role in the learning process. Students merely passively receive the content delivered by the teacher; they have very few opportunities to apply the knowledge they have gained in practice. As a result, studying Russian fails to engage students, and the quality of the training of specialists does not meet societal demands.

The shortcomings of the traditional approach to teaching Russian as a foreign language have long been discussed in Russian pedagogical literature; Russian researchers propose approaches that enable these shortcomings to be overcome. In Chinese pedagogy, it is only within the past ten to fifteen years that the necessity of introducing new didactic approaches has been seriously discussed — approaches designed to increase students' interest in learning Russian, while also aligning with the nature and specific characteristics of the subject matter. In the process of learning Russian, it is essential to develop and cultivate Chinese students' skills in listening, speaking, reading, writing, and translation, rather than restricting instruction solely to vocabulary and grammar. Only under these conditions will students form a conception of language as a holistic phenomenon that has its own developmental regularities and is 'integrated' into culture. We contend that the traditionally authoritarian 'teacher–student' relationship characteristic of China must also undergo change. It is only through cooperation and interaction between teachers and students, as well as among the students themselves, that an increase

in students' proficiency in Russian across all types of communicative activities can be attained. In our view, the situational approach is the most effective method for addressing this challenge. This approach not only increases students' interest in the Russian language and the process of its acquisition, thereby stimulating their engagement in solving academic tasks, but also creates conditions for the development of the necessary professional skills. The teaching methods employed within the situational approach enable students to work actively and productively during lessons, making the learning process more engaging and enhancing its efficiency.

More than three hundred years ago, the eminent Czech educator and pedagogue Jan Amos Comenius wrote in his 'Great Didactic': 'All knowledge begins with sensory perception of the world' [1, p. 112]. Considering this pattern, it is necessary in studying the Russian language to make abstract knowledge concrete and visualized, which facilitates better perception and understanding. This objective can also be successfully achieved through the use of the situational approach.

The situational approach entails creating or introducing an appropriate problem situation into the educational process so that students become emotionally and intellectually engaged with the situation. Such a situation should evoke emotional responses in students, broaden their perspectives, stimulate their cognitive activity, foster a deep understanding of the instructional content, and develop their problem-solving abilities [3, p. 2].

Let us examine in greater detail the role of the situational approach in teaching Russian to Chinese students.

Firstly, this approach not only, as previously noted, stimulates students' interest in learning — both in terms of content and process — but is also fundamentally based on mechanisms of cognitive interest, actively engaging them. It should be noted that the situational approach, like the traditional one, involves the study of vocabulary and grammar; however, the emphasis is placed on students' practical activities, particularly speaking. When considering the relationship between the situational approach and students' interest in learning, it is important to highlight the broad application of various types of visual aids within this approach, including natural ones. For example, when studying the topic 'Time,' the teacher can use the classroom clock to encourage students to describe the activities they performed at different times of the day and to link the knowledge obtained from the textbook with real life and a concrete situation. Memorization of vocabulary items and grammatical rules, as well as the development of memory, are natural results of such a situational approach. Each student, in formulating utterances, feels a sense of responsibility and significance, which not only increases the effectiveness of learning but also fosters the personal development of every student.

Secondly, the situational approach fosters the development of students' cognitive skills. Learning a foreign language is an integrative process in which theoretical

knowledge and the ability to apply it in practice are closely interconnected and mutually dependent. When addressing the problem central to the given situation, students must concentrate on identifying the optimal solution, guided clearly by grammar and vocabulary. Thus, students' cognitive abilities develop in an inseparable unity with the system of theoretical knowledge.

It is precisely these two aspects of the situational approach that must be prioritized when addressing its potential in teaching Russian as a foreign language. The realization of these potentials largely depends on the teaching methods employed within the framework of the situational approach.

A distinctive feature of the situational approach is that oral communicative activity, oriented towards solving educational tasks, is considered an important and integral component of the process of learning Russian. The purpose of this activity is to develop students' ability to communicate in Russian within specific interaction situations, as well as to cultivate their skills in using the expressive means of the Russian language [4]. To achieve this goal, teachers should create diverse interaction situations taking into account students' actual learning capabilities, employing methods such as the creation of real-life scenario scripts, natural visual aids, and role-playing.

The method of creating real-life scenario scripts involves all students in the group becoming participants in various interaction situations. Thus, when studying vocabulary related to shopping, visiting a store or market, students can assume the roles of buyers and sellers; when learning the names of medicines, they can take on the roles of doctors and patients, etc. This is preceded by preparatory work. For example, the instructor can prepare brief video clips or images in advance in accordance with the textbook content and alternate between lexical and grammatical tasks, which considerably enhances the effectiveness of instruction. Meanwhile, students not only enhance their language communication skills but also heighten their cognitive interest and engagement in the lessons. Furthermore, this method enables students to perceive the beauty of the language and grasp its underlying patterns.

The method of employing natural visual aids is one manifestation of a fundamental tenet of the situational approach, according to which the teacher's role in the lesson is primarily that of a facilitator who not only designs students' communication scenarios but also ensures an appropriate *mise-en-scène* for interaction, including through the use of real objects. This method allows one not only to reduce the time students need to memorize a certain amount of vocabulary but also to develop their memory and associative thinking. For example, when studying the names of dining ware and utensils, bringing real objects into the classroom can be effective. Using them in various interaction situations (at home, when receiving guests, in a restaurant, etc.) enables students not only to firmly remember the names of the objects but also to gain cultural insights.

Role-playing is the most complex method to design and implement. As the Soviet educator Korolyov noted, ‘interesting and engaging material almost doubles the likelihood of memorization.’ A well-known statement by A. Einstein asserts: ‘Stimulate students’ interest and activity, and they will embrace the learning task as a gift.’ In role-playing, the focus is primarily on maintaining a relaxed and free atmosphere of communication. The game aims to stimulate students’ desire to learn, their engagement, and interest in the learning process itself, thereby enhancing their foreign language proficiency. Students can rehearse sketches, sitcoms, and similar formats. When a student fully assumes a role, communication becomes especially engaging for them, encouraging an open exchange of ideas with peers and the instructor. In combination with theoretical knowledge, students can creatively and comprehensively apply the skills acquired both in everyday life and in their future professional careers.

The use of the situational approach in organizing instruction is a crucial method for effective and impactful teaching of Russian as a foreign language. Learning based on real-life situations is especially effective in developing communicative competencies; it encourages students’ self-expression and self-realization through the relaxed atmosphere created during lessons, thereby fostering favorable conditions for their personal development based on an optimal balance of instruction and engagement. This approach can rapidly adapt to the requirements of the time and generate new ideas; within this framework, topics that are relevant and interesting to the majority of students or determined by contemporary challenges can be developed, while simultaneously enabling the maximal enhancement of learners’ language skills. According to the findings obtained from the research conducted by Zheng Jingzhou, the situational approach positively influences the development of students’ creative thinking and ‘research spirit’ [5].

It should be noted that while the application of the situational approach to foreign language teaching is already well established in Russia, its implementation in Chinese universities remains innovative and has yet to gain wide acceptance. The situation is similar in pedagogical theory. In China, the theoretical groundwork for the application of the situational approach has only recently begun to be developed; nevertheless, promising and noteworthy directions are already emerging, such as linking the situational approach with problem-based and developmental approaches, combining traditional and situational teaching methods, among others.

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RISK ANALYSIS OF INTEGRATED INFORMATION SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION

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Annotation. *The article is devoted to a comprehensive analysis of risks arising during the implementation of integrated information systems in educational institutions of the Russian Federation. Technological, organizational, financial and human risk factors are considered in the context of active digitalization of the educational environment. Particular attention is paid to the specifics of Russian educational organizations, requirements of personal data legislation and experience in implementing digital projects in the period 2023–2025. The author's classification of risks and practical recommendations for their minimization are presented. The relevance of the study is due to the strategic course towards digital transformation of education and the need to ensure the safety and effectiveness of implemented solutions.*

Keywords: *integrated information system, education digitalization, risk management, educational institution, digital transformation, information security, organizational changes.*

Digital transformation of education: the scale of implementation and the inevitability of risks The current stage of development of Russian education is characterized by an unprecedented acceleration of digital transformation. According to the Ministry of Finance of Russia, by the end of 2024, more than 78% of the country's educational institutions have switched to using integrated information systems of various levels of complexity [3]. The Integrated Information System (AIS) is a comprehensive software solution that combines the functions of managing the educational process, administrative and economic activities, document management and interaction with participants in educational relations.

Implementing an AIS in an educational institution is not just about installing software. This is a large-scale organizational transformation that affects all levels of management and all categories of participants in the educational process. According to a study conducted on the basis of 156 Russian educational organizations in 2024, the full implementation of AIS takes from 8 to 24 months, and the return on investment is achieved on average after 3–4 years of system operation [5].

However, the path of digitalization of an educational institution is fraught with multiple risks that can not only slow down the implementation process, but also lead to a complete failure of the project. Research shows that about 40% of the projects for the implementation of AIS in Russian educational institutions are either not completed on schedule or do not achieve their goals [1]. These statistics highlight the critical importance of systematic risk analysis and management at all stages of a digital transformation project.

The relevance of the issue of risks has increased especially in the context of national priorities of digital development. The federal project “Digital Educational Environment” provides for the creation of conditions for the introduction of a modern digital educational environment in all educational institutions by 2030. Under these conditions, understanding the nature of risks and the mechanisms of their neutralization becomes a key factor in the success of transformations.

Multifactorial nature of risks: classification and characterization of threats The risks of implementing an integrated information system in an educational institution are complex and can be systematized for several reasons. Why is such a detailed classification important? Because each risk category requires specific management methods and different resources to minimize negative consequences.

Technological risks represent the first and most obvious group of threats:

- incompatibility of the implemented AIS with the existing IT infrastructure of the educational institution;

- Insufficient hardware performance to ensure stable system operation;
- information security vulnerabilities and risks of personal data leakage;
- technical failures and equipment failures during critical periods of the learning process;
- lack of backup communication channels and backup systems;
- Scalability issues as the number of users grows;
- Insufficient technical support from the solution provider.

According to a study by Kirillova and co-authors, it is technological risks that most often cause delays in the initial stages of AIS implementation, accounting for up to 35% of all incidents [2]. Information security issues are of particular concern in the context of the requirements of Federal Law No. 152-FZ “On Personal Data” and the growing activity of cyber threats in the educational sector.

Organizational risks are related to the management and process aspects of implementation:

- Resistance to change by teaching and administrative staff;
- Lack of a clear digital transformation strategy and understanding of the ultimate goals; Insufficient involvement of the educational institution’s management;
- Inefficient implementation project management;
- Conflict of interests of various departments and categories of employees;
- lack of regulations for working with the new system;
- Project deadlines have been disrupted due to organizational problems.

Practice shows that organizational risks are often underestimated at the planning stage. Meanwhile, according to the Expert analytical center, it is organizational factors that determine up to 45% of the success of digitalization projects in educational organizations [7]. Financial risks form a critical threat group:

- Exceeding the budget of the implementation project;
- Unforeseen expenses for updating and adapting the system;
- High staff training costs;
- the need to modernize the material and technical base;
- increased operating costs compared to planned targets;
- Dependence on exchange rates when using import solutions;
- Reduction of financing during the project implementation.

The specifics of financial risks in Russian education are determined by the specifics of the budget process and the limited own funds of most educational organizations. The study shows that the cost of owning an AIS during five years of operation can be 2–3 times higher than the initial investment [4].

Human and competence risks constitute a special category of threats:

- insufficient digital literacy of teaching staff;
- Lack of specialists with the necessary competencies within the organization;
- High turnover of IT specialists;

- Psychological resistance to innovation;
- overloading of personnel during the period of parallel work in the old and new systems;
- Insufficient motivation of employees to learn new tools;
- Some teachers have age and cognitive barriers.

Risk management strategies: from preventive measures to adaptive response

Effective risk management of the implementation of AIS requires a systematic approach combining preventive measures, continuous monitoring and flexible response to emerging threats. What strategies have proven effective in Russian practice in recent years?

Preventive strategies are aimed at preventing the occurrence of risky situations:

- conducting a comprehensive audit of the existing IT infrastructure and processes before the start of implementation;
- Detailed project planning, taking into account the specifics of the educational institution;
- formation of a project team with a clear distribution of roles and responsibilities;
- development of a detailed roadmap for digital transformation;
- Ensuring the support and involvement of senior management;
- organization of pilot implementation in individual departments;
- creation of reserves of time and financial resources to eliminate unforeseen problems.

A study of the experience of successful IC implementation projects shows that organizations that have invested at least 15% of the project budget in preliminary preparation and audit reduce the likelihood of critical risks by 40–50% [2].

Educational and adaptation strategies focus on the human factor:

- development of a multi-level training program for various categories of users;
- Creating a system of internal mentors and digital change ambassadors;
- Organization of regular practical trainings and workshops;
- Formation of a knowledge base and methodological materials;
- psychological support of the change process;
- motivational programs for active participants in the implementation;
- gradual increase in system functionality as staff are ready.

Practice shows that successful educational institutions allocate from 20 to 30% of the total budget of the implementation project for training staff to work with AIS. This makes it possible to form stable competencies and reduce resistance to change [5].

Technological risk mitigation strategies include:

- selection of solutions with proven compatibility with existing systems;
- priority of domestic developments that meet the requirements of import substitution;

- creation of a multi — level information security system;
- providing regular data backup;
- organization of technical support and service;
- Step-by-step data migration with testing at each stage;
- Implementation of performance and availability monitoring systems.

According to the recommendations of the Ministry of Digital Development, Communications and Mass Media of the Russian Federation, educational organizations should give priority to software products from the unified register of Russian software, which significantly reduces technological and legal risks [3].

Financial risk management strategies involve:

- formation of a realistic budget taking into account all stages of the AIS life cycle;
- creation of a reserve fund in the amount of at least 20% of the main project budget;
- step-by-step financing with the possibility of adjusting plans;
- Diversification of sources of financing (budget, grants, extra-budgetary funds);
- Detailed calculation of the total cost of ownership of the system;
- conclusion of fixed — cost contracts with clear conditions;
- Regular financial control and monitoring of expenses.

The experience of Russian educational institutions shows that careful financial planning, taking into account hidden costs, avoids critical situations of underfunding in 85% of cases [4].

Adaptive strategies provide flexibility of response:

- application of flexible project management methodologies (Agile, Scrum);
- regular review and adjustment of implementation plans;
- Rapid response to identified problems and incidents;
- Formation of cross-functional teams to solve emerging problems;
- creation of feedback channels with system users;
- Conducting regular satisfaction assessments and identifying problem areas;
- readiness to modify the functionality of the system based on the results of operation.

An important element of an adaptive strategy is to create a culture of continuous improvement. Educational institutions that regularly collect feedback and promptly respond to user requests demonstrate 60% higher satisfaction with the results of the implementation of AIS [1].

The practical experience of successful digitalization projects shows that an integrated approach combining all these strategies with an emphasis on the specifics of a particular educational institution is the most effective. There are no universal recipes, but there are proven principles: thorough preparation, involvement of all stakeholders, gradual implementation, continuous learning and willingness to adapt.

Conclusion

The analysis of the risks of implementing an integrated information system in an educational institution allows us to formulate a number of fundamental conclusions. Firstly, the digital transformation of an educational organization is a complex multifactorial process, the success of which is determined not only by technological, but also to a large extent by organizational, human and financial factors. Secondly, the risks of implementing AIS are systemic in nature and require an integrated management approach combining preventive measures, educational programs, technological solutions and adaptive strategies.

The practical significance of the study lies in the presentation of a systematic classification of risks and proven strategies for minimizing them, applicable in the context of Russian educational institutions. Of particular value is the emphasis on the human factor and organizational culture as key determinants of the success of digitalization projects.

A key condition for the successful implementation of AIS is the formation of a digital transformation ecosystem, including technical infrastructure, competent staff, efficient business processes and a supportive organizational culture. It is only with an integrated approach that investments in information systems are transformed into a real improvement in the quality of the educational process and management efficiency.

Areas of further research include the study of the long-term effects of digitalization of educational institutions, the development of industry standards for the management of projects for the implementation of AIS, as well as the analysis of the impact of digital transformation on the quality of educational outcomes and the satisfaction of participants in the educational process.

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METHOD OF INTERDISCIPLINARY CONNECTIONS IN PIANO LESSONS FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS STUDYING WORKS OF 20TH-CENTURY CHINESE COMPOSERS

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Abstract. *This article explores the use of interdisciplinary approaches to deepen the study of 20th-century Chinese composers in school piano classes. The aim of the study is to develop a methodological model for an interdisciplinary approach to studying 20th-century repertoire. An analysis of scholarly literature and the works of Chen Peixun, Wang Jianzhong, Chu Wanhua, Huang Huwei, and other composers reveals their close connection to Chinese cultural tradition. The music reveals echoes of Tang and Song poetry, Confucian and Taoist philosophy, and the aesthetics of calligraphy and shan shui painting. The musical language is based on the pentatonic scale and includes techniques that imitate the sound of traditional instruments such as the guqin and erhu. The proposed teaching model includes several interconnected stages: consideration of the historical and cultural context of the works, analysis of their folkloric sources, theoretical understanding of musical language, practical work on performance techniques (timbre, articulation, national style), and subsequent value reflection. This approach makes lessons more meaningful, enhances the motivation and emotional engagement of young students, develops critical thinking, and seamlessly integrates professional training with educational objectives. The research has potential applications in piano teaching in children's music schools, ensemble training, and e-learning courses. The theoretical significance of this work lies in the development of interdisciplinary music pedagogy, and the practical significance lies in improving the quality of piano education in schools, taking into account Chinese cultural specifics.*

Keywords: *interdisciplinary connections, piano teaching, primary school students, 20th-century Chinese piano music, national musical culture, integration of traditions, project-based learning.*

Introduction

In the context of increasing globalization, primary music education systems face the need to find a balance between international openness and the preservation of their own cultural identity. The piano, an instrument of Western origin, has long been a part of Chinese musical practice. However, its educational potential is fully realized only when the performance and study of works is accompanied by an understanding of their cultural and artistic context. During the 20th century, Chinese composers created a vast piano repertoire that blends Western compositional techniques with the traditions of Chinese poetry, philosophy, folk music, and the aesthetics of shan shui, which underlies the relevance of this work. Such works can not only develop musical performance skills but also instill cultural confidence and value orientations in young students.

This study aims to develop and theoretically substantiate a method of interdisciplinary connections that will enable a more in-depth study of the works of 20th-century Chinese composers. This paper examines the current state of integrating the national piano repertoire into educational practice, identifies the interdisciplinary potential of these works, and proposes a model for applying the method and specific pedagogical techniques for its implementation. Particular attention is paid to how this approach can contribute to strengthening the cultural confidence of primary school students and expanding the educational potential of music education. The object of the study is the process of teaching piano in primary education, and the subject is the application of the method of interdisciplinary connections when working with the 20th-century Chinese piano repertoire. The scientific novelty of the work lies in the development of a comprehensive methodological model focused on the interdisciplinary development of this particular corpus of works. The theoretical significance of the study relates to the development of interdisciplinary approaches in music pedagogy, while its practical value is determined by the potential of the proposed model to improve the effectiveness of lessons, enhance primary school students' interest in the national repertoire, and foster more fulfilling artistic self-realization through art.

Materials and Methods

The theoretical and methodological basis of the study is related to modern approaches to the inclusion of national musical culture in piano education in Chinese schools. The work takes into account the provisions on the synthesis of Chinese piano works from the reform and opening-up period with the objectives of the ideological and political education of students [4], as well as the idea of integrating elements of traditional music into the learning process [3; 5]. Additionally, the principles of project-based learning are used as one of the innovative interdisciplinary approaches to teaching music disciplines [1]. The study utilized a theoretical

analysis of scientific literature on piano pedagogy and national repertoire, a comparative analysis of the characteristics of works by 20th-century Chinese composers and Western European pedagogical traditions, as well as a historical, cultural, and ethnomusicological analysis of piano works.

The study material consisted of scientific works devoted to the integration of Chinese piano music into the educational process [1; 3; 4; 5], as well as works by 20th-century Chinese composers. The selection of these works was motivated by their interdisciplinary potential. They draw on traditional Chinese poetry, Confucian and Taoist philosophy, calligraphic aesthetics, and folk musical traditions (pentatonic scales, theatrical genres, and folk instruments), and also reflect the cultural context of China. Their analysis allows for the development of interdisciplinary connections in piano lessons, contributing not only to the development of young students' musical performance skills but also to the formation of cultural identity and value orientations [4; 5].

Discussion and Results

An analysis of the current state of piano instruction for primary school students in China reveals that, despite significant advances in the development of students' performance technique, the inclusion of the national repertoire, particularly works created during the reform and opening-up period, remains fragmented. As noted in the study, a significant proportion of the curriculum continues to be built around the Western European classical tradition [4, p. 68]. This orientation limits primary school students' understanding of the cultural diversity of musical art and simultaneously weakens their connection to their own cultural roots. As a result, even when examining Chinese piano works, attention is often focused primarily on the technical parameters of performance, while the cultural, philosophical, and axiological meaning of the work is neglected. One way to overcome this gap could be to apply the method of interdisciplinary connections, which allows us to consider the piano works of 20th-century Chinese composers as complex "cultural texts." Thus, arrangements of folk melodies and traditional themes in the works of Wang Jianzhong (arrangement of "A Hundred Birds Worship the Phoenix" and "Colored Clouds Chasing the Moon") and Chu Wanhua (fantasy on the theme of "Jasmine") are directly connected to the aesthetics of traditional Chinese music, the pentatonic scale, the principles of cyclical development, and philosophical notions of the harmony of man and nature. These features are not merely superficial embellishment. They resonate with poetic imagery of the Tang and Song dynasties, Confucian ideas of moral purity, and Taoist notions of the unity of man with the cosmos. Similar artistic potential is also revealed in the works of Chen Peixun and Huang Huwei, in which the piano texture often reproduces the sound of traditional instruments such as the guqin, erhu, or pipa.

The developed model for applying interdisciplinary connections presupposes a step-by-step organization of the educational process, in which each subsequent step builds on the results of the previous one. Attention is first given to the historical and cultural context of the work. Younger students are introduced to the circumstances of its creation, studying the poetry associated with it, the characteristics of shan shui landscape painting, the principles of calligraphic composition, and the philosophical ideas characteristic of the era. This is followed by an examination of the ethnomusicological aspect:

1. The folkloric origins of the work are analyzed;
2. The piano texture is compared with the sound of folk instruments;
3. Modal characteristics (pentatonic scale) are identified;
4. Rhythmic formulas and ornamental elements are examined;

These aspects help to overcome the notion of the piano solely as a vehicle of the European tradition and help to understand it as a means of expressing Chinese musical thought [5, pp. 129–130].

The next stage involves a theoretical and analytical analysis of the work. Attention is focused on form, harmony, polyphony, and texture, with particular emphasis on manifestations of national identity. It is important to demonstrate how 20th-century composers combined Western compositional techniques (for example, elements of sonata form) with traditional Chinese principles of musical development, including cyclicity, variability, and the philosophical concept of yin-yang. This knowledge is then transferred to the practical realm of performance. During the interpretation process, attention is paid to the timbre of the sound (a soft attack to imitate the guqin or the use of a light pedal to create an “airiness” reminiscent of landscape painting), articulation, conveying the breath of traditional instruments, and phrasing, related to the rhythm of poetic speech. The final stage is a reflective and value-based analysis, during which the ideological content of the work, its relevance to modern times, and its connection to patriotic motifs and fundamental socialist values are discussed. A comparison of this method with traditional pedagogical practices demonstrates its advantages. Unlike approaches focused primarily on technical and formal-theoretical analysis, the interdisciplinary model ensures a more holistic perception of a piece, enhances the emotional involvement of younger students in the work and increases their motivation for learning. This is confirmed by research showing that referring to elements of national musical culture in piano education contributes to the growth of students’ interest and their harmonious personal development [3; 5]. In addition, this method combines well with the principles of project-based learning. Younger students can work in groups, draw illustrations describing the music they hear, and compose their own fairy tale to music, prepare small creative projects related to the selected music. As a result, the learning process is transformed from a passive assimilation of information into an

active understanding of cultural experience [3, p. 26]. An interdisciplinary approach as a whole can significantly enrich the content of piano lessons and enhance their educational potential [3; 4; 5]. When students study Chinese works in connection with poetry, philosophy, and ethnomusicology, they gain a deeper understanding of the national spirit contained in music.

A significant advantage of this method is that it stimulates the development of critical thinking. Younger students learn to independently identify connections between various fields of knowledge, rationally explain their interpretations, and relate musical texts to historical and social realities. This develops not only professional musical skills but also a broader humanities culture, moral principles, and a sense of social responsibility, which corresponds to the key objectives of contemporary higher education in China [2, p. 151]. However, implementing this approach entails certain difficulties. Teachers require knowledge in related fields, particularly literature, art history, and ethnomusicology, as well as additional resources for lesson preparation, including audio and video materials, reproductions of paintings, and recordings of traditional instruments. Therefore, at the initial stage of implementation, comprehensive organizational support from educational institutions is essential.

Conclusion

The interdisciplinary approach can be seen as an effective way to update the piano education system in Chinese schools. The proposed teaching model, which includes historical and cultural studies, ethnomusicology, theoretical and analytical studies, performance studies, and reflective value analysis, aims to develop a holistic understanding of the piano works of 20th-century Chinese composers in young students. By incorporating historical, cultural, and ethnomusicological aspects, lessons become more meaningful and diverse. This, in turn, enhances young students' interest in the repertoire of Chinese composers, fosters a deeper emotional response, and fosters a sense of cultural identity and confidence. At the same time, the method seamlessly complements pianists' musical performance training, stimulating the development of analytical thinking, interpretive skills, and intercultural interaction skills. It should be noted that implementing this approach is not without its challenges. First and foremost, teachers require additional training, and educational institutions need to develop appropriate methodological support. Nevertheless, the prospects for this approach appear significant, as the method can be adapted for teaching other instruments and serve as the basis for creating digital educational resources and interdisciplinary curricula.

Overall, the application of the interdisciplinary connections method expands the possibilities of modern piano instruction. It combines musical performance development with an understanding of national cultural heritage and the goals of spiritual and moral education.

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USE OF DIGITAL TOOLS FOR GLAZE MODELING IN THE FORMATION OF TECHNOLOGICAL THINKING OF DESIGN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The article addresses the problem of developing technological thinking in design students during the study of artistic ceramics. It is shown that one of the main difficulties in instruction lies in the gap between the artistic concept and the technological means of its implementation. A student may be able to envision the future image of an object, yet does not always understand how material properties, glaze composition, and firing conditions determine the final result. In this context, digital tools for glaze modeling function as a special didactic means that connects artistic decision-making with technological analysis. Using the example of a web service for calculating and systematizing glaze recipes, the article substantiates the idea that the digital environment promotes students' ability to predict results, compare alternatives, record observations, analyze errors, and subsequently adjust their decisions. It is concluded that the use of digital tools for glaze modeling creates conditions for the development of technological thinking as an essential component of the professional training of design students.*

Keywords: *artistic ceramics, ceramic glazes, technological thinking, design students, digital learning tools, glaze modeling, thesaurus approach*

The training of design students within the domain of artistic ceramics inevitably entails the convergence of two foundational principles: the artistic and the technological. The former is associated with imagery, conceptualization, and the expressiveness of form and color. The latter concerns the material properties, composition, temperature regime, sequence of operations, and firing dynamics. In practical educational contexts, the most significant challenges arise precisely at the intersection of these principles. A student, as a rule, comparatively easily forms an aesthetic conception of the future product but encounters difficulties when this conception must be translated into the terminology of technological operations. [2]

This contradiction is particularly pronounced in engagement with glazes. In the educational process, the glaze is often understood solely as a final decorative coating. However, it constitutes a complex system wherein color, texture, gloss, fluidity, transparency, strength, and compatibility with the ceramic body depend on the proportion of components and the firing regime. If a student does not recognize this connection, they are placed in the role of a performer who is forced to act according to a template but is unable to consciously adapt the technology to their own artistic objective.

An important pedagogical conclusion follows from this: in the professional training of a designer, it is insufficient to develop isolated glazing skills. It is essential to cultivate technological thinking — that is, the capacity to understand the relationship between artistic intention, material composition, method of processing, and the resulting effect. Technological thinking is expressed in the ability to reproduce a known operation and in the capability to analyze task conditions, compare alternatives, make a reasoned choice, anticipate consequences, and, in the event of failure, to adjust the solution accordingly. [3]

However, this aspect of training remains the least adequately supported. The available instructional time is limited. A substantial portion of the ceramics literature is either outdated or aimed at production technologists rather than students of artistic specialties. Consequently, teaching often proceeds along one of two trajectories. Either complex issues are unduly simplified, reducing the technology to a mere collection of ready-made recipes and instructions. Or, conversely, students are provided with an excessive volume of chemical-technological information, which fails to be assimilated into their professional consciousness, remaining external and inactive knowledge. In both instances, a comprehensive understanding of the process does not materialize.

In this context, digital tools for glaze modeling acquire particular significance. Their value consists not only in accelerating calculations. Far more importantly, they render hidden technological dependencies visible and comparable. Students acquire the capability to mix components without prior knowledge of the outcome and observe how changes in composition influence the properties of the glaze, how the same artistic intent may be realized through different approaches, and which variations are permissible versus those that lead to system failure. In this way, the digital tool shifts technology from the sphere of vague assumptions into the realm of observable and verifiable knowledge. [4]

For design students, this circumstance holds particular importance. Their professional thinking is predominantly figurative and visual. Accordingly, technological knowledge must be presented in the form of visual correlations, charts, templates, comparisons, and archives of observations. The digital environment satisfies this requirement. It allows for the visualization of chemical and physical interactions,

the systematization of experiments, the documentation of changes, and the ability to revisit previously obtained results. Thus, technological knowledge becomes the object of the student's independent mental work.

From a pedagogical standpoint, this implies a transition from the assimilation of ready-made instructions to modeling and analysis. The student enters the glaze composition, correlates it with the desired artistic effect, obtains the calculation, performs a trial firing, observes the firing result, records the discrepancy between the expected and actual outcomes, and subsequently makes corrections. Within this sequence, the moment of reflecting on the error is particularly important. An error stops being a simple flaw. It becomes a source of understanding, as it reveals precisely which parameter was unaccounted for and at what point the artistic intent was not technologically ensured. At this stage, the digital tool begins to fulfill an educational role. It aids the student in developing a new recipe and constructing an internal system of relationships between concepts and phenomena. Put differently, a professional thesaurus is formed — a structured set of knowledge, representations, and relationships through which the student begins to think as a future specialist. At the outset of training, the glaze is perceived as an external decorative layer; however, as students engage with modeling, it begins to be understood as the outcome of a controlled interaction among the composition, temperature, substrate, and artistic objective.

The web service Segerlab, developed as a tool for both educational and practical work with ceramic glazes, merits special attention. Its use liberates students from the indiscriminate selection of recipes and guides them toward the deliberate design of glaze compositions. Through the use of the service, the student is not confined to calculating proportions but establishes a connection between the chemical composition of the glaze and the anticipated technological and decorative properties of the coating. This provides the opportunity for precise comparison of variants, identification of dependencies between the recipe and the firing results, as well as consistent documentation and systematic organization of trials. Significantly, Segerlab renders specialized knowledge accessible to students specializing in the artistic domain: complex technological relationships are presented in a clear and visual manner conducive to autonomous reasoning. Therefore, this tool should be understood as a means of fostering technological thinking, as it trains the future designer to perceive glaze as a system whose functioning is governed by specific regularities. Since 2025, it has been integrated into the educational practice of the St. Petersburg State Art and Industry Academy named after A. L. Shtiglitz and the Siberian Institute of Design and Technologies. The incorporation of these institutions into the educational process attests to the recognition of digital glaze modeling as an effective pedagogical instrument.

The practical significance of digital tools is particularly prominent in instances when a student conducts a series of glaze trials. Within a traditional workflow, each new trial is often considered in isolation. The digital system enables preservation of the recipe, incorporation of images, documentation of firing conditions, annotation of observations, and subsequent comparative analysis of trial series. Consequently, an organized archive of observations is accumulated. This archive becomes a crucial component of professional formation, as it cultivates the student's ability to think within a framework of variant systems and interdependencies.

It should be particularly emphasized that the digital tool does not replace hands-on practice and does not eliminate the necessity of material experimentation. Digital modeling significantly enhances the quality of practice by reducing the proportion of random actions, assisting in the precise design of experiments, enabling justified comparison of results, and thereby strengthening the educational impact of each trial firing.

This holds fundamental importance for contemporary artistic education. The limited instructional time does not permit the comprehensive transmission to students of the full scope of specialized knowledge in the chemistry and technology of glazes. Consequently, the university's objective is to equip students with tools for autonomous technological thinking. If a student is able to pose questions, select parameters, document outcomes, analyze deviations, and implement adjustments, they are capable of pursuing professional development beyond the formal curriculum [1].

Therefore, the application of digital tools for glaze modeling should be considered a critical factor in the development of technological thinking among design students. Their pedagogical value consists in connecting the artistic intent with technological reasoning, making the complex interrelations within the material visible, supporting autonomous exploration, and facilitating the transition from fragmented experience to systemic understanding. Within the framework of an art university, this enables bridging the gap between the aesthetic and technical components of training and approximates the educational process to the actual professional tasks.

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DIGITAL PORTFOLIO AS A TOOL FOR DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL-COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PHILOLOGISTS

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Abstract. *The digital transformation of higher education significantly influences the professional training of future philologists. Modern philological practice increasingly requires the integration of linguistic, analytical, editorial, and digital competencies. In this context, digital instruments become not only instruments for learning but also platforms for demonstrating professional development. The purpose of this study is to substantiate the role of a digital portfolio as a professional tool for developing and demonstrating professional-communicative competence among future philologists. The article analyzes the theoretical foundations of professional-communicative competence and identifies its key subcomponents: cognitive-linguistic, pragma-editorial, digital-interpretative, and discourse competencies. The study proposes a structural model of a digital portfolio consisting of analytical, editing, communicative, and reflective blocks, each representing specific professional skills. Particular attention is paid to the integration of national digital instruments and platforms used in Kazakhstan, including ISSAI KAZ-LLM, Kazterm, AI-YM, and other digital instruments for linguistic analysis and text processing. The results demonstrate that the digital portfolio functions not only as a repository of academic work but also as a mechanism for professional self-presentation, competence assessment, and reflective learning. The digital portfolio reflects the formation of a professional profile of a philologist and allows*

students to demonstrate their competencies in real professional contexts. The proposed approach contributes to the modernization of philological education and supports the development of future specialists capable of working effectively in digital communication environments.

Keywords: *digital portfolio, professional-communicative competence, future philologists, digital instruments, philological education, digital transformation, professional profile.*

The rapid digital transformation of modern society has significantly influenced the development of higher education and professional training systems. Digital instruments are actively integrated into academic environments, changing the traditional approaches to learning, communication, and professional interaction. In the field of philological education, digitalization has led to the emergence of new forms of linguistic analysis, text processing, and intercultural communication.

The professional activity of future philologists is increasingly associated with digital communication environments, multilingual information flows, and media discourse. Modern specialists in philology are expected not only to possess strong linguistic competencies but also to demonstrate skills in analyzing digital texts, editing media content, interpreting information, and communicating in diverse professional contexts [1].

Consequently, the development of professional-communicative competence becomes a central objective of philological education. This competence includes the ability to understand, produce, analyze, and adapt texts according to professional requirements and communicative situations. At the same time, it requires the ability to use digital instruments effectively in linguistic and professional practice.

One of the promising tools for developing and demonstrating professional-communicative competencies in the digital educational environment is the digital portfolio. Unlike traditional assessment methods, the digital portfolio allows students to collect, structure, and present the results of their professional activities in a digital format. It becomes a dynamic representation of the student's professional development and academic achievements.

The relevance of this study lies in the need to integrate digital tools into the system of professional training for future philologists and to develop mechanisms for demonstrating their professional-communicative competencies. The digital portfolio can serve as an effective instrument for reflecting the professional profile of a philologist and for documenting the process of competence formation [2].

The aim of this research is to theoretically substantiate the role of a digital portfolio as a tool for developing professional-communicative competence among future philologists and to propose a structural model of such a portfolio within the context of digital philological education.

Professional-communicative competence represents a complex integrative characteristic of a specialist that combines linguistic knowledge, communicative skills, and the ability to apply them effectively in professional contexts. In the training of future philologists, this competence plays a key role because their future professional activities are directly related to language mediation, translation, editing, discourse analysis, and intercultural communication.

Within the framework of this research, professional-communicative competence is considered as a multi-component structure consisting of several interrelated sub-competencies.

Cognitive-linguistic sub-competence. The cognitive-linguistic sub-competence involves the development of linguistic and cognitive skills necessary for effective language processing. It includes knowledge of grammar, vocabulary, syntax, and stylistic norms, as well as the ability to understand, analyze, and interpret texts in different communicative situations.

This sub-competence also involves the ability to process information, identify semantic structures, and understand the contextual meanings of linguistic units. For future foreign philologists, cognitive-linguistic competence forms the foundation for professional linguistic activities such as translation, editing, and discourse analysis.

Pragma-editorial sub-competence. The pragma-editorial sub-competence is related to the ability to construct and edit texts in accordance with professional communication requirements. It includes skills in text structuring, stylistic editing, genre adaptation, and audience-oriented communication [3].

Future philologists must be able to adapt texts for different professional contexts, including academic publications, media content, analytical reviews, and professional correspondence. This competence also includes the ability to evaluate textual coherence, stylistic consistency, and communicative effectiveness.

Digital-interpretative sub-competence. Digital-interpretative competence reflects the ability to analyze and interpret information using digital instruments and platforms. Modern philological practice requires the use of computational linguistic tools, digital corpora, and artificial intelligence technologies to analyze language data and media texts.

The development of this competence enables future philologists to work with digital sources of information, analyze large volumes of textual data, and interpret linguistic patterns using modern digital instruments.

Discourse sub-competence. Discourse competence involves the ability to organize communication effectively in different professional and cultural contexts. It includes skills in oral and written communication, argumentation, professional dialogue, and intercultural interaction.

Future philologists must be capable of constructing coherent discourse, participating in professional discussions, and adapting communication strategies according to social and cultural contexts.

The development of these sub-competencies requires methodological approaches that support meaningful modeling of professional activities. The principle of semantic modeling and the functional-stylistic approach play an important role in structuring educational tasks and professional training activities.

In the digital educational environment, the digital portfolio represents an innovative instrument for documenting and demonstrating professional-communicative competence. Unlike traditional assessment methods, which focus on isolated academic tasks, the digital portfolio provides a holistic representation of a student's professional development.

The digital portfolio should not be considered merely as a learning resource or a collection of assignments. Instead, it functions as a professional platform that reflects the competencies, achievements, and professional growth of future specialists [4].

For future philologists, the digital portfolio allows them to demonstrate a wide range of professional activities, including linguistic analysis, editorial work, translation practice, and media discourse interpretation. Through digital portfolios, students can systematically collect evidence of their professional competence and present their work in structured digital formats.

The digital portfolio also supports reflective learning processes. Students analyze their own professional development, evaluate the quality of their work, and identify areas for improvement. This reflective dimension contributes to the formation of professional identity and self-assessment skills.

Moreover, digital portfolios are increasingly used in professional environments as tools for presenting professional profiles. Employers and academic institutions often evaluate candidates based on digital evidence of their skills and achievements. Therefore, the digital portfolio becomes a bridge between academic education and professional practice.

The proposed structure of the digital portfolio is shown in Table 1, it includes several functional blocks, each designed to demonstrate specific aspects of professional-communicative competence.

Table 1. Descriptions of blocks.

Analytical Block	<p>The analytical block focuses on the analysis of media texts and linguistic materials. Students perform discourse analysis, semantic interpretation, and stylistic evaluation of various types of texts, including journalistic articles, digital media publications, and academic texts.</p> <p>This block demonstrates the development of cognitive-linguistic and digital-interpretative competencies. Analytical tasks may include identifying rhetorical strategies, evaluating linguistic structures, and interpreting communicative intentions in media discourse.</p>
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<p>Editing Block</p>	<p>The editing block includes tasks related to text editing, stylistic correction, and linguistic refinement. Students work with texts that require structural editing, grammatical correction, and stylistic adaptation.</p> <p>Through these tasks, students develop pragma-editorial competence and acquire professional skills in preparing texts for publication.</p>
<p>Communicative Block</p>	<p>The communicative block contains professional texts created by students, including analytical essays, reviews, commentaries, and professional correspondence. These texts demonstrate the student’s ability to produce coherent discourse in professional contexts.</p> <p>The communicative block highlights the development of discourse competence and professional writing skills.</p>
<p>Reflective Block</p>	<p>The reflective block focuses on self-assessment and professional development. Students analyze their progress, evaluate their achievements, and formulate personal professional goals.</p> <p>Reflection plays a crucial role in professional-communicative competence formation because it encourages students to critically evaluate their work and understand their professional trajectory.</p>

Figure 1. Structure of the digital portfolio for future philologists.

Figure 1 presents the structure of the digital portfolio for future philologists. An important aspect of the proposed digital portfolio model is the integration of national digital instruments used in Kazakhstan.

Students can analyze media texts using instruments such as ISSAI KAZ-LLM, which allows for linguistic analysis and semantic interpretation of texts. The Kazterm platform provides terminological resources for working with specialized vocabulary in different professional fields.

Another useful tool is AI-YM, which supports digital text processing and linguistic analysis. These platforms enable students to analyze texts, verify terminology, and improve linguistic accuracy.

In addition to national resources, students may also use international digital instruments for corpus analysis, translation assistance, and text editing. The integration of these instruments into educational practice helps students develop professional-communicative competence.

Digital tasks may include media text analysis, terminology verification, stylistic editing of texts, preparation of analytical reviews, and creation of professional commentary on digital media content.

Such activities allow students to combine theoretical linguistic knowledge with practical digital skills, creating a comprehensive learning environment.

The implementation of the digital portfolio model contributes to the systematic development of professional-communicative competence among future philologists.

The digital portfolio enables students to demonstrate the formation of cognitive-linguistic, pragma-editorial, digital-interpretative and discourse sub-competencies. By organizing their work within a structured digital environment, students develop the ability to present their professional achievements in a coherent and accessible format.

Another important outcome is the development of reflective skills. Students learn to evaluate their own progress and identify the strengths and weaknesses of their professional preparation.

The digital portfolio also serves as a representation of the professional profile of a philologist. Through the portfolio, students create a digital representation of their professional identity, which can later be used in academic and professional contexts.

Experimental implementation of the digital portfolio. To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed digital portfolio model in developing professional-communicative competence, a pilot educational experiment was conducted among third-year students majoring in Foreign Philology at a KazUIR&WL named after Ablai khan.

The experiment involved 42 undergraduate students, divided into two groups: a control group (20 students) and an experimental group (22 students). Both groups studied within the same academic course related to professional-communicative

competence and media text analysis. However, the experimental group additionally implemented the proposed digital portfolio system throughout the semester.

At the beginning of the semester, students in the experimental group were introduced to the structure of the digital portfolio, which included four main blocks: analytical, editing, communicative, and reflective. Each block contained specific professional tasks designed to develop corresponding sub-competencies.

Within the analytical block, students analyzed media texts using digital instruments such as ISSAI KAZ-LLM and Kazterm. The tasks included identifying key discourse strategies, evaluating linguistic structures, and interpreting communicative intentions in media publications.

The editing block involved professional text editing tasks. Students worked with academic and media texts that required stylistic correction, structural editing, and terminology verification using digital resources.

Within the communicative block, students created their own professional texts, including analytical essays, commentaries, and reviews. These tasks were designed to develop their ability to produce coherent professional discourse in digital communication environments.

The reflective block encouraged students to evaluate their progress and document their professional development. Students recorded reflections on completed tasks, identified difficulties, and formulated strategies for improving their professional skills.

At the end of the semester, the level of professional-communicative competence in both groups was assessed using a set of evaluation criteria, including linguistic accuracy, discourse organization, text editing quality, and the ability to use digital instruments in professional tasks.

The results demonstrated a noticeable improvement in the experimental group compared to the control group. Students who used the digital portfolio showed higher levels of analytical thinking, improved text editing skills, and greater confidence in producing professional written discourse.

In particular, the experimental group demonstrated:

- improved ability to analyze media texts and identify discourse strategies,
- increased accuracy in professional text editing,
- better organization of professional written communication,
- higher levels of digital literacy in linguistic analysis instruments,

In addition, students reported that the digital portfolio helped them better understand their professional development and allowed them to visualize their progress throughout the semester.

The digital portfolio also functioned as a digital representation of the students' professional profiles, enabling them to demonstrate their competencies through structured digital evidence of their work.

Thus, the experimental implementation confirmed that the digital portfolio is an effective pedagogical tool for developing professional-communicative competence among future philologists. The integration of analytical, editorial, communicative, and reflective tasks within a digital environment contributes to a more systematic and practice-oriented professional training process.

Table 2. Results of the experimental implementation of the digital portfolio model.

Indicator	Control group	Experimental group
Media text analysis	68 %	84 %
Text editing accuracy	65 %	82 %
Professional writing	70 %	86 %
Use of digital instruments	60 %	88 %

Thus, the digital portfolio becomes not only an educational tool but also a mechanism for professional self-presentation and career development.

The digital transformation of higher education requires the modernization of professional training approaches in philological education. The development of professional-communicative competence among future philologists must incorporate digital instruments, modern linguistic tools, and innovative educational methods.

The digital portfolio represents an effective tool for documenting and demonstrating professional-communicative competence. It integrates analytical, editorial, communicative, and reflective activities, allowing students to develop a comprehensive professional profile.

The proposed structure of the digital portfolio supports the systematic development of key competencies and provides opportunities for reflective learning and professional self-presentation. The integration of national digital instruments used in Kazakhstan further strengthens the relevance of this approach for modern philological education.

Ultimately, the digital portfolio reflects the formation of the professional profile of a philologist and serves as an important mechanism for bridging academic training and professional-communicative competence.

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**FROM ARCHIVAL DOCUMENTS TO MONOGRAPHIC
RESEARCH: EQUIPMENT, CONNECTION WITH LITERATURE,
AND CONCLUSIONS**

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Abstract: *In the present work, the author focuses on analyzing the sources that form the foundation of the narrative: documents from state archives, governmental agencies, and personal archives. In this context, the historical significance is demonstrated through examples of events that occurred in Soviet history and are partially reflected in the literature. The study highlights the crucial importance of combining archival information with the findings of humanities research on the relevant topics found in existing publications for fully addressing the issue. In connection with the forced resettlement of peoples in the USSR, the author cites an example from the first study on the topic — “Caucasian Eagles.” The study of the topic as a whole exposes the detrimental nature of the punitive measures imposed on the peoples of the North Caucasus and concludes on the possibility of preventing similar incidents.*

Keywords: *state, archives, references, events, ethnic minorities, “Caucasian Eagles,” resettlement, review, publication*

Discussion. Undoubtedly, it is essential to have a clear understanding of state documents that reveal the events under study, as well as documents from archives of state agencies (which may maintain permanent collections of documents — for example, the meteorological service within the state, among others), and also personal archives, which can serve as a valuable alternative source in terms of content. However, it is necessary to study these as well. Often, they contain valuable information and enable the problem under investigation to be considered from a completely different perspective, fundamentally altering previously established judgments, opinions, and evaluations. The practice of researching historical events in the country often leads to entirely different conclusions. Typically, personal

archives may hold valuable information on many events (compiled shortly after they occurred) and preserved in private settings. When a new archival collection is assembled, this task is not always carried out by a specialist; it is sometimes entrusted to a non-specialist, such as a secretary, and so forth.

Of course, an important point for the researcher is that the event is documented in the materials and that it is presented from its inception to its conclusion. In such cases, the researcher has the opportunity to perform a more thorough analysis of the phenomenon under study, formulate conclusions, evaluate the issue investigated, and analyze the impact of the event's outcomes on the subsequent development of the situation.

Why is attention drawn specifically to the publication "Caucasian Eagles"? This is primarily explained by the preparation of the work based on fresh evidence. The content of events indicates that all planned measures overseen by those responsible for this area of the peoples' lives were implemented based on fresh evidence, with the initial conclusions presented accordingly. A review compiled on the basis of intelligence and operational materials received from the NKVD in the Grozny region regarding the investigation of 88 citizens conducted between March and July 1945. The Anti-Banditry Department of the Kazakh SSR, as well as materials compiled on the bandit movement within the territory of the Chechen-Ingush ASSR. The prepared review was approved on August 8, 1945. By the People's Commissar for Internal Affairs of the Kazakh SSR, Lieutenant General N. K. Bogdanov.

As explained by People's Commissar N. K. Bogdanov in the address: 'To all heads of the NKVD, heads of District (RO) and City (GO) NKVD of the Kazakh SSR' dated August 10, 1945, all these measures were undertaken with the aim of:

- 'timely detecting and preventing any attempts and plans by former rebel bandits among the special settlers from the North Caucasus;'
- to suppress attempts to shift into illegal status and organize bandit gangs in Kazakhstan by former rebel bandits;
- to promptly detect and prevent any attempts and plots by former rebel bandits among special settlers from the North Caucasus;
- to develop specific intelligence-operational measures to enhance the agency work targeting rebel bandit special settlers from the North Caucasus;

In view of the foregoing, a conclusion follows. Undoubtedly, similar work was carried out in the territories of other administrative units with the residence of special settlers, primarily Russian Germans, as well as other ethnic groups. Naturally, reports and other analytical documents were prepared for each of them. Similar work was also conducted by officers of the USSR NKVD, particularly in the Kazakh SSR.

Stalin I. He did not accede to the requests of the leaders of the autonomous republics. It is a known fact that the chairman of the Council of People's Commissars

of the Chechen-Ingush ASSR, Mollaev, was informed about the government's decision regarding the deportation of Chechens and Ingush and the motives underpinning this decision. Undoubtedly, Mollaev understood the harmfulness of such measures. What else could he do? As L. reported, Beria to Stalin: 'After his report, Mollaev teared up but pulled himself together and promised to fulfill the tasks assigned to him in connection with the resettlement...'¹

To I. Stalin and L. Beria appealed with requests not to carry out the resettlement of the entire population, but to punish only those responsible, addressing also the leadership of the Kabardino-Balkarian and Kalmyk ASSRs. Ultimately, the study of this issue within the period from 1937 to 1942 was notably marked by an intensification of anti-Soviet activities by hostile elements. This is also confirmed by statistics showing increased connections with German intelligence.

The documents, especially with the publication of new materials, were even disseminated among the personnel of the supervisory bodies in this field, which raises the question: was it necessary to deport representatives of the non-working population — elderly people, women, and children — and to resort to such a social technology as forced resettlement? It is possible that such work was not carried out in all regions of the new settlements of special settlers, but nonetheless, 3.5 million people were subjected by the authorities to destructive impact through forced resettlement to such remote locations within the territory of the USSR.

In practice, similar difficulties often arise in the preparation of scholarly works concerning the formation and development of historical science itself, as well as the historian's role as an individual.

In 2018–2019, by Doctors of Historical Sciences T. S. Bushueva in co-authorship with N. F. Bugay, the monographs were published for the first time: "Semyon Kuzmich Bushuev. Scholar, Diplomat, Patriot." Moscow, 2018. 146 pp. and "Semyon Kuzmich Bushuev — a Benchmark in Historical Science. 1930–1950." Moscow, 2019. 636 pp. An article about Bushuev, spanning one and a half pages, was published in 1958 in Bulletin No. 3 of Moscow State University named after M. V. Lomonosov, pp. 209–210.

From 1937 onwards, S. Bushuev worked in Leningrad, and later in Moscow. It was here that his scientific activity developed until the late 1930s, especially during the establishment of the Cabinet of the History of the Peoples of the USSR within the structure of the Institute of History of the USSR Academy of Sciences. This represented a new direction in scholarly research. S. Bushuev devoted himself entirely to science. He left a rich legacy for future generations in more than a dozen monographic studies, all based on a solid documentary foundation.

¹ Caucasian Eagles. Review of materials on the bandit movement in the territory of the former Chechen-Ingush ASSR. Alma-Ata, 1945. p. 2.

His attention was drawn to the history of autonomies and the history of Islam. He makes a significant contribution to the development of the history of the Muslim republics of the Kabardino-Balkarian, Dagestan ASSR, Adyghe AO, and Chechen-Ingush ASSR.

To a considerable extent, the comprehensive coverage of the fate of this Russian historian and scholar relies on the personal archive of S. Bushuev, preserved by his family. For many years, it remained unstudied and undescribed for various reasons. At the same time, turning to the archive made it possible to uncover the richest and most interesting information about the life of the scholar, a true patriot of his state. The documents are devoted, to varying degrees, to all stages of the life of the scholar-historian. In the life of S. Bushuev recalled the meeting of the Academic Council of the Institute of History of the USSR Academy of Sciences with its active members on May 29, 1938, at which the question of further improving achievements and increasing efficiency in the work of the Office of the History of the Peoples of the USSR was discussed. Academician of the USSR Academy of Sciences B. D. Grekov spoke on the issue of the history of the peoples of the country, noting: «First of all, we will formulate the thematic framework necessary for the history of the peoples of the USSR, primarily focusing on the history of the Russian people.» In second place are topics that should «portray heroic chapters in the history of our peoples ...». Attention was also given to the speech of I. Stalin, delivered on May 17, 1938, addressed to teachers and higher education workers. In his commentary, S. K. Bushuev examined the content of V. I. Stalin's speech and evaluated it as «a fighting program for all Soviet science.»¹²

At the end of the 1930s, based on the establishment of Guomindang hegemonic unity, the USSR Ministry of Foreign Affairs, by expanding cooperation with China and with the Communist Party of China — orienting it towards democratic construction — regarded friendship with the USSR as the only realistic means to achieve victory over Japan, without which victory was inconceivable. China obtained a League of Nations decision to impose sanctions against Japan. Chaikanshiya, relying on this campaign, raised the issue of concluding a mutual assistance pact with the USSR. The situation at the front was already difficult, with military resources strained and economic and financial resources catastrophically diminished — they had been exhausted. The USSR provided assistance to China. In early December, the first steamer carrying military and economic cargo departed from the port of Sevastopol to the port of Hai Phong along route Z, followed by three additional vessels. The last steamer arrived at the port of Rangoon in April 1939. The cargo operation was led by Colonel Semyon Kuzmich Bushuyev (alias — Syn Keide). In November 1944,

¹ARAN. F. 1577. Inv. 2. File 7. Sheet 12.

²Ibid., p. 162.

S. K. Bushuyev was awarded the Order of the Badge of Honor for outstanding services to the Soviet state and successful completion of a Government assignment. At that time, S. K. Bushuyev was the director of the Higher Diplomatic School of the USSR Ministry of Foreign Affairs. Bushuev was an example of worthy service to the Fatherland. He was a father, historian, diplomat, and scholar who possessed dozens of different scientific disciplines and had extensive experience in research work and engagement with the student audience. This is a vivid example of how rich the material in a personal archive can be¹.

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PUBLIC CONTROL: HISTORY AND APPROACHES

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Annotation. *The article analyzes the key points of the history of public control institutions, modern foreign concepts and approaches to the implementation of public control; analyzes the features of its formation, problems, and achievements in this regard within the framework of Uzbekistan. For this purpose, the article used the historical-chronological method, comparative approaches. It is necessary, concludes the author, to further increase the level of political culture of the population, and study deeper domestic and foreign experience in this field.*

Key words: *Society, public control, people, purpose, responsibility, participation, experience*

INTRODUCTION

At the current stage, in many countries, in a context of instability and growing geopolitical, economic, social, and ethnic problems, the establishment of mutually relations between the State and civil society remains a crucial issue. In this process, the role of the institution of social control, which makes it possible to combine the resources of society and State structures on the path of peace, stability, and development is invaluable.

In Uzbekistan, this process conforms to the objectives of the Strategy for Action 2017–2021, which envisages further deepening of democratic reforms and modernization of the country. Accordingly, the country declared the development of a strong civil society — one of the most important priorities for its development. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Mr. Mirziyev, announced: “To date, there are no clear legal mechanisms for effective public monitoring of

the activities of State bodies. And this leads to barriers in the evaluation activities of state bodies and officials” [1].

One of the most pressing problems in society today is the intensification of corruption in the country, the prevention of unemployment, especially in the context of the pandemic, the lack of timely social and economic assistance for disabled persons, the systematization of financial assistance for single women and the development of rural areas. Public oversight is crucial to solving problems in programmes, road-building projects, poor quality, superficial work, problems in public services, civil courts, banking services and other.

To that end, it is necessary to improve the practical methods and mechanisms of public oversight for the protection of the legitimate rights and interests of citizens and to shape public interest and opinion in decisions and decisions.

In this connection, it should be noted that the study of the substance, content and forms, methods of public scrutiny by public organizations and theoretical and practical questions relating to its manifestation is one of the most pressing challenges facing scientists today. It should be noted that these issues are studied to varying degrees by domestic and foreign scientists as subjects of study. However, it is no exaggeration to say that scientific research on this problem is only beginning in Uzbekistan. Virtually no work has been done to study and generalize foreign experience and to analyze Uzbekistan’s problems, achievements and prospects in this area. This article attempts to fill some symbolic «problems» in this field by analysis and recommendations.

On the basis of the foregoing, the purpose of this article is to analyse the history of the institution of public oversight, the processes of its formation, specific mechanisms, methods, the culture of public oversight and contemporary views in Uzbekistan and abroad.

The novelty of the scientific article is that it is one of the first to analyse not only contemporary views on the institute of public control in the example of the Republic of Uzbekistan and foreign countries, but also explores common features and differences in this field. As a result, specific mechanisms and methods of social control, a culture of social control, a base of experience in this field and recommendations for their adaptation were examined.

THE HISTORY OF SOCIAL CONTROL

In order to better understand the essence of the institution of public control, we considered it appropriate the history of the formation of public control in some Western countries. The idea of social control in the United States has a long history. The fourth President of the United States, James Madison, wrote in Federalist newspaper: President Abraham Lincoln concludes his famous address to Gettinsburg in 1863 with the words: «The people’s power is a people’s

government created by people for people» [2]. and has acquired a unique wealth of experience in this field. In the United States, social control is exercised in two ways. The first is to express the wishes of these citizens directly, and the second is to express the wishes of the elected representatives of the people. It is noteworthy that it is not appropriate to speak of the superiority of two methods of control over one another, since together they serve the same purpose. In the United States, social control is exercised in two ways. The first is to express the wishes of these citizens directly, and the second is to provide citizens with full information about government activities, citizens' participation in the management of public affairs through investigative journalism, local government bodies, citizens' assemblies, public hearings, research, journalism and the creation of works of art that shape public opinion and influence the ruling elite. Public scrutiny of draft laws, etc. is carried out through parliamentary oversight, the legislative body and the representative body of local self-government. These methods constitute widespread social control over government, and the two methods have worked in harmony for centuries.

In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, non-governmental and non-profit organizations began to form in the United Kingdom. Proceeding from this, the principles of support and mutual assistance of people affected by World War II contributed to the development of the activities of non-governmental non-profit organizations. — this is the characteristic. As a result, many NGOs began their activities as a result of aid initiatives undertaken during the war. These include the Organization for the Protection of Children, founded in 1919 by sisters Dorothy Buxton and Eglantine Jeb, and the Oxford Committee, founded in 1942 by Oxfam. During the war, the organization participated in charitable activities, for example, working with refugees and fleeing hunger. These include the Christian Support Organization, which has been active in the European region since 1945 [3].

By 1957, the Treaty of Rome signed by Western European countries opened up a wide range of opportunities for civil society organizations and civil society organizations, and all socio-political and economic decisions taken by the European Economic and Social Committee provided great opportunities for civil institutions and organizations. These include: opinions in response to decisions taken by a commission, council or parliament; Participate, put forward initiatives and ideas on any issue that is considered relevant to the European Economic and Social Committee; At the request of the Committee, make proposals on the reflected topic [4].

Today, the EU sees the participation of citizens, EU institutions, and civil society institutions in the political process to advance democratic principles and public opinion not only as a necessity for NGO participation in politics and decision-making, but also as a requirement of a democratic system. They accept. NGOs monitor changes in EU institutions and analyze the dynamics of their impact. As a result,

NGOs often act as a referral system in their own countries, which has a decisive influence on key policy decisions. [5].

Thus, the idea of the institution of public control was formed on the basis of long historical processes. Therefore, there are different methods and tools for the formation of public control. The mechanisms of their use are also colorful. It depends on the history and mentality of each state.

MODERN VIEWS ON SOCIAL CONTROL

Today, there are many different views, opinions and perceptions about the Institute of Public Oversight. Modern scientific research in the field of social control is multifaceted and comprehensive, with a focus on this topic in both Western countries and Russia. In Uzbekistan, developments in this area have now begun to be reflected in scientific research with a new approach.

In this regard, Russian scientists carry out scientific work in various fields. For example, the first group of scientists studied the necessity, problems and prospects of public control over the police [6], the second group of Russian scientists analyzed the features of the development of civil society in Russia and built a strong civil society, emphasizing the importance of a commitment to improving public control [7].

A third group of scientists is distinguished by the fact that they mainly analyse social problems among the population on the basis of statistical data in the form of questionnaires [8]. The Trechnette group of scientists studied more the experience of social control in the United States. The researchers noted that the US has a wide range of opportunities and tools for public control, primarily based on the principles of transparent government, active citizen participation and collaborative efforts. The authors focus on specific methods in the United States, thus the establishment of social control over any power through social organizations and the media. This led to increased public control over the police in the United States, and in 1993 also led to the establishment of the Los Angeles County Sheriff's Special Council for Permanent Employees. This led to the emergence of the "model audit" of civilian oversight, one of two types of police oversight programs in the United States. Another model is that it typically involves voluntary action by citizens during incomplete work on specific complaints [9]. There are also studies of public control over local self-government based on foreign experience, comparative analysis of the Russian and US experience [10].

Today, in foreign studies, civil society institutions and non-governmental organizations are seen as influencing the implementation of political reforms in the country. In particular, these organizations perform functions such as the expression and control of public opinion in decision-making in the development of public education, health, the protection of workers' rights and other similar socio-economic spheres. In Sierra Leone, for example, there is a memorandum of understanding

between the Civic Education Organization and the Government, which controls the proper use of public funds. Every year the State allocates 20 per cent of the budget for education. In summary, while some elements of social control in the eastern states are similar to those of social control in the western states, other aspects generally prevail.

In Malawi, the Civil Society Education Coalition has been active in promoting the budget. Through high-level advocacy, the coalition facilitated the inclusion of education as a key priority in national development in 2011–2016. Expenditure on education increased from 12.5 per cent in 2010 to 16.3 per cent in 2016 as a proportion of total public expenditure. During this period, the share of education in GDP increased from 4.4 per cent to 6.9 per cent, making the country one of the highest in the country [11].

In Bangladesh, a coalition between the Ministry of Education and civil society has made a significant contribution to the development of science in the country. In particular, civil society institutions held public hearings in 2015 to discuss the education budget with local organizations. It also organized a policy dialogue on education funding with teachers' associations, party members, ministers and other influential public figures to develop the sector. The Coalition issued an open appeal to the Prime Minister to increase the education budget from the State budget to 20 per cent (currently 13 per cent) by 2021.

A number of scientific works on this subject have been carried out by our local scientists. For example, the essence of the concept of public control, some views on public control, the experience of some foreign countries in this regard, and the study of the legal bases of public control in the Republic of Uzbekistan [12] The principle of transparency and public scrutiny in civil proceedings. There are also monographs on transparency and public oversight of the activities of State authorities in Uzbekistan: establishment and development, and certain issues relating to the application of the principle of transparency in civil proceedings, as well as tools to ensure public oversight and improve civil proceedings [13].

A number of conclusions can be drawn from the studies of the above-mentioned scientists. Firstly, public oversight is the main effective form of control over the conduct of internal affairs and the judicial system in an open and transparent manner, as well as in the fight against corruption. Secondly, an important criterion is that citizens have a mutually trusting and positive relationship with the police, which in turn serves to ensure the full exercise of the rights and freedoms of every citizen. Thirdly, positive results in the development of the State and society can be achieved by establishing a legal basis for public control in the areas of education, health care and the State budget. Fourthly, in order to achieve these results, it is necessary to develop modern legal mechanisms for interaction between civil society institutions and public authorities.

CONCLUSION

From the above considerations and considerations it can be concluded that there are different methods and instruments in the formation of the institution of social control. Colorful and the mechanisms of their use. They are largely in harmony with the founding history of each State, national values, customs and traditions and universal human values.

However, there are commonalities and differences between state public oversight institutions. The similarities are mainly based on universal values, which are the basic principles of the rule of law, the desire to understand one's rights and freedoms, tolerance and the building of a civil society.

On the basis of the foregoing, it should be noted that, in view of the establishment of the institution of public oversight in Uzbekistan at a new stage, the principles of collectivism prevail over national values in the current political, social and economic processes, Rule of law, transparency, creativity, personal responsibility and initiative.

Practical results can be achieved by starting with the school bench. For example, to explore the ideas of our great scholars about social control in schools, classroom problem-solving roundtables, control groups, mobile lectures in high schools, and later to organize modern start-up events such as training, selection and motivation of managers. It is desirable that.

More study, analysis and adaptation of foreign experiences would also be useful. After all, today's efforts, measures to improve the legal framework, are, in the final analysis, the most important guarantee for the realization of our noble goals, such as the establishment and development of a democratic State, based on the rule of law and a strong civil society.

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THE INFLUENCE OF THE COLD WAR ON THE TRANSFORMATION OF THE ENEMY IMAGE IN SOVIET ANIMATION

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the transformation of the image of the enemy in Soviet animation within the cultural dynamics of the Cold War. Unlike live-action cinema, where ideological confrontation for a long time retained the form of direct representation, animation demonstrates a gradual aestheticization of conflict and a transformation of the functions of political satire. The study shows that in the postwar period the image of the enemy passed through several stages of transformation: from direct political caricature to a cultural-stylistic code and later to internal social criticism. The analysis draws upon research on the history of Soviet animation, the cultural politics of the Cold War, and the international artistic contacts of animation studios. The article concludes that Soviet animation functioned as a sensitive indicator of broader cultural shifts and reflects the gradual displacement of ideological conflict from the sphere of direct propaganda into the domain of artistic form.*

Keywords: *Soviet animation, Cold War, cultural policy, enemy image, political satire, auteur animation.*

The Influence of the Cold War on the Transformation of the Enemy Image in Soviet Animation: From Political Satire to an Aesthetic Code

Introduction

Twentieth-century Soviet animation represents a unique case of interaction between artistic form and state cultural policy. Unlike live-action cinema, which remained under constant ideological supervision, animation for a long time was perceived as a secondary and primarily children's art form. This perception created a particular space for artistic maneuverability. It is precisely this institutional position that makes animation a sensitive indicator of changes in the cultural logic of the Cold War era [1].

Traditionally, the influence of the Cold War on Soviet cinema has been analyzed through the prism of ideological confrontation and the representation of an external enemy. However, when applied to animation, such an approach proves insufficient. At the level of visual language it becomes evident that changes in the political context did not lead to a direct replacement of the wartime fascist enemy with the capitalist-imperialist opponent. On the contrary, during the 1950s political satire almost disappeared from the animated screen, giving way to other artistic strategies [2].

This article proceeds from the assumption that the Cold War affected Soviet animation primarily not through narrative content but through a transformation of the functions of artistic form. As a result, the image of the enemy underwent a gradual transformation: from a politically specific character to an aesthetically mediated visual code and eventually to an internal, systemic object of satire during the Perestroika period.

The aim of this study is to trace the transformation of the representation of the “Other” in Soviet animation in the context of the Cold War and to demonstrate how institutional, production-related, and international factors reshaped the very language of animated expression.

The research is based on the understanding of the Cold War not only as a political confrontation but also as a cultural process in which art functioned as a tool of ideological influence and international symbolic competition [3].

Within the framework of this study, the transformation of animated language is analyzed through four interconnected levels:

- ideological
- production-related
- international
- auteur-based

It is precisely the intersection of these factors that leads to the gradual shift in the function of the enemy image. If in early Soviet animation the enemy appeared as a politically concrete character, by the 1960s-1970s it increasingly turned into a set of stylistic markers — a kind of “idea of the West” expressed through visual elements of urban space, comic-book plasticity, and motifs of mass culture [4].

Thus, in animation the Cold War appears less as a direct ideological confrontation and more as a process of aesthetic transformation of artistic language.

Main Discussion

In prewar and wartime Soviet animation political satire played an important mobilizing role. Caricatured depictions of the enemy relied on direct demonization and a sharp opposition between “us” and “them.” Such strategies were characteristic of propaganda films of the 1930s and 1940s and were rooted in the traditions of political caricature [5].

However, the postwar period was marked by a significant change in rhetorical strategies. Humanistic and life-affirming themes came to the forefront, which significantly limited the possibilities for direct political satire.

Paradoxically, the beginning of the Cold War was accompanied not by an intensification of political satire but by its almost complete disappearance from Soviet animation. This process was connected less with direct political suppression than with the search for a distinctive artistic identity after a period of strong influence from American animation.

The campaign against “Disneyism” led to a revision of the aesthetic orientation of Soviet animation [6]. A telling example is the reception of the film *Bambi*, which Soviet ideological institutions perceived as incompatible with the humanistic rhetoric of postwar Soviet culture. At the same time, the widespread use of the eclair (rotoscoping) technique strengthened the tendency toward realism, bringing animation closer to live-action cinema and reducing the expressive potential of the grotesque conventions characteristic of earlier satirical forms [7].

Nevertheless, in the second half of the 1950s satire gradually returned — initially directed toward everyday and social issues and later evolving into more complex forms of politically mediated commentary. The reappearance of political satire in Soviet animation during the 1960s did not signify a simple restoration of the prewar model of caricatured enemies. Instead, this period witnessed a transformation in the very nature of representing the external adversary.

Whereas in the 1930s and 1940s the enemy appeared as a clearly identifiable political figure, in the 1960s it increasingly became a stylistic and cultural code.

The cultural thaw created institutional conditions for the development of auteur animation, where strategies of double coding emerged and the artistic language became more complex [8]. This transformation is clearly visible in Roman Davydov’s film *The Shareholders* (1963), whose visual style deliberately references Western comic-book aesthetics. At the same time, some films continued to rely on the traditional language of political caricature. For instance, the animated adaptation of Samuil Marshak’s poem *Mister Twister* (1963) preserves the grotesque representation of a capitalist character.

Thus, the 1960s should be understood as a transitional period in which two models coexist: the continuation of traditional political satire and the emergence of a new aesthetic strategy in which the West appears primarily as a cultural sign. This transformation coincided with the increasing integration of Soviet animators into the international professional community. Soviet artists began to perceive animation as a field of international artistic competition [9]. Under the conditions of the Cold War, animation increasingly functioned as an instrument of cultural diplomacy and soft power [11].

During this period a particular cultural “idea of the West” emerged. It was conveyed through stable visual markers — skyscrapers, urban environments, jazz rhythms, and elements of mass culture [4].

By the early 1970s Soviet animation had reached a stage of relative artistic autonomy. This phase was associated with the development of auteur animation and a gradual shift away from narrative ideological functions toward the exploration of the expressive possibilities of the medium itself [8].

Within the conditions of relative institutional stability, animation gained greater freedom to experiment with form. Unlike live-action cinema, where ideological supervision remained stricter, animation continued to be perceived as a domain of artistic convention and play.

As a result, the role of direct political satire gradually diminished. The function of conflict itself underwent a fundamental change: whereas earlier the external enemy structured the narrative, the conflict was now increasingly transferred into the internal structure of the artistic form.

By the late 1970s Soviet animation occupied a unique position. While remaining institutionally embedded within the state system, it simultaneously functioned as a space of artistic modernism in which ideological conflict existed largely in an aesthetically transformed form.

By the mid-1980s the institutional and ideological conditions of Soviet animation changed dramatically. The weakening of censorship mechanisms and the gradual dismantling of the previous system of cultural control led not only to the expansion of thematic possibilities but also to a shift in the status of artistic form itself.

Whereas in the 1960s and 1970s auteur animation developed strategies of allegory and double coding, during the period of Perestroika the necessity of these protective mechanisms gradually disappeared. Allegory, which previously served as a means of indirect expression, lost its obligatory character.

This produced an unexpected effect: the aesthetically complex language of late Soviet animation began to be used for direct and often harsh political commentary. However, Perestroika did not create a new artistic language but rather radicalized an already existing one.

An important symptom of this transformation was the change in the nature of satire. While in the 1970s the critical potential of animation had been directed mainly toward local social distortions, by the second half of the 1980s irony and parody increasingly targeted the value system of late socialism itself.

A characteristic example is the work of Garri Bardin. In *Grey Wolf and Little Red Riding Hood* (1990), familiar fairy-tale structures undergo ironic reinterpretation, and the figure of the Wolf loses its former unambiguous meaning. The external enemy disappears; the conflict shifts toward the realm of social roles and masks.

In *Puss in Boots* (1995), although produced in the post-Soviet period, the inertia of Perestroika-era disillusionment is clearly perceptible: the collapse of the illusion of a “bright future” is accompanied by an anxious tone and the deformation of familiar narrative structures.

A similar line can be observed in the works of Priit Pärn. His film *Hotel E* (1992) is built upon the contrast between two spaces — an условный “West” and “East.” However, this opposition lacks the previous ideological clarity. The West appears simultaneously attractive and alienating, while the East is recognizable yet uncomfortable. The conflict ceases to be geopolitical and instead takes on an existential dimension.

Thus, the transformation of the enemy image can be summarized as follows:

- **1930s-1940s:** a concrete political opponent
- **1950s:** a reduced or displaced figure
- **1960s:** an aesthetically stylized image
- **1970s:** a cultural background
- **late 1980s:** an internal systemic problem

This process can be viewed within the broader context of the cultural Cold War. Research shows that ideological rivalry gradually shifted from direct propaganda into the sphere of cultural forms and artistic practices. In Soviet animation this shift became particularly visible: animation was among the first media to abandon the direct depiction of the enemy and move toward the use of aesthetic codes.

However, during Perestroika the collapse of previous institutional stability also led to the loss of the aesthetic distance that had allowed animation to function as an autonomous artistic space. Direct political expression came into tension with the previously developed language of artistic convention. This tension largely defines the specificity of late Soviet and early post-Soviet animation.

Conclusion

The analysis of the transformation of the enemy image in Soviet animation offers a new perspective on the influence of the Cold War on artistic language. Unlike live-action cinema, where ideological conflict retained a direct representational form for a long time, animation demonstrates a gradual aestheticization and increasing complexity of conflict.

The Cold War influenced Soviet animation not only through thematic constraints but also through changes in the function of artistic form itself. The external enemy first disappears from the narrative center, then transforms into a stylistic code, and during the Perestroika period gives way to an internal conflict.

Thus, the evolution of the enemy image in Soviet animation reflects a broader historical process: the transition from mobilizational ideology to cultural reflection and eventually to a critical reassessment of the system’s own values.

Due to its conventional nature and relative institutional flexibility, Soviet animation proved to be one of the most sensitive media in recording this transformation earlier than other forms of screen art.

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THE CHUVASH LANGUAGE IN EDUCATION: BRIDGING SCHOOL AND UNIVERSITY

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Abstract: *This article is the author's take on continuity in teaching the Chuvash language at different levels of education: from primary school to higher educational institutions of the Chuvash Republic. The study presents the results of an anonymous survey on a sample of 168 students from the I.N. Ulyanov Chuvash State University. The purpose of the study was to identify the motivation for studying the Chuvash language and using it in everyday communication. Since Chuvashia has a special linguistic situation with a predominance of the titular population, the authors of the article analyze the impact of federal and regional language policies on the teaching system of the Chuvash language. The survey shows the influence of life experience on the value profile of students regarding the positioning of the Chuvash language as necessary to learn or not necessary to learn. The authors point out the existing problems faced by teachers of the Chuvash language at the I.N. Ulyanov Chuvash State University: a lack of teaching materials and a decrease in student motivation. According to federal monitoring data from the Institute for the Development of Native Languages of the Peoples of the Russian Federation (2018-2019), there are no textbooks on the Chuvash language and Chuvash literature in the Federal List of Textbooks. Furthermore, the authors draw attention to the legal framework governing language policy in the region and the established practice of educational programs in Chuvashia. In conclusion,*

possible solutions to the identified problems are proposed to create effective system of ethno-cultural education.

Keywords: *the Chuvash language, continuity of education, language policy, ethno-cultural component, teaching materials, motivation, Chuvash Republic.*

Introduction. The Chuvash language is taught in six constituent entities of the Russian Federation - these are the Chuvash Republic, the Republics of Bashkortostan and Tatarstan, and the Kemerovo, Samara, and Ulyanovsk oblasts. In the Chuvash Republic, the Chuvash language has the status of a state language studied in a larger number of schools compared to other regions where it is taught in areas of compact settlement of the people [7]. In the Republic of Bashkortostan, Samara and Ulyanovsk oblasts, there are permanently functioning teacher associations for the native language. However, in the Chuvash Republic and the Republic of Tatarstan, where the majority of Chuvash language teachers are located, such teacher associations have not been identified (according to monitoring data from 2018-2019) [7].

The Chuvash language, being, alongside Russian, a state language of the Chuvash Republic, represents not only a means of everyday communication but also the fundamental basis of the cultural and national identity of the Chuvash people. The preservation and development of the language under conditions of globalization and intensifying assimilation processes are of interest for research in the fields of ethnolinguistics and language teaching methodology [5, 8]. Researchers who have studied the correlation between knowledge of the Chuvash language and overall academic performance for schoolchildren have found that knowledge of the Chuvash language has a positive effect, particularly on learning English [1].

A key role in the preservation and development of the Chuvash language is played by the education system, which is designed to ensure not only the study of the language as an academic subject but also the formation of a sustainable need for its use in a person's life. However, the effectiveness of this system directly depends on ensuring continuity between its various levels. By continuity in this context, we mean the consistent, uninterrupted, and progressive development of linguistic competencies, cultural knowledge, and the student's motivational sphere during the transition from one educational stage to another: from kindergarten to primary school, from primary to basic and secondary school, and then to institutions of secondary vocational and higher education. Continuity in education requires considering students' existing knowledge at each stage and focusing on developing skills that help them apply what they have learned as they progress [2]. A break at any of these stages leads to a sharp decrease in the effectiveness of all work on language preservation: "the current situation is characterized by the absence of a unified system and inconsistency of goals at different stages of

education” [4]. Thus, the problem of continuity in teaching the Chuvash language is systemic and requires comprehensive analysis and targeted actions from the state, the scientific-pedagogical community, and civil society.

Results and discussion. E.A. Kondrashkina identifies “two levels of language policy -- federal and regional. The regional level is adequate to the republican level, since in the republics the titular languages have the legal status of state languages, for which laws and various regulations are developed” [6]. As a result of the reforms of the 1990s, the Chuvash language was introduced as a compulsory subject in urban schools of Chuvashia (alongside Russian, Chuvash was proclaimed a state language of the Chuvash Republic). In national schools, because of the introduction of Russian, the Chuvash language recedes into the background, into the shadows, and is taught according to the curriculum of the disciplines “Chuvash Language” and “Chuvash Literature”. The legal basis for studying the Chuvash language in the republic is provided by several key documents. The Constitution of the Russian Federation (Article 68) guarantees all peoples of Russia the right to preserve their native language. These provisions are detailed more specifically in the Federal Law “On Education in the Russian Federation,” which establishes that preschool, primary general, and basic general education can be obtained in the native language from among the languages of the peoples of the Russian Federation. At the regional level, the fundamental laws are the laws of the Chuvash Republic “On Languages in the Chuvash Republic” and “On Education,” which consolidate the status of the Chuvash language as a state language and regulate its study in educational institutions [9, 10]. In accordance with these documents, the Chuvash language, either as a native language or as the state language of the republic, is a compulsory subject in the school curriculum. The process of implementing language policy in school education of the Chuvash Republic from 1980 to 2019 was not easy; it was accompanied by a misunderstanding of the mandatory nature of studying the Chuvash language in areas of the republic with an absolute predominance of the Russian population [3]. Today, several models for studying the Chuvash language in schools of Chuvashia can be distinguished:

1. Studying Chuvash as a native language. This model involves the deepest immersion in the language environment. Instruction follows programs designed for native speakers or children raised in Chuvash-speaking families. However, the number of such schools and classes is steadily declining, especially in urban areas.

2. Chuvash as the state language of the republic is the most widespread model. The Chuvash language is studied by all school students, regardless of nationality, typically for 1-2 hours per week. The main goal is the formation of basic communicative skills and an understanding of the culture of the Chuvash people. In urban schools, the study of the Chuvash language is conducted according to the choice of children, the choice being made by their legal representatives (parents). In 56

public schools of Cheboksary students in grades 5, 6, and 9 study Chuvash for one hour a week during the first half of the year. For grades 7 and 8, it is one hour a week for the entire school year. At the I.N. Ulyanov Chuvash State University, everyone studies Chuvash for one semester, even international students.

3. Ethno-cultural component within extracurricular activities. In some schools, the Chuvash language and culture are studied in clubs, electives, and during thematic events.

Despite the existing legal framework, the practical implementation of these models faces serious challenges. It is at the school stage that the foundation of language competencies is laid, and it is here that the main gaps are formed, hindering the transition to the next level of education. A significant issue is the lack of modern teaching materials. Existing textbooks and manuals on the Chuvash language are often outdated, lack appealing design, and do not take into account the psychological characteristics of modern children. The shortage of audio and video materials, interactive resources, and digital educational platforms makes the learning process ineffective and uninteresting for the “digital” generation.

The main problem is the lack of student motivation. For many schoolchildren, especially in cities, the Chuvash language is perceived as a “secondary” subject with no practical value outside the lesson. The absence of a living language environment, the weak representation of the Chuvash language in the media space (social networks), and the prestige of the Russian and English languages lead to low educational motivation. Therefore, there is a shortage of students choosing to study the Chuvash language as their profession, leading to a lack of young teachers of the Chuvash language and literature. It is the lack of prestige that discourages the younger generation from becoming Chuvash language teachers. Those currently in the profession are mostly older and, although they are native speakers, often lack the IT and communication skills necessary for today’s classroom. The authors of the article, as university lecturers, can state that in teaching the Chuvash language at non-linguistic faculties, there is no clear differentiation between programs for native speakers and for those for whom it is not a native language. This leads to all students having to study the same programs, which makes it boring for those for whom Chuvash is their native language, while others do not have time to assimilate the material. As a result, even after years of study most graduates still cannot speak Chuvash fluently or use it in a professional setting. Higher education has key functions in the continuous study of the Chuvash language — above all, training future teachers. The Faculty of Russian and Chuvash Philology trains teachers of the Chuvash language and literature. The quality of this training directly determines the future of school education. The I.N. Ulyanov Chuvash State University is a center for the scientific study of the Chuvash language: its grammar, dialectology, lexicology, history, and also develops new teaching methods,

publishes academic dictionaries and grammars, which should subsequently form the basis for school teaching materials. At the other faculties of the republic's university, the Chuvash language is studied as an elective discipline or within an ethno-cultural module. This helps non-philology students keep up their language skills, but continuity between school and university remains a problem. An applicant entering philological or pedagogical specialties related to the Chuvash language faces a paradoxical situation where school graduates, even from Chuvash-speaking families, come to university with extremely weak language preparation. They do not master orthographic and punctuation norms, have a poor vocabulary, and are unfamiliar with the basics of stylistics. University lecturers have to spend significant time filling the gaps in the school curriculum instead of moving forward. In Chuvashia there is practically no system of specialized classes or targeted contracts that would purposefully prepare schoolchildren for continuing their study of the Chuvash language at university. Work with gifted children in the field of Chuvash philology is sporadic rather than systemic. School textbooks and programs are poorly oriented towards forming the competencies necessary for successful university study. The prestige of the profession of a Chuvash language teacher and Chuvash philologist among young people is extremely low, leading to low competition for the corresponding specialties and, consequently, to problems with staffing the school itself in the future. Solving these problems requires action at the state, municipal, and institutional levels. Key measures include: developing new teaching materials tailored to different groups: native speakers, those learning Chuvash as a state language, and foreign students; introducing digital technologies — interactive online courses, mobile apps, and educational portals with video and audio materials. For this purpose, the ethno-cultural center “Nasledie” (Heritage) was established at the I.N. Ulyanov Chuvash State University in 2023. The center's venues include an exhibition hall with multimedia elements “Asam” (“Magic”), creative workshops “Shevle” (“Sunbeam”) and “Merchen” (“Pearl”). In particular, an interactive kiosk with electronic games helps students immerse themselves in the history of rituals, the Chuvash costume, cooking, and home arrangement, making it possible to include elements of the Chuvash language and culture in academic subjects of other cycles (history, pedagogy, psychology).

Stimulating motivation and creating a language environment remain the main problems in ensuring continuity in the study of the Chuvash language. To increase motivation for learning the Chuvash language at the I.N. Ulyanov Chuvash State University, youth projects and extracurricular activities are being developed: a theater studio, a media center, a blogger school, and holiday language camps. The system of olympiads, scientific-practical conferences, and competitions contributes to the targeted preparation of applicants and, ultimately, to the formation of a continuous “school-university” system. In order to study student motivation,

the authors of the article conducted a survey. The research sample included 168 first- and second-year students from those faculties of I.N. Ulyanov Chuvash State University where the authors of the article teach (Faculty of Foreign Languages, Faculty of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Medicine, and Faculty of Economics). Students participated in an anonymous survey according to the following instruction: “You are asked to answer 6 questions. Your answer should be extremely brief: yes/no.” The data was processed by calculating the arithmetic mean. The study was conducted anonymously, indicating only the course of study, and was carried out at the beginning of the first semester of the 2025-2026 academic year. The study involved students who are natives of Chuvashia and other regions where the Chuvash language is studied.

The questionnaire included the following questions:

1. Do you want to study the Chuvash language?
2. Do you want to see social media in the Chuvash language?
3. Do you see continuity in the study of the Chuvash language at school and university?
4. Would you like to see Chuvash brands? In what area: food, social media, clothing, etc.?
5. Do you know any existing Chuvash brands? Name them.
6. Do you see prospects for the use of the Chuvash language in Chuvashia? Give reasons for your answer.

The answers to the first question were almost evenly split -- 56% of respondents expressed a desire to study the Chuvash language, 44% answered “no”. To the second question of the questionnaire, 87% of respondents answered positively. To the third question, 98% of respondents answered affirmatively. We combined the answers to questions 4 and 5. The vast majority of respondents -- 98% -- spoke in favour of the presence of Chuvash brands in our lives. Here is the list of brands known to students: food: “Buket Chuvashii” (Bouquet of Chuvashia), “Akkond”, “Kēr Sāri”, “Akatur”, national dishes (shārtan, khuplu), pizzeria “Tukmak”, “ShaurMattur”, cafeterias “Tutlā”, “Yuldash”, “Khamār yal” (lit. khamār own + yal village, i.e., one’s own village; recently this expression has become popular among Russian-speaking youth and is used to mean “fellow countryman”); clothing: “Pakha Tērē”, “Pike”; residential complex “Yalav”, hotel “Suvar”, food market for local producers “Pekhet”; beauty salons “Ilemlē”, “Khitre”, Youth Theater “Sespeľ”. As for the last question, 91% of respondents gave an affirmative answer, arguing the prospects of the Chuvash language as follows: “The Chuvash language is alive as long as people speak it. And people still speak it: within the walls of our university we hear Chuvash speech every day, both from teachers and from our classmates.” The survey results were surprisingly positive. Although the authors had expected much lower interest, the data clearly shows that most students

value the Chuvash language and want to see it present in modern life — from social media to local brands. This suggests that young people are more open to engaging with their regional culture than is often assumed. The findings give reason for cautious optimism about the future of the Chuvash language.

Conclusions. The problem of continuity in the study of the Chuvash language is not just a pedagogical or methodological task, but a complex, interdisciplinary issue on which the preservation of a living, developing Chuvash language as an integral part of the nation's cultural code depends. The current gaps between school and university education undermine the effectiveness of the entire system. Overcoming them requires consolidated efforts from the legislative and executive authorities, the scientific and educational community, cultural figures, and the media. Investments in modern teaching materials, digital infrastructure, and support for talented teachers and motivated students are investments in the future of the Chuvash language and culture. A unified continuous educational and cultural space, where language learning is perceived not as an obligation but as an engaging and promising process, can thus ensure its transmission to future generations.

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CULTURE AS AN INTEGRAL PART OF THE LIFE OF SOCIETY

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Abstract. *A cultured person is one whose knowledge of the ethical principles and moral norms of society has transformed into an internal conviction, resulting in a moral sentiment. He acts not because he knows what ought to be done, but because he cannot act otherwise. A person's behavior is the expression of his way of life and actions. There can be no society without culture, nor culture without society.*

Keywords: *human being, culture, behavior and communication, transformative human activity.*

The human being is an integral whole, an organism endowed with both physical and mental functions. This holistic organism leads a unified life within an integrated world. It is well established that culture constitutes the entirety of humanity's achievements in the productive, social, intellectual, aesthetic, and physical domains. The basis of any culture is respect for the individual, as well as moral laws and principles.

It is natural that a cultured individual and their behavior are interconnected. However, the nature of this interconnection can vary qualitatively. Sometimes we say 'cultured behavior of a person,' and other times — 'behavior of a cultured individual.' It appears that these are by no means identical concepts.

Cultured behavior refers to a person's conduct in accordance with the norms that have been developed and are maintained by a particular society. These are certain manners, accepted ways of communication, and forms of addressing others that seemingly suggest how one should behave.

How to behave properly and gracefully at the table, be polite and considerate towards elders and women, be able to conduct oneself in society (both in familiar and less familiar settings), master the basics of behavior associated with professional ethics, and understand what is appropriate and inappropriate to do in a given environment. General culture implies a certain degree of literacy, a more or less broad range of interests and knowledge. External tidiness, kindness, and high moral integrity.

It can be stated that cultured behavior is behavior aligned with certain generally accepted norms. Such behavior reflects these norms and serves as their external manifestation. These norms may change — and consequently, manners of behavior will also change. The essential point

in the concept of ‘cultured behavior’ is the emphasis on conduct that must be cultured. A person is aware of the rules of cultured behavior and adheres to them.

Indeed, what exactly defines a cultured person. This is a person whose knowledge of ethical principles and moral norms of society has transformed into an internal conviction, resulting in a moral sentiment. He acts in this way not because he knows how one ought to act, but because he cannot act otherwise.

A cultured, well-mannered person is guided primarily not by the necessity to observe external rules, but by their conscience — a sense of moral responsibility for their behavior toward other people in society.

Even Marcus Aurelius said: “If you wanted to, you could not separate your life from humanity. You live in it, by it, and for it. We are all created for interaction, like legs, arms, and eyes.”

A person’s behavior is the expression of his way of life and actions. It is precisely through behavior that the essence of an individual’s personality, the distinctive traits of their character and temperament, as well as their needs, views, tastes, desires, and preferences, are revealed. We judge internal motivations, thoughts, and feelings solely by means of actions.

The peculiarities of our character and temperament, our needs, views, tastes, habits, desires, and the degree of our self-confidence or insecurity, among other aspects, are manifested in both behavior and communication. Emotions and feelings play a significant role in behavior.

Our behavior is determined by the moral norms and principles that regulate interpersonal relationships in society. The relationships between people themselves constitute the social norm of behavior. Therefore, each of our actions is usually related to the values accepted in the country and described as principled or unprincipled, noble or disgraceful.

Communication is a complex process of interaction between people, involving the exchange of information as well as the perception and understanding of one another by the participants. The subjects of communication are living beings, i.e., humans. In principle, communication is characteristic

of any living beings, but only at the human level does the process of communication become conscious, involving verbal and non-verbal acts.

Culture should be considered as the totality of all types of transformative activity of humans and society, as well as the results of this

activity embodied in material and spiritual values. Values are understood as material and ideal objects capable of satisfying certain

The needs of the individual, class, and society are to serve their interests and goals. The world of values is diverse; it includes natural, ethical, aesthetic, and other systems. Value systems are historical and generally hierarchical.

One of the highest levels of such hierarchies is occupied by universal human values. Emphasizing the distinction between material and spiritual values, many researchers differentiate between material and spiritual culture. Material culture is understood as the aggregate of material goods, the means and forms of their production, and the methods of their acquisition. Spiritual culture is defined as the aggregate of all knowledge, forms of thinking, ideological spheres (philosophy, ethics, law, politics, etc.), and forms of activity aimed at the creation of spiritual values.

It is essential to draw attention to one more important aspect — the social nature of culture. Culture is an integral aspect of social life; it is inseparable from humans as social beings. There can be no society without culture, just as there can be no culture without society. Therefore, the common understanding of culture, which we often encounter when we say: ‘This is an uncultured person; he is unaware of what culture is,’ is incorrect from a philosophical standpoint. By this, we usually mean that the person in question is ill-mannered or inadequately educated. However, from a philosophical perspective, a person is always cultured, for he is a social being, and

A society without culture does not exist. Regardless of how underdeveloped a given society may be, it always creates a corresponding culture, that is, a totality of material and spiritual values and the methods of their production. The extent of cultural development, however, may vary: it can be strong or weak, high or low. This extent depends on the specific historical stage of societal development, the conditions in which humanity evolves, and the resources it has at its disposal.

Culture is the cement of the building of social life. Not only because it is transmitted from one person to another through socialization and interactions with other cultures, but also because it fosters in people a sense of belonging to a particular group. Evidently, members of a single cultural group experience greater mutual understanding, trust, and empathy toward one another than

outsiders do. Their shared feelings are reflected in slang and jargon, favorite dishes, fashion, and other cultural aspects.

Culture not only reinforces solidarity among people but also serves as a source of conflicts within and between groups. This can be illustrated by the example of language, a key element of culture. On the one hand, the possibility of communication fosters the cohesion of members within a social group. A common language brings people together. On the other hand, a common language excludes those who do not speak it or who speak it somewhat differently.

In all societies, numerous subgroups exist that possess different cultural values and traditions. A system of norms and values distinguishing a group from the majority of society is called a subculture.

A subculture is shaped under the influence of factors such as social class, ethnic origin, religion, and place of residence.

The values of a subculture influence the personality formation of group members.

Culture is an integral part of human life. Culture organizes human life. In human life, culture largely performs the same function that genetically programmed behavior performs in animal life.

Every society, and at times its individual social groups, formulate certain regulatory principles of communication that are not only embedded in

the behavioral norms it has adopted, but are also cultivated in people with varying degrees of awareness. This provides grounds to affirm that there is a certain level of communication culture.

Culture is a broader concept than communication; it encompasses all material and spiritual values accumulated by humanity. Among other things, culture encompasses the ways of human activity — the circle of forms, techniques, and norms that characterize the specifics of society's functioning and without which its existence is impossible.

Communication between people is the most fundamental characteristic of distinctly human existence. Without it, activity, the formation and assimilation of spiritual values, as well as the development and formation of personality, are impossible. Communication accompanies these processes and contributes to their realization. However, the relationship between culture and any manifestations

of social life is ambiguous and complex. Communication is multifaceted primarily because it occurs on different levels: countries and peoples, collectives, and

individuals can communicate, and accordingly, the interaction between the parties in this process will vary in its social significance. Furthermore, communication can manifest in different ways: it can be direct or indirect, vary by type, and, ultimately, during the process, people can exchange thoughts, feelings, experiences, labor skills, and so forth. This multifaceted nature of communication is connected to the fact that it is based on social relations. Since these encompass various aspects of society's functioning, they represent the specific types of socio-economic, political, legal, and moral relations characteristic of this formation. Ultimately, these relations constitute the content of communication.

Finally, communication regulates the level of emotional tension, creates psychological discharge, and ultimately forms the emotional background on which our activity takes place and which to a significant extent defines our fundamental worldview.

Every society, and at times even its individual social groups, develop certain regulatory principles of communication, which are not only established in the accepted norms of behavior but are also cultivated in individuals with varying degrees of consciousness. This provides grounds to affirm that there is a certain level of communication culture.

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THE ROLE OF HISTORICAL TEXT IN BUILDING A MODEL OF A HISTORICAL EVENT BY A SOCIAL SUBJECT

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Abstract. *This article examines the rational component of the process of constructing a model of a historical event through the appropriation of the informational component of the historical text. In their work, the authors define the specifics of synthesizing rationalist and hermeneutic approaches in constructing a model of a socio-historical event, and also analyze the structural characteristics of the historical text as an object of social-philosophical discourse.*

Keywords: *narrative substance; explanandum; explanans, causality, teleology, understanding, explanation, intention, cultural-historical tradition.*

One of the main problems in the philosophy of history is the issue of how a social subject forms hermeneutic experience based on understanding certain historical events as reflected in narrative sources.

Currently, the question of the nature of a social subject's understanding of a historical event is acquiring particular significance. This can be explained by the fact that people often need to refer back to past historical experience in order to reinterpret and adapt it to the present. In this context, it becomes necessary to study the historical text that reflects a specific event. Examining the specifics of constructing a model of a historical event through historical text helps to achieve greater objectivity in evaluating the phenomenon under investigation.

Studies on this issue have been carried out by foreign researchers such as G. von Wright, F. Ankarsmith, C. Hempel, K. Popper, M. Heidegger, A. Whitehead, and others. For example, F. Ankersmit dedicated several of his works to the genre of historical text known as narrative. In these, he evaluates various approaches to defining the ideal narrative, examining the structure of the narrative by identifying narrative subjects and narrative substances [1].

A significant contribution to the development of this topic was also made by R. Collingwood and M. White, who distinguished between ‘chronicle’ and ‘history,’ thereby contrasting cause and purpose. In this regard, the works of G. von Wright should be noted, in which models of constructing explanations of human behavior and events are examined. Hempel, in his works, investigates the principles and regularities of constructing explanations, primarily based on the deductive-nomological model.

Within Russian scholarship, the problem of understanding — specifically, the definition of levels of understanding and the identification of their peculiarities — was studied by researchers such as G. I. Ruzavin, V. G. Kuznetsov, M. Ya. Mikulenskaya, and A. P. Alekseev. The works of V. I. Svintsov, A. I. Rakitov, V. V. Belyaev, and others are dedicated to the structural features of the text from the standpoint of rationality. The semiotic aspects of text structure have been examined in the works of Yu. Lotman, V. Z. Demyankov, S. S. Gusev, and others.

Philosophical literature analyzes the nature of understanding historical events. In our view, such understanding should possess a dialogical nature. According to the assertions of M. Heidegger, the knowing subject must ‘inquire’ into the understood event, period, or epoch [7, p. 208]. One of the criteria for effective understanding in this context, as G. Gadamer argued, is the ‘breadth of the horizon’ of the knowing subject, whose extent is determined by experience, axiological orientations, goals of understanding, the emphasis placed during the understanding process, and other parameters [2, p. 357]. In this case, according to the authors of the study, it is appropriate to refer to the philosophy of existentialism, particularly E. Husserl’s phenomenology, since it is crucial to trace how the subject experiences a given historical event [4]. In some instances, if the subject is a contemporary, they partially cognize the historical event directly. However, in most cases, it is necessary to resort to an intermediary, namely the text. The informational criterion is also a factor that determines the effectiveness of understanding. However, there is another difficulty. Within the framework of the historical text, events are represented as refracted through the author’s standpoint. In this case, the cognizing subject must bear in mind that it is the event itself that should be understood, rather than the author’s stance towards the described event. The rational component of understanding historical time includes the levels of perception of the historical event by the cognizing subject, as well as the regularities governing information acquisition. One such regularity is the concept of the logic of events, presented by A. N. Whitehead [8, p. 73]. The rational component will also consist in constructing an explanation of understood historical events. This is a very important point, since constructing an explanation of a historical event involves two primary approaches: causal and teleological. The choice of the approach to constructing the explanation

of a historical event will be determined by the goals and objectives set by the cognizing subject during the process of understanding.

The rational component will also manifest itself in identifying internal relationships between specific historical events, drawing parallels between events, and identifying similar historical events.

The theoretical and methodological foundation of the research consists of general philosophical principles and methods, such as the principle of systematicity, the principle of comprehensiveness, and the principle of concreteness.

The research is also based on the following social-philosophical methods: the concrete-historical method; the historical-retrospective method; the comparative-historical method; and the method of historical and logical unity in social cognition.

The study relies on concepts synthesizing rationalistic and hermeneutic approaches to the process of modeling a historical event, clarifying the specificity of the hermeneutic approach in examining a socio-historical event through historical text. It is assumed that at the contemporary stage of development in the philosophy of history and social philosophy, the hermeneutic approach facilitates the understanding of a particular historical event depending on the informational context. Furthermore, the hermeneutic approach allows for tracing the social subject's experience of a historical event, the result of which is its understanding.

One of the sources for forming hermeneutic experience is the historical text, which functions as a mediator between the social subject and the historical event described in the text [2]. However, in the process of forming hermeneutic experience, the social subject must evaluate the author's understanding of the event presented in the narrative, assess the event described in the historical source, and finally, evaluate the historical source itself. According to which criteria will such an evaluation be conducted by the social subject? This aspect is very important because evaluation is the result of the process of understanding. In this case, one addresses the issues related to the execution of the process of understanding. In particular, one of them concerns the nature of understanding an event, namely, how should a given event be understood — from the standpoint of causality or from the standpoint of teleology? The fact is that some texts explain a certain event from the perspective of causality, other texts may explain the same event from the perspective of teleological purpose, while other texts, such as historical chronicles or a narrative, contain only a factual statement of the event. In this regard, the question arises: how does a particular type of narrative influence the formation of the hermeneutic experience of the social subject? In this case, aspects such as the nature of the historical text, its structure, the structure of the historical event depicted in the text, the degree of reliability of the information presented, and other factors become prominent. It is also important to assess the impact of temporality on the formation of the hermeneutic experience by the social subject.

The application of hermeneutic methods in the process of understanding a historical event requires engagement with the fundamental theoretical principles of hermeneutics. The problem of the rational component in understanding a historical event involves addressing various aspects of the theory of rationality. The issue of interpreting already existing historical experience and relating it to ongoing events at the current stage of development gives rise to the problem of the significance of a particular historical event both within a specific temporal stage of historical development and within the entire historical process as a whole.

The examination of the features of the influence of historical text on the construction of the model of a historical event presupposes a systematic analysis of this construction within the framework of social-philosophical knowledge, enabling the study of rationalist and hermeneutic characteristics in the interpretation of a socio-historical event through historical text.

The nature of the initial stages in modeling a historical event is conditioned by the informational context of the narrative source, as hermeneutic principles enable transcending the confines of logical-semantic analysis and the use of logical pragmatics.

Various types of historical texts, while retaining their linguistic structure, possess differentiated semantic components and, as a result, differ in their content structure. The process of understanding socio-historical reality through a particular type of historical text is partly determined by its structural and content characteristics.

The specificity of the hermeneutic approach consists in the subject's ability to reconstruct the historical event that took place through the historical text, while distinguishing the author's personal evaluation of this event from its objective characteristics [5]. The experience of a certain historical event represents a process of information processing in the consciousness of the social subject, conditioned by their axiological orientations, goals of understanding, and other parameters.

The process of understanding any historical event through a text depends on its structural and content features, since a historical text is the author's reinterpretation of a specific segment of historical reality.

Thus, the model of understanding a historical event, constructed by a social subject through narrative, will to a certain degree reflect their personal viewpoint, subjective perception, and assessment. Moreover, in most cases, the position of the author of the narrative source exerts a significant influence on the social subject's comprehension of the event under study. Theoretical and epistemological aspects indicate a certain universality of the hermeneutic approach from the perspective of the ontology of understanding, which is grounded in questions concerning the meaning of historical existence.

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UDC 130.2

PARAMETERS OF THE AXIOLOGICAL COMPONENT IN GLOBAL AND LOCAL CULTURAL TRANSFORMATION PROCESSES

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Abstract. *It is demonstrated that within the philosophical reflection on human existence and culture, in the axiological paradigm, two opposing viewpoints have emerged. The first asserts that contemporary society is experiencing a crisis of humanity and culture, the onset of which is attributed to the specific nature of the modern type of civilization (technological and informational). Another point of view, conversely, posits the existence of conditions that open up unique opportunities for cultural and spiritual growth of the individual, serving as a guarantee for overcoming the cultural crisis.*

Keywords: *culture, cultural identity, national culture, axiology, value orientations, globalization.*

The most important trends in the development of modern society associated with the process of globalization are expected to exert a significant and multifaceted impact on many components of the humanitarian sphere of society. The totality of these influences will constitute the main content of that new general civilizational phenomenon, which is becoming increasingly evident today and which can be qualified with sufficient grounds as a new humanitarian revolution. The development of this revolution is to be expected in the 21st century. It is already completely clear today that this revolution will lead not only to radical changes in the realms of education, science, and culture, but will also significantly transform the human worldview, his attitude toward nature, toward himself, and toward culture.

Today, it is essential to acknowledge that globalization processes are multifaceted and affect all spheres of human life (economic, political, cultural, social, and spiritual), becoming a new horizon that redefines an established system such as culture, altering its fundamental humanistic values, norms, and traditions. However, in the context of globalization, the interaction between the individual, society, and

culture itself must be considered in relation to cultural-philosophical standards, which consequently prompts the search for new universal values.

Globalization processes, within the context of the proposed research topic, are understood as processes of cultural transformation aimed at facilitating the adjustment and integration of various forms of activity (technological, economic, cultural, informational) to achieve a synthesis of civilizations while preserving the multiplicity of diverse cultures. Globalization cannot be actualized without transforming the overarching paradigm of human development, entailing a qualitative modification of the axiological foundations and cultural practices. “Today, the most important factor in such a synthesis should be information culture as the fundamental core for the accumulation of socio-cultural changes in contemporary society. ... it, first and foremost, tends toward transformation, determining the priorities and directions of the transformation of the entire culture” [4, p.137]. However, whereas globalization in the economic sphere is perceived as natural and unforced, cultural globalization is a more complex process due to the diversity of cultural forms.

The studies of globalization from various cultural, economic, and political perspectives are dedicated to the works of foreign scholars such as Ulrich Beck, Manuel Castells, Giovanni Chiesa, and Francis Fukuyama, as well as domestic researchers including M. Bakhtin, M. Kagan, N. Lossky, V. Tugarinov, and others. These authors analyzed the systematization of global challenges and the classification of global problems facing humanity that emerged at the turn of the 20th to the 21st centuries, problems that threaten the very survival of humanity. Analyzing global historical and cultural processes, we note the following. These processes have a long and complex history and are connected with globalization processes occurring within society, aimed at the unification and integration of various countries, peoples, and cultures into a single global economic, political, and cultural space.

In the 20th century, cultural globalization processes have been specifically associated with Americanization; the widespread dissemination of cultural traditions and principles assumed the form of their imposition. American culture is imposed as a universal one. This phenomenon has been termed the “Americanization” of culture. It becomes evident that such unification of culture may lead to the loss of its diversity, to the disappearance of the cultural heritage of many small peoples and nations. A legitimate question may arise: do national cultures truly have no alternative, and are they all destined for the same outcome — absorption into today’s dominant cultural forms, loss of their own distinctiveness and significance, leveling, and depersonalization? We are firmly convinced that this is not the case. Culture does not admit defeat. It is founded upon the values of national culture and traditions. Under no circumstances should the values of national culture be undermined, since the ability to remain true to oneself and to preserve one’s cultural distinctiveness and identity (which defines the capacity to perceive the world and

the essence of being within it) determines the successful integration of national culture into the global cultural space. National culture can and must cultivate the individual based on the values intrinsic to that culture. Thus, through ‘the cultural identity of a person there manifests universal human culture’ [2, p.144].

We are interested in the perspective of T. V. Lugutsenko in her work ‘Paradigmatic Shift of Culture in the Process of Transformation of Cultural Space’. The author demonstrates that conducting a philosophical analysis of the mechanisms, forms, and consequences of the actualization of cultural heritage necessitates understanding the direction of the evolutionary vector of cultural space in the era of the global civilizational transition. Culture is a fundamental manifestation of the intentionality of human consciousness as the aspiration to incorporate the past into the present, not simply reproducing it but renewing its semantic core and constituting its new significance for the formation of the culture of the future. It is precisely in this dynamic of continuous rethinking and re-actualization that one of the essential mechanisms conditioning the paradigmatic shift of culture in the process of transformations of the cultural space of contemporary society is concealed. ... In the context of contemporary society, characterized by the unprecedented speed of socio-cultural transformations, fragmentation of the discursive space, and the search for new metanarratives, the actualization of cultural heritage becomes not merely a methodological device, but an existential necessity that shapes new contours of cultural identity and opens horizons for innovative development” [5, p. 226].

Today, culture must be understood as a decisive dimension of globalization, rather than merely a response to economic globalization. We are discussing the culture of societies whose social structures are founded upon traditional spiritual values with a sufficiently long history of civilizational development. These include societies with an unbroken tradition of shaping their national mentality and way of life. An analysis of social history demonstrates that one of the most crucial conditions for the existence and further development of culture is the capacity for exchanging spiritual values. In each new generation, an individual becomes a person only through the assimilation of the cultural wealth of all humanity. Personality is formed through interaction with other people and through the internalization of cultural values.

The identification of new contexts of a person’s cultural identity depends on the key stages of development of their subjective qualities and abilities: self-identification, self-determination, and self-realization. At the same time, ideals, values, norms, and traditions that ensure the stability of the vector of continuity and dynamics of socio-cultural development are determined by the essence of human culture, which integrates the individual’s inner world with the external world (coherence). Therefore, the upbringing of the individual, together with the active social practice of society itself (under the influence of globalization), pertains to the most essential methods of cultural and spiritual socialization. This defines the purposeful

interdependence between the individual and society and creates favorable conditions for the 'creative spirituality' (I. A. Chernykh) of the individual.

Contemporary cultural practices, as one of the processes of personality formation, transform not only the lifestyle of the individual but also create potential conditions for changing the very understanding of the 'cultural meaning of life'. The study of cultural parameters within the global processes of contemporary reality cannot be conducted without reference to value orientations, which must be examined in relation to life values. It is necessary to highlight certain approaches to defining the structure of value orientation both as a phenomenon of consciousness and as a system of human value orientations amid global societal transformations:

- the issue of personality formation (N. Berdyaev, I. Kant, L. Tolstoy, A. Schweitzer);
- social influence on the individual in the process of their development (M. Weber, P. Sorokin);
- analysis of the specificity of value relations historically developed within socio-cultural systems (A. Zdravomyslov, N. V. Berezhnaya, I. A. Chernykh);
- functioning of normative value mechanisms regulating human cultural orientations (T. V. Lugutsenko, N. S. Pichko, V. B. Popov);
- general issues concerning the place and role of cultural values within the system of social relations (T. V. Lugutsenko, S. G. Pechenikova, O. M. Shevchenko).

The establishment of axiology as a branch of the philosophy of culture is associated with the following approaches: the objectivist (N. Hartmann, G. Rickert, M. Scheler) and the subjectivist (G. Schwarz, H. Ehrenfels), which constitute theoretical, worldview, and methodological foundations for the absolutization of the concept of 'value,' as well as for the development of value orientations, value attitudes, and their interpretations. According to the subjectivist approach, value is a good that is perceived by the individual through the lens of subjective evaluation, conditioned by their needs, which engenders 'axiological relativism' (N. Hartmann, E. Husserl, R. Ingarden, M. Scheler) in the understanding of values.

However, contemporary studies of cultural reality and the challenges of overcoming the crisis of cultural identity address the issues of the confrontation between modern axiological contradictions and the clashes of cultural value orientations within philosophical schools (G. V. Grebenkov, T. V. Lugutsenko, I. A. Chernykh). In the works of the aforementioned authors, the conceptualization of cultural identity is undertaken within the framework of contemporary axiological contradictions of the fundamental value orientations of culture. The authors focus on those values that are fundamental not only to the culture of the region but also universal — civilizational values that represent the worldview of humanism. The studies by G. V. Drach, F. V. Lazarev, T. V. Lugutsenko, and others are dedicated to the examination of cultural paradigms and the identification of key sociocultural determinants that can

facilitate the overcoming of cultural contradictions engendered by globalization. Thus, the axiological approach consolidates numerous properties of culture around the concept of 'values of culture, cultural values,' which internally determine what we call the culture of peoples and societies, and it is precisely in this manner that values become the core of a particular culture. Contemporary axiology, as an integral component of the philosophy of culture, examines the processes of identity formation, accentuating its axiological foundation, the principal criterion of which is the conformity of the individual's understanding of value and ideal to the societal worldview (E. I. Petrova).

It is important to emphasize that in the formation of personality, the motivational structures of cultural activities determine the upper limit of an individual's socio-cultural aspirations, whereas norms — determine only the average level. At the same time, the functional distinctions between norms and values (I. A. Chernykh) reveal the dialectical unity of values and norms, as well as the specific features on the basis of which the normative-value paradigm of personality is formed. This thereby defines the parameters of culture in global and local transformative processes, both of the individual's (one's) self-determination and society as a whole.

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